

Exploring the influence of parents, socioeconomic status and healthy homework on children's activity and body mass index.

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A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the West of Scotland for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy

August 2020

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Publications and communications

The work in this thesis has been disseminated in the following publications and communications:

Peer-reviewed published research

Donnelly, S., Buchan, D.S., McLellan, G., & Arthur, R. (2019) An Insight into Mothers of Low Socio-Economic Status' Involvement in Scottish Primary Schools. Health Education and Behaviour. Vol. 47(1), pp 111-122.

Donnelly, S., Buchan, D.S., McLellan, G., & Arthur, R. (2020) Use of novel metrics to explore accelerometry data in parent-child dyads. Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport. Vol. 25, pp 1-9.

Research papers under review

Donnelly, S., Buchan, D.S., McLellan, G., & Arthur, R. (Under second review) Examining indirect effects of socioeconomic status on children health indicators operating via their parent's moderate-to-vigorous physical activity and body mass index. Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport.

Conference communications

Donnelly, S., Buchan, D.S., Gibson, A. M., & Arthur, R. (2018) An insight into parent involvement in Scottish Primary School Health Education activities. Presented at 7th International Society for Physical Activity and Health Congress. London, UK, October.

Donnelly, S., Buchan, D.S., McLellan, G., & Arthur, R. (2019) Examining indirect effects of socioeconomic status on children health indicators operating via their parent's moderate-to-vigorous physical activity and body mass index. Presented at The British Association of Sport and Exercise Sciences (BASES) Student Conference. Dundee, UK, April.

Abstract

Childhood obesity is one of the most severe public health problems of the 21st Century, with inactivity proving to be one of leading determinants of obesity prevalence. Parents are known to influence children's activity and their involvement in interventions aiming to evoke positive health behaviour change is encouraged. Researchers have struggled to recruit parents with low socioeconomic status (SES) to interventions aiming to foster such positive health behaviour and as a result, children with low SES are not exposed to the positive outcomes associated with many interventions. The school setting has been recognised as an ideal environment for health-related population-based interventions for decades, as it provides access and benefit to families from all risk groups, particularly those with limited or no access to play areas and avoids stigmatization of at-risk children. As such, this thesis aimed to capture the perspectives of parents to inform the design of an intervention which will aim to encourage parent involvement from all backgrounds. Furthermore, the thesis aimed to examine the relationship between parent-child PA using robust, novel approaches and the indirect influence SES has on children's PA and body mass index (BMI) through parental factors. Ultimately, such findings will inform the design of a homework-based intervention theoretically underpinned and informed by end-user's experiences using mixed-method approaches. The studies within this thesis have adopted various methodological approaches to rigorously explore the issues surrounding previous school-based interventions which aim to foster health-conducive behaviours (e.g., increase PA and healthy eating), however fail to capture less motivated parents of low SES. Additionally, the studies within this thesis aimed to examine the relationship between parent and child PA using novel and robust methods in order to subsequently inform the design of a school-based intervention involving parents, aiming to improve children's health behaviours. Chapter 4 (Study 1) found that mothers with low SES and low involvement in school-based health activities face several barriers in

becoming involved in such activities, particularly due to issues surrounding the parent council and exclusivity of school-based events. Efforts made by the school to promote health activities and involve parents in such activities were revealed, alongside recommendations to improve upon these practices, including parent-child joint activities and home-based activities. Chapter 5 (Study 2) demonstrated that weekend parent and child moderate-to-vigorous PA (MVPA) was significantly related, similarly to parent and child BMI. A direct effect of SES on child BMI z-score was observed. A significant negative indirect effect of SES on child BMI z-score via parent BMI was also found. Associations in parent and child MVPA during the weekend were observed however, there were no associations between SES and MVPA in parent or child groups. Use of novel activity metrics were applied to further explore the relationship of parent and child PA using more comparable accelerometry methods in Chapter 6 (Study 3). These metrics included average acceleration (AvAcc) and the intensity gradient (IG) and were used to assess the relationship between parent and child activity. Findings from this chapter showed that girls BMI-z scores were positively associated with parent inactive time and parent BMI. Parent BMI was negatively associated with boy's inactive time. Parental inactive time, when adjusted, predicted girls BMI-z scores. The activity metrics were not associated with parent BMI, and no independent effects were observed between the metrics. Associations between boys IG and BMI z-score were observed in the unadjusted model, and when adjusted. When the model was adjusted further for the alternative metric, this association was not observed. No independent effects were observed between the two metrics and no significant associations were observed between boys BMI z-score and AvAcc. For girls, no significant associations were observed between AvAcc and IG with BMI z-score and no independent effects were observed between the two metrics. In summary, our study revealed no significant associations in parent-child activity using the AvAcc and IG metrics. However, we found that girls BMI z-score was positively associated

with parent inactive time per day and parent BMI. Informed with the findings from the studies outlined in Chapters 4-6, Chapter 7 (Study 4) detailed the feasibility and primary effectiveness of the Happy Homework (HH) intervention. HH was found to improve activity and sedentary behaviour (SB) in children in 8 weeks, with each outcome indicating a large effect size (≥ 0.14). Furthermore, this intervention was deemed appropriate in the recruitment and retainment of less-involved parents with low SES. Taken together, this thesis contributes original research findings to inform future health-related interventions involving parents further, aiming to bridge the gap between the home and school for health promotion in children.

Acknowledgments

There are many people I would like to thank who have helped support me over the last three or so years of my PhD studies. Firstly, I would like to thank all of the children, parents and teachers who took part in my research. Without their participation none of the studies detailed in this thesis would have been possible.

A special thanks goes to my supervisors, Dr Rosemary Arthur and Dr Duncan Buchan, as well as Dr Anne-Marie Knowles from the University of Strathclyde, for their continued support and guidance as well as offering their expertise to enable me to go the extra mile. I would also like to thank my fellow PhD colleague and great friend, Gillian McLellan. When we both started working together over four years ago whilst undertaking a Masters in Research, we both never imagined we would get to continue our work into a PhD, and even better, we got to do it together. The help you provided during data collection will always be remembered.

On a personal note, words cannot express the gratitude I have for my family (especially my mum, Angela), my boyfriend Gary, and my friends for their encouragement and support during my studies. Jordan, not only have you been a great brother to me, you have also made a supportive fellow PhD candidate. We have shared such a personal experience together whilst undertaking our PhD studies together and I hope we have made our family proud.

Declaration

I declare that the content presented in this thesis is original work, conducted and written by the author, and has not been submitted previously for another academic degree at any institution. This thesis is being submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy.

Personal details withheld.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
Active for Life Year 5	AFLY5
AvAcc	Average acceleration
ANCOVA	Analysis of Covariance
ANOVA	Analysis of variance
BMI	Body mass index (kg/m ²)
CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
CI	Confidence interval
CVD	Cardiovascular disease
DILQ	Day in the Life Questionnaire
EE	Energy expenditure
ENMO	Euclidean Norm Minus One
FIQ-E	Family Involvement Questionnaire – Elementary
FFQ	Food frequency questionnaire
h	Hour(s)
HH	Happy Homework
HWB	Health and wellbeing
IG	Intensity gradient
LPA	Light physical activity
MET	Metabolic equivalents
mg	Milli-gravitational units
mins	Minutes
MRC	Medical Research Council
MS	Metabolic syndrome

MVPA	Moderate-to-vigorous physical activity
M2 _{ACC}	Minimum acceleration above which a person's most active 2 mins
M30 _{ACC}	Minimum acceleration above which a person's most active 30 mins
M60 _{ACC}	Minimum acceleration above which a person's most active 60 mins
<i>n</i>	Sample size
NCD's	Non-communicable diseases
NHANES	National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey
PA	Physical activity
SB	Sedentary behaviour
SES	Socioeconomic status
SD	Standard deviation
SDT	Self-determination Theory
SIMD	Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation
SSB	Sugar-sweetened beverages
ST	Screen time
TV	Television viewing
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America
VIF	Variance inflation factor
WDST	Write, draw, show and tell
WHO	World Health Organization
WTC	Wear time criteria

CHAPTER 1

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the problem

Childhood obesity is one of the most severe public health problems of the 21st Century (World Health Organization, 2018a). The 10-fold increase in obesity prevalence from 11 million to 124 million seen in children and adolescents over the last four decades is undoubtedly concerning for several reasons (World Health Organization, 2018a). For instance, overweight and obese children are more likely to develop several adverse health conditions including asthma, bone and joint problems, type 2 diabetes and hypertension at a younger age (Biesma and Hanson, 2020). The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) suggest that overweight and obese children are also likely to stay obese in adulthood, further exacerbating the likelihood of developing health problems including diabetes and cardiovascular disease (CVD) (Bass and Eneli, 2015, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2016). Due to the increasing number of childhood obesity cases worldwide and the subsequent health consequences related with obesity, identifying the risk factors associated with childhood obesity is vital.

Regular physical activity (PA) is associated with several health benefits in children including a reduced risk of developing heart disease, cancer, type 2 diabetes and obesity (US Department of Health and Human Services, 2018). It is not surprising that physical inactivity has been identified as the fourth leading risk factor for global mortality, with major implications for the prevalence of non-communicable diseases (NCD's) and the general health of individuals worldwide (World Health Organization, 2018a). As such, many governments and leading organizations recommend that children should accumulate at least 60 minutes (mins) of moderate-to-vigorous PA (MVPA) daily (US Department of Health and Human Services, 2018, Australian Government Department of Health, 2019, UK Chief Medical Officer, 2019). The majority of children's daily PA should be aerobic, with vigorous-intensity activities incorporated, including those that strengthen muscle and bone, at

least 3 times per week. By meeting such guidelines, children will develop: a healthy cardiovascular system, healthy musculoskeletal tissues, neuromuscular awareness including coordination, and maintain a healthy body weight (World Health Organization, 2018a).

Despite the well-established health benefits of meeting these PA guidelines, most children fail to meet these recommendations. Indeed, recent findings provided by a Global Matrix (3.0) from 49 Countries indicated that for overall PA, Scottish children, as well as those from Belgium, China, South Korea, and Taiwan, received an “F” grade in meeting the recommended guidelines (Aubert et al., 2018). This grade constitutes that very few children (<20%) are meeting the 60 mins of MVPA per day guideline (Aubert et al., 2018).

Furthermore, a recent study exploring the global trends of PA from 1.6 million youths from 146 countries also found that 81% of youths were insufficiently physically active (Guthold et al., 2019). It is important therefore to explore the determinants which may influence children’s PA levels, and subsequently their weight status, in order to design effective interventions that will improve children and adolescent’s health and wellbeing (HWB).

Children with low socioeconomic status (SES) often fail to meet recommended MVPA guidelines, with rates of childhood obesity disproportionately affecting those in the lowest SES groups (Gidlow et al., 2006, Moraes et al., 2012, Tremblay et al., 2014). This may be explained by families with low SES often having less access to facilities and resources in order to be active (Thompson et al., 2010, Holt et al., 2011). It should be noted however that research exploring the influence of SES on PA typically has a limited quantity of primary studies, weak research designs and lack of accuracy in the PA and SES assessment methods employed (O’Donoghue et al., 2018). Nevertheless, parental SES has been found to significantly predict the MVPA of children (Mutz and Albrecht, 2017). As such, further exploration of the role parents and SES play in the levels of activity in children is encouraged.

It is widely accepted that parents play a significant role in influencing children's health behaviours (Kaplan et al., 2014). Indeed, parent support to be active and parents own PA levels have been shown to affect the activity-related behaviours of their children (Tandon et al., 2014; Trost & Loprinzi, 2011; Yao & Rhodes, 2015). Nevertheless, studies examining the relationship between parent and child PA have provided contrasting findings with some suggesting that parents PA does not directly influence their child's PA (Pfeiffer et al., 2009, Jago et al., 2010, Dowda et al., 2011). In light of equivocal findings, a recent systematic review noted that half of the studies investigating parent and child PA used questionnaires to estimate parental PA (Petersen et al., 2020). Given the substantial amount of variance not shared between self-reported and more objective methods (e.g., accelerometers), objective and self-report measures of PA are not interchangeable (Petersen et al., 2020). This suggests that the choice of method to assess PA in both parents and children should be the same for both groups, which many studies fail to achieve (Petersen et al., 2020). Moreover, ambiguity in study findings may also be explained by the use of pedometers and the reporting of different PA intensities such as MVPA and overall PA (Trost and Loprinzi, 2011, Craig, Cameron and Tudor-Locke, 2013, Stearns et al., 2016). The methods used to assess PA in parents and children tend to be self-reported or involve pedometers. The use of subjective methods within this area of research increases the ambiguity of findings as subjective measures of PA are prone to recall bias (Chinapaw et al., 2010). Furthermore, pedometers have been found to be inaccurate in assessing distance covered and energy expended (Ndahimana and Kim, 2017). It remains clear that more research is needed using comparable methods to accurately determine the relationship between parent and child PA.

The school setting has been recognised as an ideal environment for population-based PA interventions as it provides access and benefit to families from all risk groups, particularly those with limited or no access to play areas (Harrell et al., 1996, McKenzie et

al., 1996). A multitude of school-based health interventions have been implemented globally to tackle childhood inactivity, however recently, findings from meta-analyses have found that many of these interventions have demonstrated no improvements in MVPA or sedentary behaviour (SB) (Love, Adams and Sluijs, 2018, Jones et al., 2020). Various school-based interventions have found success by employing a multicomponent framework, being underpinned by theoretical models of behaviour change, and involving parents (Sluijs, McMinn and Griffin, 2007, Contento, 2008, Kriemler et al., 2011). Additionally, school-based interventions have found success by encouraging participants to engage in health-related homework tasks outside school time (Duncan et al., 2011, 2019) however, these are limited in number. Whilst these homework tasks have shown positive intervention effects in activity levels, such studies have assessed PA through pedometers (Duncan et al., 2011, 2019). As previously highlighted, further discrepancies exist in research findings when employing objective and subjective measures of PA. Taken together, the findings from previous research in this field highlights the importance to accurately monitor and examine the activity levels of participants using robust and objective methods, given that this measure is how many researchers quantify whether their interventions are effective. Additionally, future research is warranted to fully understand the relationship between SES and parent and child activity and as such, design and implement effective interventions informed by accurate interpretations of such research.

1.2 Accelerometry

Accelerometry is widely accepted as the current best practice technique for measuring free-living PA in adults and children (Ridgers and Fairclough, 2011). Nevertheless, comparing findings between studies that use different accelerometer devices, different cut-points and different methodologies is challenging. For instance, the lack of transparency in study protocols and accelerometer processing decisions make drawing direct

comparisons challenging (Strutz et al., 2018, Rowlands, Plekhanova, et al., 2019). Indeed, ambiguous wear time criteria (WTC) (or failure to report WTC at all) is evident (Yao and Rhodes, 2015, Strutz et al., 2018). Moreover, PA intensity information is usually expressed as time spent within cut-points that have typically been derived using validation studies (Rowlands et al., 2018). Cut-points are heavily dependent on the study protocol used to derive the cut-points and the calibration sample which has been found to lead to problems comparing outcomes across populations and studies (Troiano et al., 2014). As such, the validity of these outcomes is dependent not only on the validity of the measure used to calculate acceleration, but also on the validity of the algorithm. Such outcomes fail to incorporate activity movements expressed over a 24-hour (h) period. As such, future efforts to construct a metric(s) which does not limit the data by cut-points and is transparent are warranted (Rowlands et al., 2018). Cut-point free accelerometry research is increasing through the use of novel accelerometry metrics such as average acceleration (AvAcc) and the intensity gradient (IG) (Rowlands et al., 2018). These recent developments in accelerometry research represent a move towards directly comparable outcomes which in turn may reduce equivocality in research exploring activity between populations and devices (Rowlands et al., 2018, Fairclough, Taylor, Rowlands and Boddy, 2019, Rowlands, Plekhanova, et al., 2019). Given how recent these new metrics are, there is a need for further research exploring the effectiveness of interventions which aim to improve outcomes within these metrics.

Participant compliance in accelerometry research can be challenging. For instance, findings from a study detailing the rules, variables and definitions applied to accelerometer data in the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES), 2003-2006, found that only around 25% of participants provided the requested 7 days of data, which was mostly attributed to the discomfort or inconvenience of wearing a device on the hip over time and

forgetting to put the monitor back on after taking it off when going to bed (Tudor-Locke, Camhi and Troiano, 2012). Due to poor compliance rates reported from hip-worn devices, the use of wrist-worn devices have become more popular, demonstrating an increase in compliance rates (Tudor-Locke et al., 2015, Fairclough et al., 2016, McLellan, Arthur and Buchan, 2018). A recent systematic review exploring the reporting of accelerometer methods in PA interventions suggest an increase in the number of studies employing accelerometer devices worn at the wrist is to be expected (Montoye et al., 2018). As such, with increasing ambiguity in the relationship between parent and child activity, and school-based interventions currently proving to be ineffective in increasing activity across the whole day, there is a need to explore the findings of studies that deploy wrist-worn accelerometers to increase compliance and report comparable accelerometry metrics. In doing so, researchers may be able to obtain a clearer understanding of the relationship of parent and child PA, the influence SES has on PA, and evaluate the effectiveness of school-based interventions aiming to increase children's PA.

1.3 Statement of the problem

Whilst some efforts have been made to enhance interventions aiming to foster health-conducive behaviours (e.g., increase PA and healthy eating) through increasing parent involvement and implementing homework-related activities, such interventions are still proving to be largely ineffective as shown in a meta-analysis of cluster randomized controlled trials with accelerometer-assessed activity (Love, Adams and Sluijs, 2018). This may be explained as such interventions are typically undertaken with no theoretical underpinning and fail to recruit lower SES groups (Clarke et al., 2015, Ruiters et al., 2015, Cassar et al., 2019). Therefore, the individuals most in need (i.e., low SES groups with less-involved parents) are not exposed to the intervention and the possible positive effects associated with the intervention. Additional research is warranted in this area due to the lack

of theory-informed interventions aimed at encouraging the involvement of parents, including those with low SES. Whilst deployment of accelerometer devices is strongly encouraged, accelerometry-assessed research remains limited by the use of device- and population-specific cut-points and failure to fully report methodological decisions.

1.4 Overview of the thesis

Whilst researchers are continually developing school-based interventions with the aim of improving health-related behaviours of children, many are proving to be ineffective. Comparing methods and in-turn the outcomes of such interventions is proving difficult due to incomparable measures used including both self-report and accelerometer data as well as varying accelerometer protocols. As such, there is no consensus on the most effective method to employ when designing and implementing school-based health interventions. Whilst parent involvement in such interventions is favourable, as well as multicomponent designs and theoretical underpinning, researchers struggle to recruit parents with low SES. As such, research is necessary surrounding the measurement of activity particularly between parent and child groups of varying SESs' as well as the most effective methods to design and implement an effective intervention which aims to improve 24 h movement behaviours.

1.4.1 Aims of the thesis

The aims of this thesis are as follows:

- To capture the perspectives of mothers with low SES that are not typically involved in school-based health activities to inform the design of interventions which aim to encourage parent involvement in school-based health activities.
- To objectively examine the relationship between parent-child PA using robust, novel approaches.
- To examine the influence SES has on children's PA and body mass index (BMI) through their parents PA and BMI.

- To design, implement and evaluate the fidelity of a health-related homework-based intervention theoretically underpinned and informed by end-user's experiences using mixed-method approaches.

1.4.2 Organisation of the thesis

This thesis was constructed to accumulate evidence in order to support and inform the design, implementation and testing of an 8-week pilot homework programme which aimed to improve the health behaviours of school children. The organisation of the thesis can be found in Figure 1-1.

Chapter 2 of the thesis provides a review of the current literature with key topics surrounding research areas relevant to this thesis, beginning with an overview of childhood obesity and its determinants. Literature will then be presented and discussed regarding children's PA, determinants of children's PA, and measurement issues in assessing children's PA. Finally, this chapter will end with an overview of the literature pertaining to school-based interventions and behaviour change.

Whilst there are many consistent methods used across the studies detailed in Chapters 4-7 of this thesis, Chapter 3 outlines the general methodological approaches undertaken in each research study. Study-specific methodologies will be discussed within their respective chapters.

Chapter 4 outlines the first study of this thesis which addresses a gap in knowledge surrounding the perspectives of typically uninvolved parents with low SES in school-based health interventions involving their children. Specific eligibility criterion was used to ensure that only mothers with low SES, who were less-involved in school activities, were individually interviewed as part of the qualitative inquiry.

Figure 1-1 Organisation of the thesis.

As such, previously unheard perspectives surrounding active ingredients and barriers to parent involvement in school-based health activities are presented. Researchers, policy makers and school staff may find this study of particular interest as it presents key recommendations on how to involve parents with low SES in school-based health interventions: an endeavour in which researchers typically struggle to achieve.

Chapter 5 outlines the second study of this thesis which is a cross-sectional investigation exploring the relationship between parent and child MVPA and BMI in a sample of children (4-11 years old) using wrist-worn accelerometers. Researchers may find this study of particular interest as it is the first, to the best of my knowledge, to explore mediating processes by which SES influences child MVPA and BMI z-score through their parents MVPA and BMI.

Chapter 6 presents the third study of this thesis which is a cross-sectional investigation exploring the relationship between parent and child objectively measured PA levels using novel activity metrics. As such, this study explored whether the intensity of PA or overall PA was associated with BMI in children and adults using these novel metrics in a sample of children aged 4-11 years. Researchers may find this study of interest as it is the first, to the best of my knowledge, to apply novel accelerometry metrics to parent and child dyads and explore such outcomes in relation to the BMI of parents and their children.

Chapter 7 outlines the fourth study of this thesis which focuses on the design and development of a curriculum-based HWB homework intervention delivered by classroom teachers and then via parents at home. Through mixed-methodological approaches, Chapter 7 details the feasibility and effectiveness of this intervention on children's activity, sleep and dietary behaviours. A purposeful sample of children aged 9-12 years participated in the study alongside their parent(s). Researchers, policy makers and school staff may all find this study of interest as it provides recommendations on how to implement a sustainable and effective

intervention and by doing so, minimise the pressure school staff face in delivering health-related school-based interventions.

Finally, Chapter 8 will summarise the significant findings from Chapters 4-7 and synthesise these findings in relation to current literature. Furthermore, the general strengths and limitations of the thesis will also be discussed and recommendations for future research and practice will be provided.

1.4.3 Original Contributions to knowledge.

Original contributions to knowledge will be made throughout each study chapter. In Chapter 4 (Study 1) qualitative data from mothers with low SES, who are typically not involved in school-based health activities, provided previously unheard perspectives. These perspectives are of a target population of whom researchers fail to include in interventions and thus, should take into consideration their perspectives in order to improve the implementation and involvement of those from groups who will benefit most from school-based health interventions. In Chapter 5 (Study 2), accelerometers were distributed to both parents and their children to explore the relationship of parent and child MVPA and BMI. Mediating processes by which SES influences child MVPA and BMI through their parents MVPA and BMI were investigated, which has previously gone unreported in research. In Chapter 6 (Study 3) PA was assessed using novel accelerometry metrics to utilise the rich nature of the data available in order to fully describe the 24 h movement profile without being population or protocol specific. It is believed that the use of such metrics allows for the comparison of outputs across groups (i.e., parents and children) and provide the basis for harmonization of accelerometry data from various devices for future studies by providing comparable datasets.

Based on the findings presented in previous literature and recommendations outlined in Chapter 4 (Study 1), the design, pilot, implementation, and evaluation of the Happy

Homework (HH) intervention is undertaken in Chapter 7 (Study 4). Novel accelerometry metrics and strict WTC for both ActiGraph and ActivPAL outcomes, aiming to capture the participant's activity over a 24 h per day period in Chapter 7 (Study 4) was employed.

Additionally, qualitative investigations exploring the fidelity of HH with teachers and pupils supports the quantitative data examining intervention effects on activity and dietary

outcomes. As such, mixed-methodological robust evidence on the feasibility, acceptability and effectiveness of an original pilot intervention is provided.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Introduction

The following chapter will review literature surrounding topics relevant to this thesis, beginning with an overview of obesity in children (i.e., children school-aged, 5-12 years old for the purpose of the thesis) and relevant determinants of childhood obesity. Literature will then be presented and discussed regarding PA and the determinants associated with children's PA including the influence of their parents and SES. Literature surrounding issues in assessing children's PA will also be presented and discussed, alongside the methodological approaches recommended to effectively and objectively measure PA. Finally, this chapter will end with an overview of the literature pertaining to school-based interventions which aim to improve health behaviours in children.

2.2 Obesity

Overweight and obesity are defined as abnormal or excessive fat accumulation that may impair health (World Health Organization, 2018a). BMI is a simple index of weight-for-height that is commonly used to measure overweight and obesity and can be defined as a person's weight in kilograms divided by the square of their height in meters (kg/m^2) (World Health Organization, 2018a). For children under 5 years of age, overweight and obesity is defined when weight-for-height is greater than 2 and 3 standard deviations (SD) above the World Health Organisation (WHO) Child Growth Standards median (World Health Organization, 2018a). For children and adolescents aged between 5-19 years, overweight and obesity is defined when BMI-for-age is greater than 1 and 2 SD above the WHO Growth Reference median (World Health Organization, 2018a). Although BMI is ideally suited for population-level studies, it is important to highlight that describing obesity by BMI can result in inaccurate assessment of adiposity, as research suggests the numerator in the calculation of BMI fails to distinguish lean muscle from fat mass (Cornier et al., 2011). As such, a person with central obesity (i.e., with excessive visceral fat) can have a normal BMI, however they

could have a high mortality risk (Coutinho et al., 2011). Additionally, BMI does not take sex differences in the distribution of fat or age-related decline in muscle mass into consideration, and BMI studies based on self-reported measurements and retrospective data from chart reviews have been found to be imprecise (Dutton and McLaren, 2014).

In the United Kingdom (UK), one of the most widely used methods to classify children as either healthy weight or obese/overweight is relative to the UK 1990 BMI population reference data (Cole, Freeman and Preece, 1995, Pongiglione and Fitzsimons, 2019). Using software provided by the Child Growth Foundation, weight status can be classified using the definitions for healthy weight (BMI z-score <1.04 , below the 85th percentile) and overweight/obese (BMI z-score ≥ 1.04 , above the 85th percentile) in children (Pan and Cole, 2010). Current growth charts in the UK are a combination of the UK 1990 references and the WHO 2006 child growth standard (Cole et al., 1995; World Health Organization, 2006). Growth charts provide a true growth reference representing the normal growth of children, whereas the WHO 2006 growth standard illustrates the optimal growth of children who were specifically selected for inclusion in the chart source sample as they were exclusively or predominantly breastfed until at least four months of age in environments free from any socio-economic constraint to their growth (de Onis et al., 2004, Johnson, Wright and Cameron, 2012). These new charts are called the UK-WHO child growth charts and combine recalculated UK 1990 reference birth data with the WHO standard data in children aged 2 weeks to four years old (Cole, Williams and Wright, 2011). Using these charts, which were adopted for practice in 2009, the WHO estimated that the number of overweight or obese infants and young children increased from 32 million globally in 1990 to 41 million in 2016 (World Health Organization, 2018a). If current trends continue, the number of overweight or obese infants and young children globally is expected to increase further to 70 million by 2025 (World Health Organization, 2018a).

Scottish national surveys suggest 14% of 2-15 year olds are obese (Scottish Government, 2016a). Statistics on Obesity, PA and Diet in England, 2019, observed that 20% of all year 6 children (10-11 years old) are classified as obese (NHS Digital, 2019). Additionally, the prevalence of obesity in these children was over twice as high in the most deprived areas than the least deprived areas (NHS Digital, 2019). As the prevalence of obesity in children is high, particularly of those with low SES, the consequences of obesity and influencing factors should be understood in order to develop informed interventions which aim to tackle the crisis of childhood obesity.

2.2.1 Consequences of obesity

Children who are overweight are likely to become overweight as adults, and for those who do become overweight as adults, are also at greater risk of developing severe physiological conditions including: type 2 diabetes, hypertension, dyslipidaemia, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, and CVD at a younger age (Daniels et al., 2009, Elizondo-Montemayor et al., 2010, Paulis et al., 2014). This cluster of diseases and disorders is collectively termed metabolic syndrome (MS). In 2007, the International Diabetes Federation attempted to define paediatric MS using age-specific diagnostic criteria and proposed that MS may be prevalent in (1) children aged 6-10 years who are obese (i.e., defined as having a waist circumference: 90th percentile) and have other relevant risk factors (e.g., family history of cardiometabolic disease) and (2) in children aged 10-16 years who are obese (i.e., defined as having a waist circumference \geq 90th percentile) and meet the adult MS criteria for triglycerides, high-density lipoprotein-cholesterol, blood pressure, and glucose concentrations (Zimmet et al., 2007). Using the International Diabetes Federation definition in the paediatric population and data from the NHANES database, the reported prevalence of MS in adolescents from the United States of America (USA) for the period 1999-2004 was approximately 4.5% (Ford et al., 2008). The authors also found that the prevalence of MS

increased with age, was higher among males (6.7%) than females (2.1%), and was highest among Mexican-American adolescents (7.1%) (Ford et al., 2008).

Whilst there are numerous physiological implications associated with overweight and obesity in children, obese youth are known to have greater psychological and behavioural issues compared to their non-obese counterparts (Wardle and Cooke, 2005). Indeed, children who are overweight are more likely to experience lower self-esteem, as well as negative consequences in their cognitive and social development (Amin, Al-Sultan and Ali, 2008). A recent study examining the association between childhood obesity and feelings of unhappiness and low levels of self-esteem in children found that those overweight and obese tend to have lower levels of self-esteem compared to normal weight children (Delgado et al., 2018).

The economic costs of treating obesity related conditions are substantial (Tremmel et al., 2017). The expected total NHS cost of obesity and overweight for England in 2015 was to be approximately £15.4 billion, representing around 15% of the NHS budget (Scarborough et al., 2011). Given the increasing prevalence rates of obesity and costs associated with obesity, it is unsurprising that Governments across the world are trying to provide additional funding/resources with the aim of reversing current obesity trends. For example, the UK Government pledged to invest the revenue from the sugar levy (i.e., a tax on sugar-sweetened beverages; SSB's) into school-based programmes to promote PA and healthier diets in 2017 (UK Government, 2017). Various interventions including school-based health interventions aim to exploit many determinants of childhood inactivity including diet and activity which effect childhood overweight/obesity. Such determinants will be discussed in the subsequent sub-sections.

2.2.2 Determinants of childhood obesity

There are numerous behavioural, environmental and social determinants of childhood obesity (Campbell, 2016). At the individual level, the most direct determinant of children's obesity is the energy imbalance between nutritional intake and activity (Owen et al., 2000, Nelson et al., 2005, Boone-Heinonen, Gordon-Larsen and Adair, 2008). As such, these health-related behavioural determinants have been included in both preventive and therapeutic interventions for years. Whilst these determinants are seen to directly influence children's obesity, the family, physical, and social environment influence children's obesity risk in two ways: (1) through a direct influence on children's nutrition and activity behaviours, and (2) through indirect influences. For example, parental education, parental nurturing, and higher self-esteem have been found to reduce obesity risk in girls (Crossman, Anne Sullivan and Benin, 2006). The following subsections will outline the following determinants: PA levels, SB, sleep, diet, SES and family.

2.2.2.1 PA levels

The term PA refers to bodily movements produced by skeletal muscles that require energy expenditure (EE) (Pate et al., 1995). Conversely, the term physical inactivity refers to the absence of recommended levels of PA or exercise, usually measured by not meeting PA guidelines (de Onis, Blössner, & Borghi, 2010). Although the causes of obesity are multifactorial, the link between physical inactivity and overweight/obesity is well established (U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2016, World Health Organization, 2018b). MVPA, light PA (LPA), SB, and sleep are mutually exclusive time-use components that together comprise the entire 24 h day (Talarico and Janssen, 2018). A series of systematic reviews examining these movement behaviours in isolation has indicated that they are related to obesity and many other health indicators within children (Carson, Hunter, et al., 2016, Chaput et al., 2016, Poitras et al., 2016).

Indeed, MVPA is an established determinant of cardiometabolic risk factors in children including waist circumference and systolic blood pressure (Ekelund et al., 2012). Indeed, the absence of PA is an important contributing factor in the maintenance of childhood obesity which has been acknowledged for over a decade (Troost, Kerr, Ward and Pate, 2001). Nevertheless, emerging evidence suggests that all intensities of PA, including LPA, may be important for health promotion and disease prevention (Carson et al., 2013, Ekelund et al., 2019). Indeed, greater consideration should be given to the role of time spent in LPA. This is in line with the 2018 PA Guidelines Advisory Committee report in the USA which noted that the benefits of PA can be achieved in a variety of ways, and highlighted that the role of time spent in LPA has yet to be elucidated (Young et al., 2016, US Department of Health and Human Services, 2018). Interestingly, whilst the proportion of time spent in LPA and SB have both been found to be detrimentally associated with obesity and CVD markers, the association with SB has shown to be stronger (Chastin et al., 2015).

2.2.2.2 SB

SB is any waking behaviour characterized by an EE \leq 1.5 metabolic equivalents (MET's), while in a sitting, reclining or lying posture (Sedentary Behaviour Research Network, 2012). Large-scale international studies have shown that SB increases as children age (Cooper et al., 2015). Alarming, children are becoming more sedentary, with evidence indicating that over 60% of Canadian preschool children exceed daily screen time (ST) recommendations and children from the USA spend on average 7 h per day in front of a screen (Council on Communications and Media and Strasburger, 2011, Pujadas Botey et al., 2016). To tackle the increase of SB's, several current national guidelines, including those from the UK and Australia, have also recommended focussing on decreasing time spent in SB in addition to engaging in daily MVPA (Tremblay et al., 2016, Australian Government Department of Health, 2019, UK Chief Medical Officer, 2019). Given the above findings,

researchers have developed a “‘couch-potato’ hypothesis” (Vandewater et al., 2004, p.72). This hypothesis suggest that, through the use of electronics such as: (1) games and social media on smart phones, (2) tablets, and (3) computers, PA is displaced and in some cases, these behaviours can even decrease metabolism, more than sitting or sleeping (Vandewater, Shim and Caplovitz, 2004). The use of electronics also leads to an increase in snacking and increases exposure to advertisements for densely caloric foods in children (Vandewater, Shim and Caplovitz, 2004).

A review of screen-based device use by children and adolescents since 2000 found that television viewing (TV) was the most common measure of ST, with fewer studies reporting the engagement of ST in newer screen-based devices such as mobile phones (<4.6%) and active gaming consoles (<1%) (Thomas et al., 2019). TV is thought to relate to obesity due to eating behaviours and food choices. For instance, research involving Canadian and American children found that eating meals while watching television may be associated with overeating high-fat and high-sugar diets as well as an overall poorer quality of diet (Liang, Kuhle, & Veugelers, 2009; Zimmerman & Bell, 2010). Additionally, a systematic review exploring the association’s between children’s diet quality and TV during meal/snack consumption found that eating whilst watching television is associated with poorer diet quality among children, including more frequent consumption of SSB’s and high-fat, high-sugar foods as well as the consumption of less fruits and vegetables (Avery, Anderson and McCullough, 2017). Alarmingly, findings from a meta-analysis which was conducted to examine time spent TV and the risk of this with childhood obesity, observed that 1 h per day increment of TV corresponded to a 13% increase in risk of obesity (Zhang et al., 2016). Findings from a scoping review of 130 surveillance studies indicated that, on average, 52.3% of youths exceeded 2 h per day of ST, and total ST was 3.6 h per day (Thomas et al., 2019).

Research examining SB has been largely informed by self-reported questionnaires completed by parents and children which focus primarily on specific SB's, such as ST (LeBlanc et al., 2015). This comes with limitations as ST has been shown to be only moderately correlated to sedentary time, and ST estimates typically rely on subjective measures which are associated with the inherent limitations of all self-report instruments including social desirability and recall biases (Olds, Maher, Ridley and Kittel, 2010, Sallis and Saelens, 2000).

SB can be measured objectively, most accurately by accelerometer devices.

Specifically, the ActivPAL has been found to be a valid measurement tool for assessing time spent in postures associated with SB including sitting/lying, standing, walking and sit-to-stand transitions (Aminian and Hinckson, 2012). ST can also be objectively recorded using television ST trackers however these can be expensive and could potentially require research personnel to perform a home visit for installation (Vizcaino et al., 2019). As such, alternative methods in assessing ST have been developed. Self-reported methods for quantifying ST have acceptable reliability and validity in children (Hardy et al., 2013). Past research on ST has focused almost exclusively on quantifying "screen use" as the number of h's of TV in a given week (Wilmot et al., 2012). Only a small number of studies have aggregated TV with videos, games and computer use (Stamatakis, Hamer and Dunstan, 2011, Wijndaele et al., 2011, Vizcaino et al., 2019). By doing so, this method enables researchers to examine the association between modern ST and its influence on health outcomes in children including activity and sleep. Indeed, findings from a systematic review of ST and sleep among youth indicate that ST is adversely associated with sleep outcomes in 90% of studies (Hale and Guan, 2015). Undoubtedly, sleep plays an important role in the health of children and is a significant determinant of childhood obesity and overall HWB.

2.2.2.3 *Sleep*

Sleep is a physiological state, occurring in alternation with wakefulness (Cardinali, 2016). Generally, sleep is defined as a naturally recurring state of body and mind which can be characterized by altered consciousness, relatively inhibited sensory activity, inhibition of nearly all voluntary muscles and reduced interactions with surroundings (Chaput et al., 2014). The CDC recommend that children get 9-12 h's of sleep per night (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2020). Associations between insufficient sleep and ill health are well established (Yoong et al., 2016). Cross-sectional associations between short sleep duration (generally <6 h's per night) and increased prevalence of obesity or higher BMI in both adults and children from various countries have been observed (Knutson and Van Cauter, 2008, Marshall, Glozier and Grunstein, 2008, Patel and Hu, 2008). Furthermore, an inverse relationship between sleep and morbidity, mortality, and chronic conditions including type 2 diabetes and hypertension have been observed (Kripke et al., 2002, Ayas et al., 2003, Ferrie et al., 2007, Patel and Hu, 2008). A large number of epidemiological studies and meta-analyses have identified a consistent pattern of increased odds of being short sleeper if you are obese, both in childhood and in adulthood (Cappuccio et al., 2008, Chen, Beydoun and Wang, 2008, Liu, Zhang and Li, 2012, Lee and Park, 2014, Li et al., 2017, Wu et al., 2017, Miller et al., 2018). It is important to draw attention to the findings from a recent narrative review concerned with the associations between BMI and sleep duration that highlights that whilst there is some modest evidence of a bidirectional relationship between BMI in both children and adults, there is no solid evidence that this relationship (in either direction) is in fact causal (Garfield, 2019). Nevertheless, increasing evidence has shown that insufficient sleep duration may be associated with obesity as sleeping plays an important role in the balance of psychological, emotional, and physical health of children (Bayon et al., 2014).

Insufficient sleep, delayed sleep-wake behaviour, and sleep disturbances are common among youth and adolescents (Gradisar, Gardner and Dohnt, 2011). The role of sleep is more complicated in children because of higher sleep needs as well as the growth- and lifestyle-related sleep changes seen at these developmental stages (Glaze, 2004). Few studies have explored the role of sleep on adiposity among UK children, however the available evidence suggests there is a link between insufficient sleep duration and overweight/obesity in 7-year-olds (Wilkie et al., 2016). The association between short duration of sleep and obesity have stimulated debates for years given the potential implications this has for children (Currie and Cappuccio, 2007). Research demonstrates a consistent increased risk of obesity amongst short sleepers in children and in adults (Cooper et al., 2018, Miller et al., 2018). In fact, findings from a recent meta-analysis of short sleep duration and obesity in children and adults found that short sleep duration may be associated with the development of obesity from childhood into adulthood (Miller, Kruisbrink, Wallace, Ji, & Cappuccio, 2018). Additionally, research has found that insufficient sleep is associated with increased caloric consumption, poor dietary habits, increased snacking as well as the number of meals consumed per day in children (Chaput, 2014).

2.2.2.4 Diet

Whilst habitual movement patterns and sleep have a substantial impact on children's weight status, poor diet is widely acknowledged to be a key driver of childhood obesity (Faught et al., 2016). Assessing dietary intake in children has been of interest for decades and for various purposes. Research suggests that, when measuring total diet, challenges are common and can convey a large burden in terms of time, cost, technical expertise, and impact on respondents (Magarey et al., 2011). The characteristics of each developmental stage and associated cognitive abilities are two factors that influence the ability of children to provide valid and reliable data on food consumption (Pérez-Rodrigo, 2015). As such, the 24 h recall,

dietary records, dietary histories, Food Frequency Questionnaires (FFQs), brief instruments, observations of children's diets and mixed instruments such as a dietary record-assisted 24 h recall have all been used to quantify children's dietary intake (Pérez-Rodrigo, 2015). An example of such is The Day in the Life Questionnaire (DILQ) which has been validated in 7-9 year old children (Edmunds and Ziebland, 2002) and has been used with 6-11 year old children (Sharps and Robinson, 2015, 2016). The DILQ uses words and pictures to encourage children to recall and describe a range of activities from the previous day (24 h recall method), including everything they consumed (Edmunds and Ziebland, 2002). Various researchers have used the DILQ to measure fruit and vegetable consumption within their school-based cluster randomised control trials, with Kipping and colleagues obtaining valid data for fruit and vegetable consumption for 2121 children, and observing that the Active for Life Year 5 (AFLY5) school-based intervention is not effective in increasing fruit and vegetable consumption in primary school children (Kipping et al., 2014). On the other hand, Prelip and colleagues observed a slight increase in fruit and vegetable consumption from pre- to post-test, although this was not significant and was observed for both the intervention and control schools (Prelip et al., 2011). The DILQ appears to be an effective tool for measuring fruit and vegetable consumption in primary school children.

Dietary factors have been studied extensively for their contributions to the rising rates of obesity with most studies focussing on fast food consumption, SSB's, snacking, and portion sizes (Sahoo et al., 2015). Consuming large portions, in addition to frequent snacking on high caloric foods, contribute to an excessive caloric intake that over time, can contribute towards obesity (Anderson and Butcher, 2006). The NHS recommend that children eat 5 portions of fruit and vegetables a day however, only 13% of children aged 2-15 years meet the 5-a-day fruit and vegetable consumption recommendation in Scotland (NHS Digital, 2018, Hughes et al., 2019). These findings, in comparison with other countries seeking to

improve the fruit and vegetable intake of children highlight the concern for Scottish children. Indeed, the latest New Zealand Health Survey observed that 51.4% of 2-14 year-olds met the recommended serving of vegetables per day, and 72.4% consumed adequate fruit servings (Ministry of Health New Zealand, 2020).

Consumption of SSB drinks, but not 100% fruit juices and milk, have also been found to be associated with obesity in children (Papandreou et al., 2013). A review of systematic literature reviews found a direct association between SSB consumption and weight gain, overweight, and obesity in children and adolescents (Keller and Bucher Della Torre, 2015). However, recent evidence from well-conducted meta-analyses shows variation in results regarding the association between SSB's and weight gain, overweight, and obesity among children and adolescents (Keller and Bucher Della Torre, 2015). This may be explained due to review- and study-level bias, such as the use of inappropriate study and review design, energy adjustment, as well as the acknowledged limitations linked to dietary assessment methods (Keller and Bucher Della Torre, 2015). In order to establish the true extent of the relationship between diet and obesity, improving the methodological quality of studies and reviews as well as ensuring responsible conduct of research and scientific integrity has been advocated (Keller and Bucher Della Torre, 2015). The association between poor diet has also been found to be related to low SES, a topic which itself, plays a significant role in obesity within children (Pechey and Monsivais, 2016). Indeed, children who grow up in areas of low SES have a higher risk of CVD, unhealthy behaviours, all cause-mortality and higher obesity prevalence rates when compared to those who grow up in areas associated with higher SES (NHS Digital, 2006, Laaksonen et al., 2008, Bukman et al., 2014).

2.2.2.5 *SES*

Europe is a diverse region with widely varying socioeconomic differences in childhood overweight and obesity (Lissner et al., 2016). Indeed, according to the first report

from The Childhood Obesity Surveillance Initiative, the prevalence of childhood obesity in 12 European countries ranged from 6.0% to 26.6% in boys and from 4.6% to 17.3% in girls (Wijnhoven et al., 2014). Research further shows that children with lower SES are at a higher risk for overweight and obesity and are exposed to home and neighbourhood environments that are uncondusive to health-promoting behaviours (Goisis, Sacker and Kelly, 2016, Noonan, Boddy, Knowles, et al., 2016). For instance, at age 5, children in the bottom income quintile in the UK had 2.0 increased relative risk of being obese whilst children aged 11 had 3.0 increased risk compared to children in the top income quintile (Goisis, Sacker and Kelly, 2016). The SES of children has been found to negatively influence their diet and may be exacerbated by a greater number of unhealthy food outlets being located in more deprived areas (Cetateanu and Jones, 2014). However, the inverse socioeconomic gradient in childhood obesity has been observed long before the height of fast food outlets. In fact, a six fold higher prevalence of obesity was found in 1972 among American girls from low income families when compared to more affluent families (Stunkard et al., 1972). Findings from the NHANES 2005-2008 in the USA also reported a significant inverse relationship between obesity prevalence and the educational attainment of the head of the household (Ogden, Carroll, Curtin, Lamb, & Flegal, 2010). Among boys, 11.8% of those living in households where the household head has at least a college degree were found to be obese compared with 21.1% of those living in households where the head of the household has less than a high school degree (Ogden, Carroll, Curtin, Lamb, & Flegal, 2010).

Being of a lower SES is arguably one of the strongest risk factors for developing obesity in countries that have made the transition to Western lifestyles (Stamatakis, Wardle and Cole, 2010). Furthermore, socioeconomic disparities in childhood obesity and obesity-related behaviours have increased (Frederick, Snellman and Putnam, 2014). While obesity rates among children with high SES have begun to plateau in recent years, the rates among

children with low SES have continued to increase (Frederick, Snellman and Putnam, 2014). A similar pattern was found in the prevalence of obesity-related behaviours among children with low SES (Frederick, Snellman and Putnam, 2014). Indeed, it is clear that there are various indirect determinants of childhood obesity including SES which is facilitated through the family environment.

2.2.2.6 Family environment

The role of the family environment in childhood obesity has been of interest for over a decade. Interestingly, parent BMI z-score change has been found to be a significant predictor of child BMI z-score change (Boutelle et al., 2012; Wrotniak et al., 2004). Cross-sectional studies have demonstrated that having an overweight mother, living in a single-parent family, and being raised in a low income household are strongly associated with overweight or obesity prevalence in children (Gibson et al., 2007, Hesketh et al., 2007, Gray and Leyland, 2008). As such, the high global prevalence of obesity in adults, and in particular those in Scotland, presents significant challenges for those implementing lifestyle interventions designed to improve obesity prevalence rates within children. It is clear that PA, among various other obesity-related behaviours, not only influence the weight status of children, but also simultaneously influence each other (e.g., SES and diet). Therefore, such determinants should be taken into consideration when examining health-related outcomes (e.g., activity and weight status) in children, and when designing interventions to improve such health-related outcomes.

2.3 Rationale for PA

Regular PA is associated with various benefits for children including improvements in cardiorespiratory fitness, building strong bones and muscles, effectively controlling weight, reducing symptoms of anxiety and depression, and reducing the risk of developing health condition such as heart disease, cancer, type 2 diabetes, high blood pressure and obesity (US

Department of Health and Human Services, 2018). School-aged children who are physically active tend to have better grades, school attendance, cognitive performance (e.g., memory, concentration) and improved classroom behaviours (e.g., on-tasks behaviour) (US Department of Health and Human Services, 2010, Michael et al., 2015). The promotion of PA is thus warranted to reduce the risk of developing NCD's and the financial burden associated with physical inactivity.

2.3.1 PA and SB Guidelines

PA guidelines have been proposed as early as 1988, with The American College of Sports Medicine originally recommending that youth should participate in 20-30 mins of vigorous exercise daily, with the aim of encouraging people to achieve the health benefits associated with PA participation (American College of Sports Medicine., 1988). A decade later, two recommendations for PA were made for young people aged 5-18 years: (1) young people should participate in at least 60 mins of moderate intensity PA per day, although children that participate in only a little amount of activity should participate in at least 30 mins of moderate intensity PA daily, and (2) activities focused on developing bone density, muscular strength and flexibility should be carried out twice a week (Biddle, Sallis and Cavill, 1998). Sixty mins was the recommended time for PA daily as the prevalence of childhood overweight and obesity was increasing while the majority of young people were accumulating 30 mins of PA each day (Biddle, Sallis and Cavill, 1998).

More recently, the WHO detailed current global PA guidelines which urge children to engage in a minimum of 60 mins of daily MVPA and adults to accumulate 30 mins of MVPA on most days of the week (US Department of Health and Human Services, 2018, World Health Organization, 2018b, UK Chief Medical Officer, 2019). Most of children's daily PA should be aerobic, with vigorous-intensity activities incorporated, including those that strengthen muscle and bone, at least 3 times per week. However, it is worrying that in many

high-income settings, average time spent in MVPA is well below the recommendations provided (Hallal et al., 2012). A recent WHO funded study exploring global trends in insufficient PA in young people found that, in 2016, 27 countries had a prevalence of insufficient activity of 90% or more for girls, whereas this was the case in only two countries for boys (Guthold et al., 2019). Existing estimates of children's activity levels indicate that only 42% of children aged 6-11 years, and only 5% of adults actually achieve their daily activity goals (Troiano et al., 2008). With children across the world failing to meet recommended activity guidelines, it has never been so important to determine the true magnitude of this inactivity and devise interventions to combat the growing prevalence of this trend.

From a Global Matrix (3.0) from 49 countries, findings suggest for overall PA, Scottish children, as well as those from Belgium, China, South Korea, and Taiwan, received an "F" grade in meeting the recommended guidelines of MVPA per day, which indicates that very few children (<20%) are meeting the MVPA guideline of 60 mins per day (Aubert et al., 2018). This claim is further substantiated through additional research, with findings suggesting Australian youth are insufficiently active, engaging in high levels of screen-based SB's, and only 28% of Ethiopian children and youth (17% urban and 39% rural) meet the 60 mins of daily MVPA per day recommendation (Schranz et al., 2016, Abdeta et al., 2018). Whilst current PA guidelines emphasise the importance of achieving the recommended 60 mins of MVPA per day, MVPA typically only accounts for a small proportion (<5%) of the day in contrast to sleep (~40%), SB (~40%) and LPA (~15%) (Chaput, Carson, Gray, & Tremblay, 2014). Efforts to address the single-minded focus on MVPA has led to a proliferation of SB research and to the creation of the world's first SB guidelines for children and youth (Chaput, Carson, et al., 2014). Failing to recognise the other components of the movement continuum (i.e., sleep, SB, LPA) while focusing efforts exclusively on MVPA

(accounting for <5% of the time in a 24 h) greatly limits the potential to optimize the health benefits associated with movement behaviours (Chaput, Carson, et al., 2014). Research indicates that SB's are omnipresent and represent a health risk independent of MVPA (Tremblay et al., 2010, Colley et al., 2011). Indeed, regular engagement in MVPA and limiting SB are considered independent risk factors of health outcomes in children and youth across the world (Carson, Hunter, et al., 2016, Poitras et al., 2016). As such, guidelines for SB have been developed across the world including the UK, Canada and Australia (Chief Medical Officers, 2011, Tremblay et al., 2011, Australian Government, 2018). For instance, to achieve health benefits, Canadian SB guidelines suggest that children (aged 5-11 years) and youth (aged 12-17 years) should minimize the time that they spend being sedentary each day (Tremblay et al., 2011). This may be achieved by (1) limiting recreational ST to no more than 2 h per day - lower levels are associated with additional health benefits, and (2) limiting sedentary transport (i.e., motorized), extended sitting time, and time spent indoors throughout the day (Tremblay et al., 2011).

Recent findings suggest that all movement behaviours (i.e., sleep, SB, LPA) and how they interact in a 24 h period have important health implications for children which should be considered in the future design of school-based interventions (Carson et al., 2017). Thus, each element of the 24 h day movement continuum should be targeted to maximize health benefits (Chaput, Carson, et al., 2014). Compositional analyses deal with data that is a proportion of a finite whole (e.g., 24 h) and can be used when all parts or just some parts of the finite whole have been measured (Chastin et al., 2015). Such analyses also provides novel insights into collective health implications of 24 h movement behaviours and can generate interesting opportunities for future investigations (Carson, Tremblay, et al., 2016). As such, complementary compositional analyses has been used to examine 24 h movement behaviours and their relationship with health indicators using Canadian Health Measures Survey data

(Tremblay et al., 2016). The guidelines provide evidence-informed recommendations for a healthy day, comprising a combination of sleep, SB, LPA, moderate PA, and vigorous PA (Tremblay et al., 2016). As the time available each day (i.e., either the 24 h cycle or waking day) is finite, changing the time spent in one behaviour will necessarily impact time spent in the other behaviour (Buman et al., 2014, Chastin et al., 2015).

With the notion of one behaviour impacting upon another over the 24 h period in mind, latest guidelines were developed in Canada and most recently Australia which represent a paradigm shift in thinking about movement behaviours over the entire 24 h period (Tremblay et al., 2016, Australian Government, 2018). Such recommendations have shifted from traditional guidelines focussing on a single specific movement behaviour such as MVPA, to an integrated movement behaviour model. This model includes recommendations that children and youth (aged 5-17 years old) should: (1) participate in at least 60 min of daily MVPA, (2) view no more than 2 h of recreational ST, and (3) have adequate sleep durations of between 9-11 h per night as well as consistent bed and wake times (Tremblay et al., 2016, Australian Government, 2018). It has been shown that individuals meeting all three recommendations have demonstrated the lowest odds ratio for obesity or having a high BMI z-score in children in comparison to those individuals not meeting all three recommendations (Carson, Tremblay, et al., 2016, Roman-Viñas et al., 2016, Saunders et al., 2016). It was also found that, while meeting two recommendations is better than meeting one, and meeting one is better than meeting none in relation to having the lowest odds ratio for obesity or having a high BMI z-score (Roman-Viñas et al., 2016).

Findings from a 12-country study exploring the associations between meeting combinations of 24 h movement recommendations and dietary patterns found that limiting ST habits to the recommended amount was most strongly associated with healthier dietary patterns (Thivel et al., 2019). Furthermore, a less unhealthy dietary pattern was observed

when more movement behaviour recommendations were met (Thivel et al., 2019).

Combinations of children meeting recommendations including: (1) movement behaviours (i.e., ≥ 60 min of daily MVPA), (2) ≤ 2 h of daily recreational ST, and (3) between 9 and 11 h of nightly sleep) were those most strongly associated with a less unhealthy dietary pattern (Thivel et al., 2019). Overall, these findings suggest that meeting more movement behaviour recommendations is generally associated with better dietary patterns in children from around the world, with limiting ST habits showing the strongest relationship with better dietary patterns (Thivel et al., 2019). Yet despite this, only a small percentage of children met all recommendations. In fact, the global prevalence of children meeting the recommendations for all three behaviours was only 7%, with children from Australia and Canada showing the highest adherence (15%) (Roman-Viñas et al., 2016). It is important therefore that future efforts should aim to find effective methods to increase daily PA, reduce ST, and ensure an adequate night's sleep in children to reduce the risks of overweight/obesity and the subsequent health outcomes associated with obesity (Roman-Viñas et al., 2016).

Development of effective interventions that encourage children to meet the 24 h movement guidelines each day is a key priority for public health researchers. By providing specific SB guidelines alongside the most common PA and dietary-related recommendations, the importance of such behaviours to the HWB of children is now well-recognised. Indeed, research suggests that SB in children aged from birth through to 4-years is associated with several adverse health outcomes including: excess adiposity, poor psychosocial health and decreased cognitive development (Downing et al., 2016). It is important therefore that researchers employ measures to quantify SB's objectively in order to effectively capture prevalence rates to understand the true magnitude of the problem and in doing so, identify those most in need of intervention. Research has found that 60–75 min of MVPA per day is necessary to negate the effect of excessive time spent in SB, however conversely the findings

also highlight that sitting for over 8 h daily can negate the beneficial effect of MVPA in individuals who just meet the recommended guidelines (i.e., equivalent to 150 min of moderate intensity activity per week) (Ekelund et al., 2016). These results provide further evidence on the benefits of PA, particularly in societies where increasing numbers of people are forced to sit for long h's due to their education and/or employment. Prior to the development of interventions that encourage children to meet the 24 h movement guidelines, it is important to be aware that, similarly to obesity, there are also determinants associated with PA which influence each other interchangeably and must be taken into consideration.

2.4 Correlates of PA and SB

Physical inactivity refers to the absence of recommended levels of PA or exercise, usually quantified by individuals not meeting PA guidelines (de Onis, Blössner, & Borghi, 2010). Physical inactivity increases the risk of many NCD's and has been recognised as a major contributor to the global burden of ill health (Lee et al., 2012). SB is also contributing to negative determinants of childhood obesity. SB usually takes place in regular prolonged bouts with infrequent breaks and tend to occur whilst TV, attending school or for those in desk-led occupations (Leitzmann, Jochem and Schmid, 2018). Compared to the research area of PA, SB-related research is still developing. Nevertheless, there is increasing evidence that SB is associated with ill health and that reducing the amount of time an individual spends sedentary reduces the risk for adverse health outcomes (Tremblay et al., 2016, Leitzmann, Jochem and Schmid, 2018, Ekelund et al., 2019). Research from a cross-sectional study with 4757 adult participants from the 2003/04 and 2005/06 US NHANES found that, independent of exercise time and other potential confounders, total sedentary time was detrimentally associated with several biomarkers including waist circumference (Healy et al., 2011). Recently, findings from a systematic review and harmonised meta-analysis found a statistically significantly higher risk of death observed for SB's lasting 9.5 or more h's per

day (Ekelund et al., 2019). Numerous determinants of childhood obesity have been linked to children's activity levels. A systematic review of reviews exploring risk factors associated with the PA levels of children and adolescents identified that PA is a complex and multi-dimensional behaviour determined by numerous biological, psychological, sociocultural and environmental factors (Sterdt, Liersch and Walter, 2014). Such factors included in this thesis are: (1) family involvement, (2) SES, (3) diet and (4) sleep. These factors are discussed in-depth within the following sub-sections as correlates of PA.

2.4.1 Family involvement

The influence parents can have on their child's PA levels is well established (Trost and Loprinzi, 2011, Xu, Wen and Rissel, 2015, Yao and Rhodes, 2015). A recent systematic review indicated that the clear majority of studies observed a weak positive relationship between parent and child PA regardless of age of the child, the gender of the parent-child dyad, and type of PA (Petersen et al., 2020). Parents can influence their children's PA in various ways through role modelling (i.e., being active themselves), material support (i.e., financial, logistic, co-participation), and encouragement (Gustafson and Rhodes, 2006). Indeed, in a study exploring the effect of parental involvement on children's PA, researchers found that parental participation during PA with their children resulted in a significant increase in the number of ActiGraph accelerometer counts in children ($109,523 \pm 32,155$ counts) than the "alone" ($67,938 \pm 37,857$ counts) and "parent watching" ($85,624 \pm 44,985$ counts) conditions (Rebold et al., 2016). Counts during "parent watching" were also significantly greater than the "alone" condition (Rebold et al., 2016). Additionally, more time was allocated to sedentary activities during the "alone" (16.2 ± 9.6 mins) condition than "parent watching" (9.6 ± 9.3 mins) and "parent participating" (3.8 ± 5.1 mins) (Rebold et al., 2016). Interestingly, a greater proportion of children identified the "parent participating" (80%) as their preferred condition over either the "parent watching" (10%) or "alone" (10%)

conditions (Rebold et al., 2016). The evidence suggests that children are likely to be more physically active when their parent is involved, and enjoy this more than engaging in activities by themselves. Additionally, a meta-analysis of parental correlates in child and adolescent PA showed a moderate effect of parental support on child PA (summary $r = .38$, 95% CI .30-.46) and that parental modelling was weakly associated with child PA (summary $r = .16$, 95% CI .09-.24) potentially suggesting that child PA might be more influenced by supportive behaviours than parental participation in PA (Yao and Rhodes, 2015). Interestingly, separate analyses examining the moderating effects of gender on the child PA found that father-son PA modelling ($r = .29$, 95% CI .21-.36) was significantly higher compared to mother-son PA ($r = .19$, 95% CI .14-.23; $p < .05$) yet parental gender did not moderate the relationship between parental modelling and girls' PA ($p > .05$) (Yao and Rhodes, 2015). Fundamentally, a systematic review of associations of parental influence with PA and ST among young children found that parents' encouragement and support can increase children's PA, and reducing parents' own ST can lead to decreased child ST (Xu, Wen and Rissel, 2015). Therefore, improving parenting health-related practices or changing parenting style may also be promising approaches for increasing PA time and reducing ST in children (Xu, Wen and Rissel, 2015). The involvement of families has been shown to be a key component of effective PA interventions in children, with research indicating that the involvement of parents in such interventions may be more beneficial when compared to those which do not (Ha et al., 2019).

Parent and child shared activity and the enjoyment of tasks has recently been explored in a study involving 31 parent-child dyads (Filanowski et al., 2020). Findings revealed that when compared to parents, children spent proportionally more time in MVPA during jumping games, body-weight exercises, and tag games. The authors also reported that tag games were the most enjoyable PA for children and parents, whilst children enjoyed body-weight

exercises more than parents (Filanowski et al., 2020). A study examining the effects of a family-focused active play intervention which aimed to influence children's total PA and time spent in SB, recruited families from children's centres in the North West of England (O'Dwyer et al., 2012). Significant intervention effects were observed for sedentary time and PA for both week and weekend days with children in the intervention group engaging in 1.5% and 4.3% less sedentary time during week and weekend days, respectively and 4.5% and 13.1% more PA during week and weekend days, respectively than children in the comparison group. The authors also found that parent's participation in sport and their own PA levels, child's gender, availability of media in the home and attendance at organised activities were all significant predictors of sedentary time and PA in children (O'Dwyer et al., 2012). This is significant as parents were found to have a positive effect on the PA and SB of their children, both when they are most likely to be together (i.e., weekends) and when they are not (e.g., school days during the week) whilst engaging in an active play intervention (O'Dwyer et al., 2012). As such, the evidence is clear that parents should be involved in interventions which aim to increase children's own activity, as the outcomes may be substantially more beneficial than including children alone in such interventions. Nevertheless, further exploration surrounding the relationship between parent and child PA is needed to add clarity to the existing research which is currently contradictory.

2.4.2 SES

The influencing relationship between SES and PA levels has been observed in adults and children (Trost et al., 2002, Drenowatz et al., 2010). Indeed, research suggests that children with low SES show a trend of lower PA levels and spend more time in SB when compared to children with high SES (Drenowatz et al., 2010). Nevertheless, recent research has questioned the strength of the influence of SES upon PA (Beenackers et al., 2012, Stalsberg and Pedersen, 2018) with equivocal findings regarding the relationship between

SES and PA arising from a limited quantity of studies, weak research designs, the use of self-reported measures of PA and variation in the methods employed to measure SES. Although children from lower-income families are less likely to attend sessions of structured out-of-school PA than those from wealthier families, children from lower-income families have been found to be just as active as children from higher-income families (Voss et al., 2008). A possible explanation for this may be explained as children living in deprived areas have been found to participate in more unstructured outdoor free-play than children from more affluent families (Sallis, Prochaska, & Taylor, 2000). A recent review comparing differences in PA across socioeconomic groups concluded that a positive relationship between SES and PA was apparent for LPA, however the relationship was non-existent or even opposite for all other activity intensities (Stalsberg and Pedersen, 2018). With some research indicating that SES negatively effects children's PA, and others indicating opposite effects, further research is warranted to explore SES and its influence on the PA of children and their families.

2.4.3 Diet

The average child in Scotland aged between 4-10 years old consumes an average of around 24.5 kilograms of unhealthy snacks annually which equates to over 110,000 calories (Food Standards Scotland, 2015). It is not surprising therefore that Scottish national surveys suggest 14% of 2-15 year olds are obese, with researchers indicating that in Scotland, obesity prevalence may be much worse than official figures suggest (Gray and Leyland, 2011, Hughes et al., 2019). Unhealthy dietary behaviours have been shown to co-occur with low PA (Leech, McNaughton and Timperio, 2014). Indeed, greater levels of MVPA are associated with healthy dietary habits, such as increased fruit and vegetable consumption, breakfast consumption, and a lower intake of unhealthy sugary snacks (Pearson et al., 2009, Szczerbński, Karczewski and Siemienkiewicz, 2010, Lazzeri et al., 2013, Silva and Silva, 2015). Whilst research has presented contrasting findings concerning unhealthy dietary

behaviours and their link with PA, research indicates that active children do not necessarily have 'healthier' diets when compared to the diets of children who are inactive (Ottevaere et al., 2011, Wilkie et al., 2016). Research also indicates that children who eat breakfast regularly, generally spend less than two h's a day engaging in SB (i.e., TV or computer use) (Lazzeri et al., 2013). Additionally, evidence indicates that physical inactivity and SB tend to cluster with various additional modifiable health risks such as poor dietary intake, along with insufficient sleep and substance misuse (Pronk et al., 2004, Plotnikoff et al., 2009). Indeed, reviews exploring adiposity in children and adolescents found that diet, PA and SB cluster together in complex ways (i.e., both healthy and unhealthy) that are not fully understood (Leech, McNaughton and Timperio, 2014, Biddle, García Bengoechea and Wiesner, 2017). Healthy behaviours including regular participation in PA may compensate for unhealthy ones such as poor diet, which would offer some explanation for the inconsistency across studies. This has important implications for public health because understanding which behaviours need to be targeted simultaneously may assist in the development of targeted HWB initiatives. Most promisingly, interventions that are appropriately targeted and effectively bring about multiple behaviour change (e.g., diet and SB), may be more cost-effective and maximise reach to those most in need (Prochaska, 2008, Luckner, Moss and Gericke, 2012).

2.4.4 Sleep

Hypotheses invoking indirect behavioural pathways to link short or inadequate sleep and obesity propose that active play during the day is replaced by SB such as TV due to short sleep in children (Sekine et al., 2002, Chen, Beydoun and Wang, 2008, Must and Parisi, 2009). A Canadian study involving 856 children aged 10-12 years showed that the relationship between sleep and PA varied by day (Stone, Stevens and Faulkner, 2013). The authors observed that the overall intensity of PA was higher among children achieving recommended sleep (>9 h's) through weekdays and weekend days when compared to those

who slept less than 9 h's during the week and engaged in weekend 'catch-up-sleep' (Stone, Stevens and Faulkner, 2013). This study did however use self-reported measures of sleep which may limit the accuracy of study findings (Erwin and Bashore, 2017). When using objective measures for sleep and PA, no associations were observed between mean PA and sleep duration in children (Nixon et al., 2008). However, a limitation of the study is that the activity monitors were worn only for 24 h's. A single 24 h period of ActiGraph measurement may not yield reliable estimates of sleep (Ancoli-Israel et al., 2003). Interestingly, PA is favoured by many physicians and sleep experts, and deemed preventative, as an alternative treatment for insomnia (Dishman et al., 2015). As such, further exploration into the associations of PA and sleep in children is important as it is another correlate that can be influenced to improve HWB outcomes in children.

2.5 Measurement of PA and SB

Accurate assessment of PA and SB is vital in order to explore the associations between PA and health outcomes, to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions and to derive public health recommendations. Historically, self-report questionnaires have been used to assess PA in large-scale and surveillance studies given their cost effectiveness and ease of administration (Ishikawa-Takata et al., 2008, Corder et al., 2009). Nonetheless, studies have shown a modest agreement between self-reported and objectively measured PA which suggest that population levels of PA derived from self-report should be interpreted cautiously (Steene-Johannessen et al., 2016). Indeed, potential disadvantages of self-report questionnaires include an inability to provide valid estimates of PA EE and MVPA in children (Shephard, 2003, Corder et al., 2009). Pedometers have also commonly been used to measure PA, with their simplicity, relatively low cost, and ability to pick up short durations of PA, often missed by self-report measures, making these devices popular with researchers (Sylvia et al., 2014). Nonetheless, pedometers are unable to record intensity, frequency, or

duration of PA, and have limited storage capacity (Freedson and Miller, 2000, McNamara, Hudson and Taylor, 2010).

Using accelerometers is the gold standard for measuring free-living PA in adults and children (Troiano et al., 2014). In PA research, accelerometers measure accelerations of the body segment to which the monitor is attached (Migueles et al., 2017). Some commonly used activity monitors for PA assessment in clinical and research applications include: the ActiGraph, ActivPAL, Actical, GENEActiv, RT3, and Lifecorder Plus (Strath et al., 2013). The ActiGraph (Pensacola, FL, USA) accelerometers are the most frequently used by researchers, accounting for >50% of published studies (Wijndaele et al., 2015). In 2009, ActiGraph launched a novel triaxial accelerometer, the so-called GT3X, which led to an important technological advancement in accelerometry development by offering the ability to access the triaxial raw acceleration data prior to being processed, filtered and scaled from devices. The ActiGraph GT3X has been used within a variety of populations including adult hospitalised patients recovering from critical illness children with cerebral palsy (O'Neil et al., 2014, Anderson, 2017). These accelerometers have also been used in different research settings including the laboratory setting, field-based settings such as schools and free-living environments (Aadland and Ylvisåker, 2015, Ferguson et al., 2015, Feehan et al., 2016, Borghese et al., 2017, Reid et al., 2017). The latest generation of ActiGraph devices include the GT3X+, wGT3X-BT and the GT9X link (ActiGraph, Pensacola, FL, USA). Establishing cut-points has been the most widely used method to create the link between accelerometer counts and PA intensity. Cut-points are typically developed from laboratory validation studies where participants perform various types of laboratory activities such as treadmill running or daily life activities whilst wearing an accelerometer alongside the concurrent collection of EE from a criterion measure such as indirect calorimetry. Accelerometer activity

counts are then compared to the criterion measure (i.e., METs) with the counts corresponding to defined values for EE of MVPA.

There are multiple cut-points available but findings suggest that the application of different cut-points can result in vastly different estimates of MVPA (Beets et al., 2011, Migueles et al., 2017). A recent review of European studies that objectively assessed PA with accelerometers reported that the prevalence of children meeting guidelines for sufficiently active youth ranged vastly between 3-100% depending on the cut-points used (Guinhouya, Samouda and de Beaufort, 2013). It has also been suggested that it is not possible, and probably never will be, to know the prevalence of those meeting the recommended PA guidelines from accelerometer cut-points as, prevalence rates can range from almost zero to nearly everyone (Migueles, Cadenas-Sanchez, et al., 2019).

In recent years, opportunities for measuring patterns of sitting/lying time have been made possible through the use of inclinometers such as the ActivPAL (PAL Technologies Ltd, Glasgow, UK) to detect postures. ActivPAL accelerometers are considered the gold standard in measuring SB's and have been found to be more accurate in their detection of SB's when compared to ActiGraph GT3X devices (Baumgartner et al., 2015, Kim, Barry and Kang, 2015). The ActivPAL4™ micro (PAL Technologies Ltd., Glasgow, UK), weighing 9g and measuring 25x45x5mm, quantifies sedentary time during free-living conditions. As with any accelerometer worn on the hip, the difficulty in differentiating sedentary activities based on posture makes the ActiGraph unable to distinguish between sitting and standing accurately (Hart, Ainsworth and Tudor-Locke, 2011). Indeed, numerous validation studies report the accuracy of the ActivPAL to distinguish sitting/lying, standing, stepping and features of SB including time-spent sitting/lying and breaks from sitting/lying (Godfrey, Culhane and Lyons, 2007, Grant et al., 2008, Chastin and Granat, 2010, Kozey-Keadle et al., 2011, Lyden et al., 2012, Bassett et al., 2014). These reports include both laboratory and free-living settings

involving diverse samples (e.g., toddlers to the elderly, men and women, lean and overweight, healthy and diseased, able-bodied and physical handicapped). Indeed, studies deploying ActivPAL devices have observed that children spent 614 mins per day on school days and 690 mins per day on weekend days sitting (Sherry et al., 2019). Additionally, when observing the SB's of obese children, one study found that obese children spend an average of 70% of their day sitting/lying, 19% of their day standing, and only 11% of their day stepping (Wafa et al., 2017). As such, in order to accurately assess SB and in doing so, obtain information regarding the movement behaviours of children across the whole day, future research deploying ActivPAL devices is warranted. Indeed, such research should be undertaken particularly in randomised control trials exploring the effectiveness of interventions which claim to improve such behaviours across the 24 h period.

Due to the extremely rapid development in accelerometry, there is an overwhelming amount of data collection and processing criteria decisions to be taken (Trost, Mciver and Pate, 2005, Matthews et al., 2012, Cain et al., 2013, Troiano et al., 2014, Migueles et al., 2017). However, such decisions are dependent upon multiple factors including the type of accelerometer device, placement location and population investigated (Migueles et al., 2017, Migueles, Cadenas-Sanchez, et al., 2019). Consequently, it is difficult for researchers and practitioners to make the right decisions about which criteria to use in a given situation. This is important as the chosen criteria can influence the outcome and limit the comparability of findings between studies. As the usual output from ActiGraph accelerometers is in proprietary counts, it is difficult to compare findings between studies using different accelerometer brands. Moreover, these laboratory produced cut-points are dependent on the calibration sample and protocol used which can also make their application to populations that differ from the validation sample challenging (Troiano et al., 2014). Given the known limitations of relying upon cut-points to estimate PA, Rowlands et al., (2019) aimed to

demonstrate how data-driven accelerometer metrics, can (a) quantify the prevalence of meeting current PA guidelines for global surveillance, and (b) moving forward, could inform accelerometer-driven PA guidelines (Rowlands, Plekhanova, et al., 2019). In doing so, the authors hoped that such metrics would provide a means to harmonize accelerometer-assessed activity outcomes across epidemiological datasets that may have used different accelerometers.

Overall activity level, defined as AvAcc over a 24 h period, is directly measured and does not rely on population-specific calibration protocols to derive outcome measures; thus, AvAcc is comparable across studies and populations (Rowlands et al., 2018). However, it tells us little about the intensity distribution (i.e., IG) as it is possible to have a high AvAcc because of a large volume of LPA and relatively little or no MVPA, or because of a substantial amount of MVPA with a large volume of sedentary time (Rowlands et al., 2018). Therefore, it is important to capture both overall activity and intensity distribution as these two metrics can be used to quantify both the intensity and volume of activity undertaken. As such the two metrics together would use the rich nature of the data available to more fully describe the 24 h activity-related behaviour profile. The benefits of reporting these metrics lie in their suitability for comparison across studies and subsequent populations including parents and children, since the metrics are not reliant upon calibration protocols or certain populations (Rowlands et al., 2018).

Recent studies reporting AvAcc and IG illustrate the potential of these metrics for generating age and sex-specific percentile norms (Buchan, McLellan, et al., 2019, Fairclough, Taylor, Rowlands and Boddy, 2019, Rowlands, Plekhanova, et al., 2019). For instance, the PA profiles of five diverse datasets were examined from wrist-worn accelerometers in children ($n=145$), adolescent girls ($n=1669$), office workers ($n=114$), pre- ($n=1218$) and post- ($n=1316$) menopausal women, and adults with type 2 diabetes ($n=475$) (Rowlands,

Sherar, et al., 2019). Multiple regression analyses showed the IG, but not AvAcc, was independently associated with BMI z-score and % body fat in children and adolescents. In adults, associations were stronger, and the effects of AvAcc and IG were additive. Elsewhere, findings have found that AvAcc to be negatively associated with BMI z-score independent of age and gender but not IG (Buchan, McLellan, et al., 2019, Fairclough, Taylor, Rowlands and Boddy, 2019). From the same studies, the authors found that IG was negatively associated with BMI z-score independent of potential correlates and AvAcc, whereas total MVPA was not associated with BMI-z score (Buchan, McLellan, et al., 2019, Fairclough, Taylor, Rowlands and Boddy, 2019). These are important findings and suggest that the IG and AvAcc metrics may be used to explore the independent or cumulative effects of the volume and intensity distribution of activity upon measures of HWB in children to inform specific activity recommendations.

In a recent study, Fairclough and colleagues aimed to demonstrate that applying an equivalent cut-point to the M30_{ACC} metric would give similar, and therefore comparable prevalence results as a traditional MVPA cut-point approach (Fairclough, Taylor, Rowlands and Boddy, 2019). School day MVPA and the minimum acceleration value above which the most active 30 mins were accumulated during school (i.e., M30_{ACC}) were calculated. Less than half of girls and 75% of boys accumulated 30 mins of school day MVPA. Agreement between MVPA and M30_{ACC} tertiles was high, and as such, these findings demonstrate that M30_{ACC} has the potential as an accelerometer-specific metric that does not rely upon population specific laboratory generated cut-points. The high degree of comparability of this approach due to the minimal influence of researcher decision-making is a key advantage over cut-points and should be reported alongside traditional activity measures in future studies.

In addition to the challenge of comparability between monitor brands, an additional challenge is the comparability of raw accelerometer outputs from monitors placed on

different body locations. Limitations of hip-placed accelerometers usually include underestimation of EE during activities with little or no movement at the hip in addition to the potential loss of data due to removal of the monitor when dressing, participating in some sports (e.g., swimming), and whilst sleeping (Migueles et al., 2017). Findings have shown greater wear time compliance with wrist-placement devices in comparison to hip-worn devices when worn concurrently (Fairclough et al., 2016, McLellan, Arthur and Buchan, 2018). Indeed, it has been found that wear time compliance for the wrist is greater than the hip, regardless of WTC applied in children aged 9-12 years old (Fairclough et al., 2016, McLellan, Arthur and Buchan, 2018). Given this increased compliance rate evident from wrist-worn accelerometers, a number of researchers have advocated placing accelerometers at the wrist to evaluate PA given the potential of capturing more data which may be more representative of habitual activity levels (Troiano et al., 2014). As such, future research should focus on the use of novel accelerometry metrics with data being captured from wrist worn accelerometers to facilitate comparisons between future studies employing different accelerometer devices and involving different populations including parents and children.

2.6 School-based interventions to improve children's health-related behaviours

The UK Government views schools as central to tackling the obesity crisis as they are an ideal setting in which to actively engage children and their families across the socioeconomic spectrum with the aim of fostering health-conducive behaviours (e.g., increase PA and healthy eating) (UK Government, 2017). The school setting has been recognised as an ideal environment for population-based PA interventions for decades, as it provides benefit to children from all risk groups, particularly those with limited or no access to play areas and avoids stigmatization of at-risk children (Harrell et al., 1996, McKenzie et al., 1996). Therefore interventions directed at entire school populations (e.g., whole-school

approach) could effectively avoid this stigmatization (Dobbins et al., 2013). School-based strategies targeting all students across the educational curriculum ensures 100% of students are exposed to the intervention. Without intervention, obese infants and young children will likely continue to be obese during childhood, adolescence and adulthood (World Health Organization, 2019). There is good evidence from systematic reviews that school-based interventions are effective in increasing health-related outcomes including: the duration of PA, reducing blood cholesterol, reducing time spent watching television, and increasing $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ (Kriemler et al., 2011, Demetriou and Höner, 2012, Dobbins et al., 2013, Lonsdale et al., 2013). However, more recent reviews have presented conflicting results regarding the effectiveness of such interventions to foster health-conducive behaviours (Love, Adams and Sluijs, 2018, Norris et al., 2019, Jones et al., 2020). One review provides the first meta-analysis of the effects of physically active lessons on educational outcomes and overall PA, as well as health, cognition and educational outcomes (Norris et al., 2019). This review suggests that, in elementary and preschool settings, PA lessons incorporated into the curriculum can have a positive impact on both PA and educational outcomes. These findings support policy initiatives encouraging the incorporation of PA lessons into teaching in elementary and preschool settings. Nevertheless, another recent meta-analysis of cluster randomized control trials with accelerometer-assessed activity indicates that school-based PA interventions are not effective in increasing young people's PA across the full day (Love, Adams and Sluijs, 2018). Within this review, twenty-five trials met the inclusion criteria, and 17 trials provided relevant data for inclusion in the meta-analyses. The pooled main effect for daily mins of MVPA was non-existent and non-significant with no evidence of differential effectiveness by gender or socioeconomic position (Love et al, 2018). This review provides the strongest evidence to date that current school-based efforts do not positively impact young people's PA across the full day, with no difference in effect across gender and

socioeconomic position (Love, Adams and Sluijs, 2018). More recently, a mixed-studies systematic review and meta-analysis of school-based interventions to promote PA and/or reduce SB in children also found no evidence of effect on MVPA and inconclusive evidence of effects of sedentary time (Jones et al., 2020).

Compared to school-based interventions, less work has been undertaken implementing and evaluating the effectiveness of after-school based obesity prevention interventions (Branscum et al., 2012). With ever-increasing demands being placed upon school staff, and recent literature observing school-based interventions to be ineffective in improving activity in children when examining accelerometer-derived mins of MVPA across the whole day (Fairclough et al., 2013, Hollis et al., 2016, Tymms et al., 2016), it is vital that researchers and practitioners target alternative settings that still service a large number of children but are also sustainable to promote behaviour change. As such, programmes delivered after-school may offer promise for obesity prevention programming as there is more available time with fewer bureaucratic obstacles and curricular inflexibilities when compared to school-based programmes (Pate and O'Neill, 2009). A meta-analysis of the impact of after-school programmes on PA and fitness in children observed positive effect sizes for PA, physical fitness, body composition, and blood lipids (Beets, Beighle, Erwin, & Huberty, 2009). The expansion of PA opportunities including after-school activities, active travel, and multidimensional intervention strategies across settings (e.g., home and school) are likely required to achieve sustained effects across the whole day and are the most promising types of interventions. As such, further research is warranted which presents greater attention to theoretical rationale, levels of implementation, and measures of PA to improve the effectiveness of health-related interventions.

Indeed, programmes can often not be implemented in the same way as intended by programme developers, which could be labelled as a 'lack of fidelity' or 'programme failure'

(Schaap et al., 2018). A better understanding of the implementation process is important to determine if and when disappointing effects can be ascribed to intervention failure. Whilst there is growing recognition for conducting process evaluations, previous studies have commonly focussed on examining programme effectiveness, with process evaluations often being an afterthought (Naylor et al., 2015). Indeed, Medical Research Council (MRC) guidelines advocate consultation with the end-user in the design and implementation of complex interventions (Craig et al., 2008, Senn et al., 2013). A qualitative study and process evaluation exploring the development of parent involvement in school-based obesity prevention interventions found school newsletters and homework that included events such as cooking and physically active games to be a feasible way of involving parents (Kipping, Jago, & Lawlor, 2012).

2.6.1 Parent involvement in interventions

Research suggests that without the involvement of family members in PA promotion, it is unlikely that long-term change in children's PA levels is possible (Van Sluijs and McMinn, 2010, Kipping et al., 2014). Parent support, such as provision of transport, co-participation or encouragement has been consistently and positively associated with the PA levels of youths (Gustafson and Rhodes, 2006). A systematic review exploring interventions aiming to promote PA in youths suggests that the addition of a family component (e.g., parent education) to school-based health interventions has shown to be efficacious (Van Sluijs et al., 2007). Indeed, a systematic review and meta-analysis of parent participation in weight-related health interventions suggests that parent involvement in school-based interventions has been found to effectively reduce the BMI of child and adolescent participants (Niemeier, Hektner and Enger, 2012). Furthermore, a systematic review of the effectiveness of school-based PA and nutrition interventions suggests that school-based interventions with direct parental involvement have the potential to improve children's weight status, PA and SB (Verjans-

Janssen et al., 2018). Additionally, findings from another systematic review examining the effectiveness of school-based interventions in Europe to promote healthy nutrition found school-based health interventions involving parents to be more effective than interventions which do not include a parent component (Van Cauwenberghe et al., 2010).

As childhood obesity is an urgent public health concern, longitudinal, high-quality, primary interventions involving parents and children are warranted (Enö Persson et al., 2018). Requiring the active participation of parents is important to increase the effectiveness of school-based interventions, as they are influential in modelling and establishing children's eating and PA patterns (Savage, Fisher and Birch, 2007, Goldthorpe et al., 2020). Moreover, multiple systematic reviews have reported that higher intervention effects for children are observed by involving parents in interventions to prevent overweight and obesity in various settings (Golley et al., 2011, Ward et al., 2017). Unfortunately, many researchers struggle to recruit and retain parents with low SES to their research studies (Robinson et al., 2016). Indeed, parents with low SES tend to be less involved in their child's education than more affluent parents and experience multiple barriers to being involved (Hornby and Lafaele, 2011, Roksa and Potter, 2011). As such they are also less likely to engage in additional activities such as school-based health initiatives and subsequently a small proportion of the target group are exposed to the intervention, who are often those least in need of intervention (Mytton et al., 2013). Whilst robust recommendations exist to engage parents of varying levels of SES, these are often provided in the context of children's academic achievement and behaviour (Reid et al., 1999). As such, the lack of inclusion of parents with low SES is a limitation which is common within school-based health interventions, and further exploration of their perceptions is warranted to effectively engage these groups in future school-based activities (Norman, Nyberg, Elinder, & Berlin, 2016).

A study employing focus groups to explore parents' views on engaging families of middle school students in obesity prevention and control found that parents interest in participating in obesity prevention programs was apparent, however their motivation to engage in the program was not as a result of their desire to improve the health of their families (Cowgill et al., 2014). Instead, their motivation to engage in the programme stemmed from an overarching desire among parents to feel better about themselves as parents, which could lead to pursuing improvements in their family's health behaviours (Cowgill et al., 2014). Parents wanted to lead by example, navigate their busy lives more efficiently, and develop needed skills and knowledge that would allow them to participate in cooking classes and family sports leagues (Cowgill et al., 2014). Exploration of behaviour change techniques in school-based obesity prevention interventions identifies that interventions should also be focused on developing not only children's perceived competence at making dietary and PA changes, but also parent competence to make the same health-related changes (Nixon et al., 2012). As such, school staff have a responsibility to develop competencies at a family level which in-turn should encourage health-conducive behaviour changes to happen across the school and home settings.

Parents play a vital role in the promotion of health behaviours in children. A systematic review on parent involvement in long-term European childhood weight control interventions with a nutritional focus found that low parental involvement was identified in prevention studies, whereas medium and high parental involvement were frequently reported in long-term effective treatment studies (Kruk et al., 2013). Interventions rarely consider the complexity of parents' working and living arrangements, how these would vary dependent on SES, and the lack of supportive strategies likely to diminish the potential for change (Summerbell et al., 2005). The majority of lifestyle interventions for children have focused on the promotion of healthy behaviours while children are at school; however, there is a

growing body of evidence suggesting that children are more likely to consume unhealthy foods when at home (Rockell et al., 2011, Pleasant et al., 2019). Limited studies have examined parent-child interventions outside school and in the home setting. It's important therefore that future research examines this setting to establish whether it's a viable setting for sustainable intervention delivery.

Given the increasing levels of social deprivation in central Scotland, parent involvement in Scottish school-based health education is likely to present unique challenges (Scottish Government, 2020). Studies which look at the perceptions of parents and their involvement in education suggests that the perceptions of uninvolved parents are not captured (Yoder & Lopez, 2013). Uninvolved parents, commonly referred to as hard-to-reach parents, can be defined as: (a) the unemployed, (b) those with low income, (c) those who have English as an additional language, and (d) those of poor attendance/unresponsive (Campbell, 2011). A possible strategy to increase both parent involvement in school-based interventions and to increase activity behaviour profiles in children, could be through the use of health-related homework tasks. Although established research provides specific domains, strategies and processes which influence parent involvement, steps to effectively improve parent involvement in school-based activities remain unclear, particularly in relation to health education in Scotland (Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler, 1995, Peña, 2000, Hoover-Dempsey et al., 2005, Walker et al., 2005, Hill and Tyson, 2009). As such, Chapter 4 (Study 1) of this thesis will explore the perceptions of mothers with low SES who are typically less-involved in school-based activities. In doing so, the aim was to explore their perceptions regarding their involvement in school-based HWB activities.

2.6.2 School-based homework interventions to increase PA

Homework has been implemented as a method to improve health behaviours in children for years, however the concept of curriculum-based PA or nutrition 'homework' is

relatively under-utilised (Duncan et al., 2019). Various studies have tried to promote PA and/or healthy eating outside of school by incorporating homework components into school-based interventions with some studies demonstrating positive results (Luepker et al., 1996, McKenzie et al., 1996, Friel et al., 1999, Fitzgibbon et al., 2005, Christodoulos et al., 2006, Manios, Kafatos and Kafatos, 2006, Marcus et al., 2009, Kriemler et al., 2010, Duncan et al., 2011, 2019, Eather, Morgan and Lubans, 2013, Eyre et al., 2016). Nevertheless, some studies have shown no intervention effect (McKenzie et al., 1997, Pate et al., 2003, Warren et al., 2003, Hopper et al., 2005, Fitzgibbon et al., 2006, Reilly et al., 2006, Abraham and Michie, 2008, Resaland et al., 2016, Aadland et al., 2019). In all cases, homework assumed secondary importance to in-school components and primarily, such interventions tend to implement homework components within fairly complex interventions.

The Healthy Homework intervention was a compulsory homework programme with the primary aim of the intervention being to improve PA and dietary behaviours in participating children through homework activities (Duncan et al., 2011, 2019). Ten key sub-behaviours were identified for intervention and included: (1) walking frequency, (2) TV use, (3) participation in sport, (4) participation in informal games, (5) participation in fitness activities, (6) fruit and vegetable consumption, (7) breakfast consumption, (8) fluid intake, (9) food labelling knowledge, and (10) food preparation knowledge. In the most recent cluster randomised control trial examining the efficacy of Healthy Homework, PA was the primary outcome measure, and was assessed using two sealed pedometers that monitored school- and home-based activity separately (Duncan et al., 2019). Secondary outcome measures included screen-based sedentary time and selected dietary patterns assessed via parental proxy questionnaire. From their analysis, the authors found significant intervention effects were observed for weekday PA at home, weekend PA, BMI, and fruit consumption. Additional analyses revealed that the greatest improvements in PA occurred in children from the most

socioeconomically deprived schools. No consistent effects on sedentary time, waist-to-height ratio, or other dietary patterns were observed. Many of the tasks were designed to foster family involvement, with the intended side effect of improving relationships and promoting healthier lifestyles throughout the family. Pedometers were used to assess PA and fidelity was not assessed, therefore the overall intervention effect should be interpreted with caution. Nevertheless, homework appears to be a feasible and effective way of fostering health-conducive behaviours in school-children. Further exploration of theoretically-underpinned homework interventions which are multi-component in nature and involve parents is warranted through objective measures of PA and SB as well as sleep to examine the effects over the whole day.

2.7 Theoretical underpinning

There is no single, correct or universal theoretical framework for a particular area of study (Gibbs et al., 2011). Given the complexity of issues associated with increasing PA in children, it is likely that several theoretical frameworks are needed to guide interventions and to interpret their findings (Gibbs et al., 2011). The need for theoretically informed intervention design when aiming to change behaviour, including school-based health interventions is profound. As epidemiological research has associated multiple chronic disease risk with participation in health-related behaviours (e.g., Loeff and Walach, 2012), health organizations and Governments globally have sought to develop behavioural interventions that lead to practically-significant changes in these behaviours and concomitant reduction in disease risk (Hagger and Weed, 2019). Behavioural scientists propose that interventions based on theories from the behavioural sciences, particularly psychology, will be optimally effective in evoking behaviour change (Glanz and Bishop, 2010). Indeed, evidence suggests that theory-informed school-based interventions aiming to tackle obesity are more effective in doing so, compared to interventions that do not utilize a theory (Sharma,

2006). Debates regarding the extent to which interventions based on behavioural theory work in the real world to address population health outcomes are evident in the literature (Hagger and Weed, 2019). Incorporating evidence-based strategies is critical to increase the likelihood of successful school-based obesity prevention interventions (Ickes et al., 2014). Nevertheless, with literature indicating that there is no clear consensus of the most effective mechanisms to design and implement an effective school-based obesity prevention intervention, or which theory to use, guidance is needed.

The MRC have specific guidelines for developing and evaluating complex interventions (Craig et al., 2008, Senn et al., 2013). These guidelines suggest that, when developing a complex intervention, it is important to identify and develop theory as the rationale for a complex intervention. A key early task in the design of interventions is to develop a theoretical understanding of the likely process of change (i.e., behaviour) by drawing on existing evidence and theory, supplemented if necessary by new primary research. This should be done whether the researcher is developing the intervention or evaluating one that has already been developed.

In a study in which Hagger and Weed debate whether interventions based on behavioural theory work in the real world, Hagger debates that there is fundamental evidence supporting the efficacy and effectiveness of interventions underpinned by behavioural theory when promoting population-level health behaviour change in the real world setting (Hagger and Weed, 2019). Weed argues there is no evidence to demonstrate behavioural theory interventions are genuinely effective in real world settings in populations that are offered them, believing that they are only efficacious for the participants that are involved (Hagger and Weed, 2019). Hagger challenges this and argues that interventions based on behavioural theory are effective in changing population-level behaviour in real world contexts, however more evidence on the best methods to implement them and how to engage policymakers and

practitioners to provide sustained funding is warranted (Hagger and Weed, 2019). Weed calls for a paradigm shift, moving away from aggregative efforts to influence behaviour change and towards a focus on disrupting social practices (Hagger and Weed, 2019). Regarding Hagger's argument, it is clear that theory-informed school-based interventions have found to be more effective than those which are not underpinned by theory, and include the use of various theories (Sharma, 2006, Ickes et al., 2014, Ntoumanis et al., 2020). However, with regards to Weed's encouragement towards a paradigm shift away from disrupting social practices, it is realistic for interventions to be implemented, underpinned by theory, in a real-world setting (e.g., homework tasks) to improve children's health-related outcomes including activity and weight.

A substantive body of research has identified the effectiveness of theory-based interventions targeting change in modifiable determinants or mechanisms of health (Kok et al., 2016, Massey et al., 2017). To maximise the effectiveness of interventions, designers of such interventions are likely to benefit from drawing from a wider range of theories than currently used (Davis et al., 2015). A review of reviews surrounding the effects of school-based interventions to control childhood obesity examined the findings from studies which reported an application of theoretical frameworks in their interventions (Amini et al., 2015). Four reviews and meta-analyses were identified which did not mention and test the theory of behaviour change used in the single studies. One meta-analysis and two reviews mentioned names of theories used in primary studies but did not assess their effectiveness (Kanekar and Sharma, 2008, Brown and Summerbell, 2009, Silveira et al., 2011). Such theories included Social Cognitive Theory and the Theory of Reasoned Action. In one review five studies had applied psychological theories in which two studies applying Social Cognitive Theory had a significant effect on overweight (Lissau, 2007). A lack of reporting theory utilisation within review articles is evident, which hinders research in the pursuit of optimal frameworks to

inform behaviour change within obesity and PA interventions. Nonetheless, informing school-based interventions with theory would appear to provide a guided protocol to encourage positive intervention effects by promoting health behaviour change.

2.7.1 Behaviour change theory in School-based interventions

Conceptual models and research studies have explored various factors that may increase parent involvement in school-based education and activities (Walker et al., 2005, Olmstead, 2013, Williams and Sánchez, 2013, Marschall and Shah, 2016). The Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler model of the parent involvement process describes the specific processes that influence parents' decisions to engage in parent involvement school-based education (Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler, 1995, Walker et al., 2005). Hoover-Dempsey and colleagues (1995) hypothesize that parents' decisions to engage in parent involvement are influenced by three motivational factors: (1) motivational beliefs, (2) parent's perceptions of invitations to become involved, and (3) parents' personal life context. Therefore, as undertaken in Chapter 4 (Study 1), research exploring parent's motivational factors to be involved and how their personal life can influence this should be encouraged.

A systematic review which identified effective behavioural models and behaviour change strategies which underpinned school-based obesity prevention interventions for children found that the most commonly used model was social cognitive theory/social learning theory either as a single model or in combination with other behavioural models (Nixon et al., 2012). Studies that used social cognitive theory/social learning theory in the development of the intervention had significant favourable changes in one, or more, outcome measures (Nixon et al., 2012). It is important to recognise that within this review of studies adopting behaviour change strategies, 10 of the 12 studies also involved parents or caregivers, with European and Non-European studies adopting behaviour change theories such as Self-determination theory (SDT), Social cognitive theory and the transtheoretical

model all indicating high levels of parent involvement (Nixon et al., 2012). In fact, parental involvement and behaviour change techniques are often cited as important determinants of the effectiveness of long-term childhood weight control interventions (Kruk et al., 2013). The conceptual framework provided by SDT can be used to explain long-term adherence to positive health behaviours by exploring the dynamics of motivation during behavioural change (Ryan and Deci, 2000a). SDT proposes that motivation varies in kind and not just in amount, that internal motivation is energized through the satisfaction of an individual's basic psychological needs, and that there are several forms of regulatory motives which vary along a continuum of self-determination, reflecting the extent to which the individual acts with volition instead of feeling forced to act.

2.7.2 SDT

SDT suggests that motivation can be categorised according to whether it is driven by reasons emanating from the self (e.g., pleasure or satisfaction), or in response to external demands (e.g., expectation of rewards or punishments) (Ryan and Deci, 2000a). At its core, SDT promotes the idea of three basic psychological needs: (1) all individuals strive for and need autonomy (the need to feel free and self-directed), (2) competence (the need to feel effective), and (3) relatedness (the need to connect closely with others) in order to develop (Ryan and Deci, 2000a). SDT highlights a series of behavioural regulations graded on a continuum of autonomy (i.e. self-determination). Applied to PA, these include: (a) amotivation (i.e., where a person lacks any motivation to be physically active), (b) external regulation (i.e., where PA motivation is regulated by tangible rewards or avoidance of punishments), (c) introjected regulation (i.e., driven by self-administered and intrapersonal contingencies of activity including guilt), (d) identified regulation (i.e., underpinned by expected personally valued outcomes of activity: integrated regulation, arising from the congruence of activity with self-identity), and (e) intrinsic regulation (i.e., characterised by

inherent interest in activity itself) (Gardner and Lally, 2013). Research has shown that meeting children's basic psychological needs is predictive of PA participation as they are more likely to experience more autonomous forms of motivation (Breslin et al., 2017).

While the focus on consequences renders external, introjected, and identified regulation (i.e., forms of extrinsic motivation), identified regulation sits on the autonomous end of the continuum, together with integrated and intrinsic regulation (Ryan and Connell, 1989). Research has shown that self-determined regulation is associated with greater PA intensity, frequency and duration (Edmunds, Ntoumanis and Duda, 2006, Wilson et al., 2006, Standage, Sebire and Loney, 2008, Duncan et al., 2010). Internally driven regulation prompts stronger PA intentions (Biddle, Soos and Chatzisarantis, 1999) and, when controlling for intention strength, intentions based on autonomous motivation are more likely to translate into PA (Chatzisarantis, Biddle and Meek, 1997). Regulatory style also determines maintenance, with autonomously regulated activity more likely to be sustained over time (Ryan et al., 1997, Daley and Duda, 2006, Thøgersen-Ntoumani and Ntoumanis, 2006, Silva et al., 2011). This may perhaps reflect a tendency for self-determined PA to become habitual. As such, Chapter 7 (Study 4) within this thesis presents the findings from a homework intervention based on SDT which aimed to satisfy children's basic psychological needs through tasks aimed at encouraging habitual activity and positive dietary behaviours.

2.7.2.1 SDT applied in School-based interventions

The application of motivational theory such as SDT within health-related interventions including school-based interventions has increased (Ryan and Deci, 2000a, Girelli and Luccidi, 2016, Sebire, Kesten, et al., 2016, González-Cutre et al., 2018, Demetriou and Bachner, 2019). A school-based motivational intervention to promote PA from a SDT perspective found significant intervention effects for various outcomes including

parental and peer autonomy support, children's integrated regulation in PE and physical self-worth (González-Cutre et al., 2018). Indeed, a recent meta-analysis of SDT-informed intervention studies in the health domain (including schools) observed there was evidence demonstrating modest efficacy of SDT-based interventions to change health behaviours, primarily regarding PA, and to a lesser extent dietary behaviours (Ntoumanis et al., 2020). Generally, SDT-informed interventions were found to positively affect indices of health, although these effects were modest, heterogeneous, and partly due to increases in self-determined motivation and support from social agents (Ntoumanis et al., 2020). Despite clear guidance (Craig et al., 2008, Senn et al., 2013) and encouraging effects (González-Cutre et al., 2018) relating to the use of theory in interventions, researchers frequently overlook the need to underpin their behaviour change interventions with appropriate theory such as SDT, or in fact, fail to incorporate theoretical underpinning entirely (Davis et al., 2015). As such, future research is warranted which underpins school-based interventions with SDT transparently in order to encourage researchers to apply such theory to their future interventions.

2.8 Overall summary

Children continue to be inactive, with <20% of those from Scotland, among other countries, failing to meet recommended PA guidelines of 60 mins of MVPA (Aubert et al., 2018). Despite the links between inactivity and its key correlates including obesity, SES and parent involvement being well-established, limited understanding of how to affect these correlates to improve children's PA levels remains. As research in this area advances, so too does the efforts made to provide interventions which aim to tackle these issues. School-based interventions aiming to improve health-related outcomes in children are widely recognised as an appropriate site to achieve this aim. Nevertheless, recent school-based interventions have

shown to be ineffective in increasing positive health behaviours including accelerometry-derived activity (Fairclough et al., 2013, Hollis et al., 2016, Tymms et al., 2016).

Whilst research is being progressively published in areas surrounding school-based interventions to improve children's health, studies are typically failing to take into consideration the recommendations presented from previous process evaluations of school-based interventions. Growing evidence suggests that school-based interventions should be multicomponent in nature, underpinned by theory, and include a family component (Kriemler et al., 2011, Bleich et al., 2018, Ntoumanis et al., 2020). Research also suggests that children most effected by inactivity and increased weight status are those of lowest SES, whose parents are less likely to participate in studies aiming to foster health-conducive behaviours (Moraes et al., 2012, Tremblay et al., 2014, Robinson et al., 2016). Therefore, to develop and implement sound interventions in the school setting more research is warranted surrounding the design, development and implementation of such interventions, as childhood inactivity and in turn, obesity, is an overwhelming public health concern. As such, this thesis aims to understand the perspectives of typically uninvolved parents with low SES, and the relationship between parent and child activity to effectively implement a school-based, multicomponent intervention formed upon homework activities. Such activities were curriculum-based and encouraged the involvement of parents in health-related activities. The specific aims of the thesis are broken down and detailed further in the following section.

CHAPTER 3

GENERAL METHODOLOGY

3.1 Overview

This chapter aims to describe and justify the use of these methods. Additional methods and/or study specific procedures will be described in their relevant chapters. Many of the same methods are applied across studies. Furthermore, the studies completed for this thesis include mixed-methodologies, combining both qualitative and quantitative research components. The overall goal of mixed-methods research, is to expand and strengthen a study's conclusions and heighten knowledge and validity within an area of research (Schoonenboom and Burke Johnson, 2017). Indeed, by integrating qualitative and quantitative data, a more comprehensive understanding of complex public health issues may be reached. As such, the mixed-method approach is widely used in public health research surrounding children's activity and the involvement of their parents (Solomon-Moore et al., 2018). Additionally, such approach is particularly appropriate in studies which aim to determine the effectiveness, feasibility and acceptability of interventions aimed at improving health outcomes in children (Khan and Bell, 2019, Whooten, Horan, Cordes, Dartley, Aguirre, and Taveras 2020).

3.2 Ethical approval

All studies received ethical approval from the School of Health and Life Sciences Ethics Committee at The University of the West of Scotland prior to recruitment of participants. For Chapter 4, the Ethical Approval number was 19-10-16-001. For Chapter 5 and 6, the Ethical Application number was 0938 and the submission number was 837. For Chapter 7, the Ethical application number was 6571 and the submission number was 6610.

3.3 Research assistants and sensitivity

The lead researcher carried out all measures, accompanied by research assistants who comprised solely of academic colleagues (PhD Students) with similar research interests relating to the activity levels of children/adolescents. These colleagues did not require any

training due to the experience they already had in collecting similar measures within their own postgraduate research. During data collection, head teachers, class teachers, and/or teaching support staff were of assistance to the researchers by ensuring the children were completing their questionnaires in a timely manner and not being disruptive to other classes whilst waiting to have their anthropometric measures taken, or being provided with their accelerometers. Sensitive measurements such as the measurement of mass were taken during school time in secluded areas where both the pupils and researchers were visible to school staff.

3.4 Participants and consent

All participants participated in the studies voluntarily. The Head Teachers from each school were approached prior to advertising the study and were provided with information regarding the relevant aims of the proposed study. Opportunities to ask any questions regarding the study were also afforded to the Head Teacher at the initial meeting. Once the Head Teacher of each school provided informed written consent to participate in the study, participants and their parents/guardians were provided with information sheets detailing each studies procedure and their involvement in the study itself prior to distributing participant assent and parental consent forms. Participants were made aware that they could drop out of the study at any point and without reason. Chapter-specific participant recruitment details will be outlined in the following sub-sections.

3.4.1. Chapter 4 - Study 1: An Insight Into the involvement of Mothers of low Socioeconomic Status in Scottish Primary School Health Education Activities.

An initial recruitment drive was carried out across five primary schools in Glasgow and Lanarkshire, Scotland, in which awareness building strategies including handing out flyers (See appendix 1A) and speaking at assembly events which were attended by parents was undertaken. Afterwards, parent evenings were attended which is an event in which

parents attend their child's school in the evening to discuss their child's progress at school with their class teacher. Parent evenings were chosen as a recruitment site as parents from various socioeconomic backgrounds and those who typically would not attend school for health-related activities, would be in attendance. At these events, a stall was set up with posters outlining the study protocol. Parents were recruited based on those who were approached by the researchers/came to the stall and were provided with information and consent forms ($n = 132$) (See appendix 1B and 1C) as well as a FIQ-E (See appendix 1D) which is detailed in its sub-section below. Of the 132 parents who completed these forms (113 female, 19 male), 120 agreed to be interviewed. Of the 120 parents who agreed to be interviewed, 24 mothers (18.18%) met the inclusion criteria based on being less-involved and with low SES, and 16 mothers were interviewed using an interview guide (see Appendix 1E). All eligible mothers were contacted by telephone up to four times, five mothers were contacted but did not answer the telephone, and three rearranged the call for more convenient times but failed to answer subsequent calls. Eligibility criteria for the interviews included: (a) the mother of the child, (b) scored below the median response of parents in the sample (below 2) on the FIQ-E (Manz, Fantuzzo, & Power, 2004), and (c) low levels of SES based on an index of deprivation linked to their home address which suggested they resided within 20% of the most deprived areas in the country (SIMD) (Scottish Government, 2016b). Data collection took place in May 2017.

3.4.2. Chapter 5 - Study 2: The effects of socioeconomic status on parent and child dyads moderate-to-vigorous physical activity and body mass index and Chapter 6 - Study 3: Relationship between parent and child physical activity using novel acceleration metrics.

Parent-child dyads were recruited for both Chapter 5 (Study 2) and Chapter 6 (Study 3) via a whole-school approach (Primary 1-7; 4-11 years old) in six primary schools across

Lanarkshire and Glasgow, Scotland. Recruitment took place during parent evenings where parents were provided with information see (Appendix 2A) and consent forms ($n = 201$) (see Appendix 2B) to complete on behalf of themselves and their child. Parental attendance at these events is normally high and parents are directly contacted by teachers if they do not attend. As such we hoped to recruit a diverse range of parents, including those who may be less likely to volunteer to participate in school-based research activities. Each family chose which parent participated in the study during the recruitment phase. Data collection took place between October 2018 and May 2019. Children ($n = 201$; $n = 103$ boys) and one of their parents ($n = 151$ female) consented to participate in the study. In Study 2, 113 dyads (56.22%) met the inclusion criteria (i.e., study-specific inclusion information can be found in Chapter 7) whereas in Study 3, 90 dyads (44.78%) met the inclusion criteria (i.e., study-specific inclusion information can be found in Chapter 6).

3.4.3 Chapter 7 - Study 4: Exploring the feasibility of a cluster-randomised control trial to improve children's 24 h movement behaviours and dietary intake: Happy Homework.

Head teachers, classroom teachers, parents and children aged 9-12 years from four primary schools across Lanarkshire, Scotland, were recruited. Head teachers and classroom teachers were aware that their involvement in the study may entail the delivery of a HWB intervention once the schools involved had been randomised. Head teachers (see appendices 3A and 3B) and classroom teachers (see appendices 3C and 3D) received informed consent paperwork. One class per school was selected by the Head teacher based on the pupils ages (9-12 years old), and informed consent paperwork was issued to each child (see Appendices 3E and 3F) in the four classes ($n = 128$; 69 girls) and their parent (see Appendices 3G and 3H). Families also received additional paperwork regarding device information (see Appendix 3I). Due to a low return-rate of consent from one school, an additional class was

selected by the Headteacher and additional ($n = 30$) informed consent paperwork was issued. The reason for the low-return rate from the school was unclear. Therefore, children ($n = 158$) and one of their parents were provided with information and consent information regarding the study, with 68 children and their parent (42.41%) included in the study. Schools were randomised into two intervention schools and two control schools. Schools were blinded to this information until pre-intervention measures were collected from each child. Data collection took place between April - June 2019.

3.5 Measures

Study-specific measures are detailed in their respective chapters. The following subsections will detail the general measures used in these research studies outlined in Chapters 4-7.

3.5.1 Anthropometrics

Body mass measurements were used in Chapters 5-7 and measured barefoot to the nearest 0.1kg with an electronic scale (Seca Digital Scales, Seca Ltd, Birmingham, UK) while stature was measured barefoot to the nearest 0.1cm using a stadiometer (Seca Stadiometer, Seca Ltd, Birmingham, UK) in accordance with standard procedures (Cole, Freeman and Preece, 1995). BMI was calculated as the weight in kilograms divided by the square of the height in meters. BMI z-score of each child participant was determined, and children were classified as healthy weight or obese/overweight relative to the UK 1990 BMI population reference data (Cole, Freeman and Preece, 1995). Using software provided by the Child Growth Foundation (Pan and Cole, 2010) the following definitions were applied for healthy weight (BMI z-score <1.04 , below the 85th percentile) and overweight/obese (BMI z-score ≥ 1.04 , above the 85th percentile) individuals. Parent BMI was classified relative to the World Health Organization (WHO) classification (World Health Organization, 2018a), with BMI scores <18.5 defined as underweight, 18.5 to <25 defined as normal weight, 25 to <30

defined as overweight, excluding obese, 30 to <40 defined as obese excluding morbidly obese, and ≥ 40 defined as morbidly obese. BMI is ideally suited for population-level studies and has been used to examine obesity within Chapters 5-7 of this thesis. Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge the limitations associated with BMI when examining obesity. Research has shown that the numerator in the calculation of BMI fails to distinguish lean muscle from fat mass and as such, by describing obesity by BMI, an inaccurate assessment of adiposity may be presented (Cornier et al., 2011). Furthermore, BMI fails to consider sex differences in the distribution of fat or age-related decline in muscle mass and BMI studies based on self-reported measurements and retrospective data from chart reviews have been found to be imprecise (Dutton and McLaren, 2014).

3.5.2 Accelerometry Measures.

Accelerometry devices were deployed in Chapters 5-7. Specifically, Chapters 5 and 6 deployed ActiGraph GT3X+ accelerometers, whereas Chapter 7 deployed both ActiGraph GT3X+ and ActivPAL4™ accelerometers.

3.5.2.1 *ActiGraph GT3X+*.

In Chapter 5 (Study 2) and 6 (Study 3), parent-child dyads were instructed to wear the ActiGraph GT3X+ (PAL Technologies Ltd., Glasgow, UK) device, weighing 9g and measuring 25x45x5mm, on their non-dominant wrist for seven consecutive days. Hand dominance was confirmed by the parent for both parent and child participants. Dyads were asked to wear the devices for 24 h with the aim of increasing adherence rates and subsequently, the number of participants meeting the WTC (Tudor-Locke et al., 2015).

3.5.2.2 *ActivPAL4™*.

The ActivPAL™ has previously been shown to be a valid measure of body posture and for quantifying SB and PA (Dowd, Harrington and Donnelly, 2012, An, Kim and Lee, 2017, Lyden et al., 2017) and was used in Chapter 7 (Study 4) of this thesis to measure SB

and sleep in children. The ActivPAL™ was placed in a small flexible nitrile sleeve to waterproof the device. Participants were instructed to wear the device for 24 h per day during a 7-day period. Children were instructed to wear shorts during the first session to allow researchers to fit the device to participants right thigh using Hypafix tape (Hypafix®). Children were provided with additional tape, a nitrile sleeve and instructions for their parents on how to re-apply the device to the thigh should it become loose, as well as information on the device itself (See Appendix 3I).

3.5.3 Socio-demographics.

Demographic variables were captured in each study included within this thesis (Chapters 4 – 7) including home postcodes, household income, occupation status, and highest education qualification as these are further indicators of SES which can be compared easily across the data set via informed consent document (Darin-Mattsson, Fors and Kåreholt, 2017). Home postcodes were inputted into the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) online calculator (Scottish Government, 2016b). The SIMD identifies areas of deprivation across all of Scotland in a consistent way, ranking areas into a relative decile score between 1 and 10 (1 being the most deprived areas and 10 being the least deprived areas). Scores for each area were calculated based on objective indicators across 6 domains: (1) residents' income, (2) employment, (3) housing, (4) health education, (5) skills and training, and (6) geographic access to services and telecommunications. SIMD scores for all locations in Scotland were publicly available at the time of the research and were used to select participants with low SES based on the location of the participant's home address.

3.5.4 Diet.

The DILQ was used to assess children's fruit and vegetable consumption in Chapter 7 (Edmunds & Ziebland, 2002). The DILQ was developed as a supervised classroom activity to assess the number of servings of fruit and vegetables consumed by children. Through the use

words and pictures, the DILQ encourages children to recall and describe a range of activities from the previous day (24 h recall method), which includes everything they had to eat and drink (See Appendix 3L). Write and draw questions regarding what the child ate are embedded within other items of the DILQ which take the child through a range of daily activities, in chronological segments (i.e., morning to evening). This method provides a context which helps the child to recall what they ate the day before (Edmunds and Ziebland, 2002). This questionnaire has been validated in 7-9 year old children performing either well or acceptably on all of the validity, reliability and sensitivity tests (Edmunds and Ziebland, 2002). The DILQ has also been used in older populations (e.g., 6-11 year olds) and was therefore deemed suitable for use in Chapter 7 (Ashfield-Watt, Stewart and Scheffer, 2009, Sharps and Robinson, 2015, 2016).

3.5.5 Family Involvement

The 46-item FIQ-E version (Manz, Fantuzzo and Power, 2004) is a multidimensional validated self-report scale measuring the frequency of family involvement (Semke et al., 2010) and was used in Chapters 4 and 7 (Studies 1 and 4). Within Chapter 4, the FIQ-E school-based involvement subscale was used to identify parents who were 'harder to reach' and less likely to be involved in school activities. Within Chapter 7 (Study 4), the FIQ-E Home-based learning subscale was used to determine the involvement of parents in the study for demographic purposes. The FIQ-E has demonstrated good factorial fit according to conventional criteria (Hu & Bentler, 1999) and excellent internal consistency ($\alpha = .91-84$). With this in mind, this questionnaire was deemed particularly appropriate for Chapter 4 (Study 1) and 7 (Study 4), as it was developed for parents from low-income backgrounds (Manz, Fantuzzo and Power, 2004).

3.5.6 ST

ST was measured via a self-reported questionnaire in Chapter 7 (Study 4) (See Appendix 3M). Children were asked to report how many h's they engaged in ST on weekdays (before school and after school) and weekend days (morning and evening) for mobile phone/tablet use, TV, and playing computer/video games which did not require them to be active (i.e., sat down). The scores from each device were then added together and multiplied by 5 to provide an overall weekday indication of ST duration, and multiplied by 2 to provide a weekend ST duration. Self-reported methods for quantifying ST have acceptable reliability and validity in children (Hardy et al., 2013).

3.5.7 Fidelity measures

Teacher participants involved in the intervention arm of Chapter 7 (Study 4) were asked to report class completion of a HWB homework intervention each day (Monday, Wednesday and Friday) for the 8-week period of HH delivery. Teachers were provided with a fidelity check sheet to complete in order to calculate children's completion of the homework activities

3.6 Qualitative inquiry

When evidence-based programmes are implemented in real world settings, their effectiveness is often disappointing (Schaap et al., 2018). MRC guidelines advocates the use of qualitative measures when developing and evaluating complex interventions (Craig et al., 2008, Senn et al., 2013). Qualitative inquiry allows for the exploration of the perceptions of participating within such programmes to provide insight into the interventions, which cannot be captured through objective measurements such as accelerometry or anthropometry. As the nature of this PhD is mixed-methods, a pragmatic philosophical approach was deemed appropriate as a research paradigm due to its flexibility, allowing for the amalgamation of both qualitative and quantitative inquiry (Feilzer, 2009). The integration of quantitative and

qualitative inquiry has been suggested to provide a comprehensive understanding of public health issues (Cresswell, 2015). The following sub-sections will provide information regarding the use of qualitative inquiry within this thesis.

3.6.1 Individual Interviews.

Individual interviews were conducted with parents in Chapter 4 (Study 1) to explore the perceptions of mothers with low SES regarding their involvement in school-based health activities using a semi-structured interview guide (See appendix 1E). These interviews were conducted over the telephone at a day and time which was suitable for the parent. Face-to-face interviews with teachers were conducted individually in Chapter 7 (Study 4) using a semi-structured interview guide with the aim of gaining insight into their perceptions of a HWB homework intervention and gaining key recommendations to improve the intervention (See appendix 3O).

3.6.2 Write, Draw, Show and Tell (WDST)

WDST group interviews were conducted with the children in Chapter 7 (Study 4) to gain information on their experiences and acceptability of a HWB intervention across schools. These WDST group interviews were informed by Noonan and colleagues conceptual framework and practical checklist (Noonan, Boddy, Fairclough, et al., 2016). This method was developed as an inclusive, interactive and child-centred methodology that could facilitate the exploration of topics within the WDST session. Semi-structured WDST group guides were used to ensure consistency across WDST groups, informed by SDT (See appendix 3P) (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

Thesis Study Map

Study	Objectives
<p>Study 1: An insight into mothers with low socioeconomic status' involvement in Scottish primary school health education activities</p>	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recruit less-involved mothers with low SES • Interview these mothers to establish barriers to their involvement in school-based health education and gain insight and recommendations on how to engage families with low SES • Based on the findings, propose strategies schools can use to increase parent involvement in future health-related activities
<p>Study 2: The effects of socioeconomic status on parent and child dyads moderate-to-vigorous physical activity and body mass index</p>	
<p>Study 3: Relationship between parent and child dyads physical activity using novel acceleration metrics</p>	
<p>Study 4: Exploring the feasibility of a cluster-randomised control trial to improve children's 24 h movement behaviours and dietary intake: HH</p>	

CHAPTER 4 STUDY 1

An Insight Into the Involvement of Mothers of Low Socioeconomic Status in
Scottish Primary School Health Education Activities

4.1 Introduction

Schools are one setting recommended by the WHO as an ideal site to implement activities that encourage children to improve their health and wellbeing (World Health Organization, 2018a). Currently the UK government are encouraging schools to address health issues (e.g., Public Health England, 2015) and there are a wide variety of activities which can occur: health-promoting teaching practices, classes on HWB topics, school projects or challenges, PA breaks during school time, health-related homework and after-school clubs. Researchers have evaluated numerous school-based health interventions focussing on the key determinants of health including mental wellbeing, nutrition, sexual health and PA (Ruiter et al., 2015, Sani et al., 2016, Lloyd et al., 2018). However, findings from recent systematic reviews and meta-analyses have demonstrated equivocal results (Evans et al., 2012, Love, Adams and Sluijs, 2018, Mackenzie and Williams, 2018). Indeed, school-based interventions can have positive effects on children's health in the short-term (Gonzalez-Suarez et al., 2009) however there is a lack of evidence regarding the sustainability of such effects (Evans et al., 2012, Verjans-Janssen et al., 2018). Further research is needed to identify health initiatives and activities which schools can implement to create long-term health benefits.

Involving children's proximal adults (e.g., parents) in school-based health activities could be a crucial way of improving the sustainability of positive outcomes, by encouraging positive health behaviours at school and at home. School-based health initiatives involving parents have shown promising effects on health outcomes (Niemeier, Hektner and Enger, 2012). As such, parents may be key contributors to the effectiveness of such interventions (Van Cauwenberghe et al., 2010, Verjans-Janssen et al., 2018). Indeed, research has shown that modifications to parents PA and dietary behaviours can influence such behaviours in their children (Yao and Rhodes, 2015, Blaine et al., 2017). Furthermore, systematic reviews

suggest that school-based health interventions involving parents are more effective than interventions without a parent component (Van Cauwenberghe et al., 2010). Thus, efforts to enhance parent involvement in such interventions are crucial and often proposed (Kipping, Jago, & Lawlor, 2012; Ruiters, Fransen, Molleman, Van der Velden, & Engels, 2015), but for whom these recommendations are for is unclear.

Many researchers struggle with the recruitment and retention of parents with low SES (Robinson, Adair, Coffey, Harris, & Burnside, 2016); a limitation which is common within school-based health interventions (Norman, Nyberg, Elinder, & Berlin, 2016). Moreover, parents with low SES tend to be less involved in their child's education than more affluent parents (Roksa & Potter, 2011) and experience multiple barriers to being involved (Hornby & Lafaele, 2011). As such they are also less likely to engage in additional activities such as school-based health initiatives. Whilst robust recommendations exist to engage parents of varying levels of SES (Reid, Eddy & Fetrow, 1999) these are provided in the context of children's academic achievement and behaviour. Whether these are appropriate for engaging within school-based health initiatives is ambiguous. Furthermore, it is unclear if proposed recommendations to enhance parental involvement in school-based health interventions (e.g., Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2012) would be relevant for those who are typically uninvolved, with low SES. As it is important to ensure that health interventions are accessible and inclusive to all children, more information regarding the experiences and involvement of these hard-to-reach families with low SES in school-based health programs is needed.

Mothers remain responsible for the bulk of family care regardless of their employment status (Craig, 2006; Sayer & Gornick, 2012). Mothers play an essential role in their child's development and are highly influential in their children's health outcomes. For example, maternal care behaviours play an important role in children's weight (Rodgers et

al., 2013) and mental wellbeing (Stafford et al., 2016). It is therefore important to understand the specific reasons that deter mothers with low SES from being involved in school-based health activities so that specific strategies and recommendations can be provided to encourage their future involvement. This study aimed to interview mothers with low SES, who are not typically involved in school-based health activities, to establish the active ingredients and barriers relating to their involvement, and gain insight into their perceptions of school health initiatives. Based on this information we propose strategies that schools can use to increase parent involvement in future school-based health activities.

4.2 Method

A qualitative approach was employed whereby questionnaires were completed by a range of parents. From the questionnaire results, mothers who had low SES and were less involved in school activities were identified and then invited to be interviewed.

4.2.1 Recruitment

Institutional ethical approval was granted and participants were recruited using a face to face recruitment method across five primary schools within a 12-mile radius of the University conducting the current research. Three schools were serving deprived communities and two were in more affluent areas. Each school had a parent council which represent parents' views and encourages parents to be actively involved in school life. Parents were recruited via awareness building strategies (e.g., flyers, pupil assembly visits which were attended by parents) (see Appendix 1A), followed by in-person recruitment at parent's evenings to increase the likelihood of recruiting less-involved parents. Parents evenings are in-school events where teachers and parents discuss their child's academic and behavioural performance. All parents are expected to attend and the events normally have very high parental attendance rates (Two Headteachers of recruited schools, personal communication, February 27th, 2019). During these events we set up a recruitment table and the 1st author and

4th authors directly approached all parents who walked past. Whilst at the stall, parents received information about the study and completed consent forms (see Appendices 1B and 1C), a FIQ-E (see Appendix 1D), provided demographic information and were asked for their availability/times to participate in a telephone interview.

4.2.2 Eligibility Criteria and Instrumentation

Eligibility criteria for the interviews included: (a) the mother of the child, (b) scored below the median response of parents in the sample (below 2) on the FIQ-E (Manz, Fantuzzo and Power, 2004) and (c) low levels of SES based on an index of deprivation linked to their home address which suggested they resided within 20% of the most deprived areas in the country (Scottish Government, 2016b).

The FIQ-E (Manz et al., 2004) is a validated self-report scale measuring parent involvement in school activities using three subscales: school-based involvement, home-based involvement, and home-school communication. For the purposes of the current study, the 13 items from the School-based involvement subscale were used to select mothers who had lower than median levels of school-based involvement. The FIQ-E was deemed relevant for this study as it has been tested with lower-income urban caregivers of children attending primary school (Manz et al., 2004) and has demonstrated good factorial fit according to conventional criteria (Hu and Bentler, 1999) and excellent internal consistency ($\alpha = .91-.84$).

SIMD identifies areas of deprivation across all of Scotland in a consistent way (Scottish Government, 2016b). SIMD ranks small areas from most deprived (ranked 1) to least deprived (ranked 6,976) which are then converted into a relative decile score between 1 and 10 (1 being the most deprived areas and 10 being the least deprived areas). Scores for each area are calculated based on objective criteria across 6 domains: residents' income, employment, housing, health education, skills and training, and geographic access to services and telecommunications (Scottish Government, 2016b). SIMD scores for all locations in

Scotland were publicly available at the time of the research and were used to select participants with low SES based on the location of the participant's home address scoring a decile score of 2 or below.

4.2.3 Participants

Parents ($n = 132$) completed an informed consent document, provided demographic information and completed the FIQ-E. Of the 132 parents who completed these forms (113 female, 19 male), 120 agreed to be interviewed. Of the 120 parents, 24 eligible mothers were identified (18.18%) and 16 mothers were interviewed across the 5 schools. All eligible mothers were contacted by telephone up to four times, five mothers were contacted but did not answer the telephone, and three rearranged the call for more convenient times but failed to answer subsequent calls. The mothers in our study ($35.88 \text{ Mage} \pm 7.67 \text{ years}$) included single parents ($n = 5$) and co-parents ($n = 7$); some mothers did not specify their family type ($n = 4$). Of these mothers, 11 were employed, four were unemployed, and one was a student. The highest educational qualification obtained by mothers were: lower secondary school qualification ($n = 2$), upper secondary school qualification ($n = 2$), college qualification ($n = 3$), a University qualification ($n = 1$), a degree qualification ($n = 1$) and some mothers did not report any qualifications ($n = 7$).

4.2.4 Interview Procedure

All interviews were conducted by a female researcher with four years of experience conducting qualitative inquiry including a Masters of Research (MRes) in qualitative research. The interviewer grew up in an area of deprivation (SIMD 2) near to the recruited schools however none of the participants had met the interviewer prior to study recruitment. Interviews were conducted via telephone using a semi-structured interview guide with questions centred on healthy lifestyle promotion at school and parent involvement within health activities at school (see Appendix 1E). All interviews were audio recorded and lasted

on average 43.34 mins. (± 12.20). Pilot interviews were conducted with a random selection of mothers recruited from the first school visit ($n = 6$ out of 11) and recordings were reviewed by both the interviewer and the director of studies upon which small amendments were made to the interview guide. Of these six pilot participants, only one met the inclusion criteria of being less-involved, with low SES. This mother was interviewed again to cover the alterations made to the interview guide and her pilot interview (22.25 mins) and additional interview (16.21 mins) was included in the analysis. No other pilot data was included in the final analysis. For anonymity purposes, all participants were assigned a participant number. The interviews were then transcribed verbatim by an independent transcription company.

4.2.5 Data Analysis

An inductive-deductive approach using hierarchal content analysis was taken to develop knowledge concerning our subject and the experience of the participants (Sparkes & Smith, 2014, p. 273). A social constructivist philosophy was adopted focusing on understanding how the mothers constructed their own reality of being involved in school activities (Patton, 2002, p. 97). The interviewer undertook the qualitative analysis by first reading the transcripts whilst listening to the interviews to become familiar with the data. Using NVivo 11, she then independently examined the transcripts and each comment or meaningful unit was identified and labelled inductively as nodes. Then similar nodes were grouped together according to both; the key research questions and emergent ideas. We sought to establish themes with internal homogeneity (where all nodes in one theme share meaningful characteristics) and external heterogeneity (the differences between nodes in different themes are clear) and grouped themes into higher order themes. Ensuring rigour and transparency in analysis is a vital component to assessing the quality of research (Gale et al., 2013). Thus, to ensure quality in the analysis, the supervisory team, who were not present during data collection, independently reviewed the data at several stages of the analysis and

multiple iterative discussions between the interviewer and supervisory team took place to ensure the representativeness of themes. An opportunity for member checking was provided by disseminating an overview of themes to all parents via email. One mother replied via email seeking to differentiate their views from those of other mothers. She was reassured that the themes represented all mothers' views, rather than solely her own views.

4.3 Results

Four overall themes emerged from the data: (a) barriers to being involved in health activities at school, (b) active ingredients to being involved in health activities at school, (c) School efforts, and (d) recommendations to the schools (see Figure 4-1).

4.3.1 Barriers to Being Involved in Health Activities at School

The barriers which deter mothers from being involved in school-based health activities were grouped into second-order themes: personal circumstances, child influence, issues with events, issues with the parent council and a disconnect between the school and parents (see Table 4-1).

The mothers discussed personal circumstances as barriers to their involvement including having additional commitments such as attending college, other child related-activities (e.g., sports clubs) and employment (e.g., shift work). Being a single-parent was a barrier to involvement for some mothers, particularly as it often wasn't possible to bring their other children to the school events (quote B.2 Parent 10).

Figure 4-1 Emergent themes

Table 4-1 Barriers to mothers' involvement in health education activities at school

Second-order theme	First-order theme	Example Quotes
Child influence	Child being older and not wanting to attend school with parent Child enjoys activities on their own Psychological issues with child including separation anxiety	<i>'My son's a bit older now. He wouldn't want to go to school with me.'</i> (B.1 Parent 1)
Personal circumstances and commitments	Additional responsibilities Already takes child to other activities College commitments Employment (shifts) Parent would rather spend time with family on days off Parents only day off Unable to commit Keeping the home and school separate Lack of time Parent confidence issues Parents not having friends at school Not wanting to be involved/not seeing it as important Single parent status affecting involvement	<i>'I have no one to look after my son, so I can't really go down... so it makes it hard for some of the parents...single-parents.'</i> (B.2 Parent 10)
Issues with events	Events not running for long enough The timing of events doesn't suit schedule Fears of allegations being made against parents PVG certificate required Issues with obtaining tickets for events Pressure on parents for not being involved Same people attending events	<i>'Parents you know, they'd be good as coaches to teach the kids how to play football...you hear of so many bad things about coaches in football... that's maybe why a lot of parents don't want to get involved because of allegations...'</i> (B.3 Parent 15)
Issues with the parent council	Clique Feelings of not fitting in Not feeling liked Not feeling supported Not hearing about meetings Not knowing what the parent council do Parent council members have communicated negatively Parent council members put people off being a part of it Timing of meetings Would rather speak to school directly – fear of how things can be relayed	<i>'I'd rather speak to the teacher or head teacher... you don't know how it's going to be put across.'</i> (B.4 Parent 16)
Disconnect between school and parents	Not being made aware of sport activities involving parents Not knowing who parents can talk to about health education Parents don't see teachers anymore to talk to School failing to follow up with interested parents	<i>'I was raring to go but this head teacher... moaned about not having resources to take kids out of classes. I said you know I've gave you my PVG, I could be up there helping and you've not even phoned me.'</i> (B.5 Parent 14)

Note. PVG = Protecting Vulnerable Groups

Also, a lack of time was cited as an issue and some mothers discussed that they would rather not spend the free time they did have being involved in school activities. Some participants also had a general disinterest in being involved in such activities and did not view their involvement as important. As well as personal circumstances, it was suggested that the child and their preferences could also deter involvement, particularly if the child was older, or experienced issues such as anxiety (quote B.1 Parent 1).

There were several barriers which deterred mothers from being involved in specific school events such as practical issues (e.g., obtaining tickets) and issues related to the safety and the social aspects of the events. Most notably, mothers consistently discussed the timing of events which acted as a barrier to their involvement in school-based health activities. For example, mothers were unable to attend events being held during school hours due to employment. Mothers also discussed the timing of events as being difficult particularly if weekly sessions take place on the same day and they have unpredictable and inflexible work schedules.

To ensure the safety of children in Scotland, a Protection for Vulnerable Groups (PVG) certificate is required for adults to work with children, which was reported as a barrier to volunteering at school as some mothers did not have a PVG certificate or know how to obtain one. Furthermore, some mothers indicated that due to recent revelations of abuse by those working with in sport, a fear of allegations could deter some parents from being involved as volunteers (quote B.3 Parent 15).

In reference to the social aspects of school-based health activities, some mothers lacked confidence to be involved and not having other parents as friends could deter some parents. Furthermore, mothers suggested that it was often the same parents attending events, who were most likely to be affiliated with the parent council. The parent council are a group of volunteer parents who meet regularly to work with the school to represent the views of

parents/carers and encourage links between the school and parents. The parent council groups are often pivotal to organising health-related activities in schools (e.g., sport days, fundraising events for playground equipment and sports clothes) were repeatedly described as “cliques” with mothers feeling neither liked nor supported by parent council. Furthermore, mothers not being made aware of parent council meetings, not knowing what the parent council do, and the timing of council meetings were highlighted as barriers to their involvement. Indeed, some mothers suggested that they would rather speak and feedback to teachers directly in fear of how information could be relayed by members of the parent council (quote B.4 Parent 16).

More generally, mothers also suggested a degree of disconnect between the school and parents, as they did not know who to talk to about health-related activities, they were not always made aware of activities taking place and, in some situations, teachers failed to follow up with parents who were interested in being involved (quote B.5 Parent 14). In general, some mothers did not feel they had a partnership with the staff, and it was difficult to access teachers and discuss health-related activities with them.

4.3.2 Personal Active Ingredients to Being Involved in Health Activities at School

The data related to personal aspects which encourage parents to be involved in health activities related to child and family influence (see Table 4-2). Both mother’s and child’s interest in activities would encourage these mother’s participation in health activities (quote A.I.1 Parent 11). Specifically, the opportunity to create life-long healthy habits, set a good example to their children, provide enjoyment for their child, and improve their relationship with their child via shared activities all encouraged parents to be involved (quote A.I.2 Parent 2). Extended family involvement (e.g., the possibility of grandparents attending events) was also highlighted as a method of facilitating more home-school connection and family involvement in school-based health activities (quote A.I.3 Parent 1).

Table 4-2 Personal active ingredients to mother's involvement in health education activities at school

Second-order theme	First-order theme	Example Quotes
Child influence	Being involved sets a good example to children Benefits to child health Child enjoyment at parent participating Child interest and encouragement for parent to be involved Creating positive health habits Parent involvement improving parent-child relationship	<i>'Just to set a good example to my own children. That it is good to get involved in things and it is good to keep yourself healthy and active. Just for them really.'</i> (A.I.1 Parent 11) <i>'[Parents and children] should be doing things together that would be a good idea to be able to do that. Also, for the relationships between the kids and the parents as well.'</i> (A.I.2 Parent 2)
Family influence	Extended family involvement Parent enjoyment required to participate Parent interest required to participate	<i>'My mum actually goes to sports days when I was out in college... or she would go to their parties that they had.'</i> (A.I.3 Parent 1)

4.3.3 School Efforts

The mother's recognised efforts made by the school regarding healthy lifestyles, parental involvement, and communication with home regarding health activities (see Table 4-3). Mothers identified numerous health activities run by the school to encourage healthy lifestyles including PA events (e.g., walk to school, sports day, afterschool clubs and the daily mile) and dietary-related activities (e.g., cooking classes, promotion of healthy snacks and garden club). Most of such activities were free for the children and overall the mothers held positive views of the schools' encouragement of healthy lifestyles. In some schools, the mothers thought rewards systems where children received class points for healthy behaviours encouraged positive behaviour (quote S.E.5 Parent 1). Whilst these activities were geared towards the children's health behaviours, many activities involved or depended on parents including, assisting their children to take healthy snacks to school and walking younger children to school.

Table 4-3 School efforts to encourage parental involvement in health education activities at school

Second-order theme	First-order theme	Example Quotes
School-Home communication of health activities	<p>Letters are sent to parents</p> <p>Children pass on information from school to home</p> <p>Homework diaries and notes from the teachers in jotters</p> <p>Facebook can be used</p> <p>Information regarding when children will have PE</p> <p>Newsletters to inform parents of upcoming health activities</p> <p>Only contacted by teachers if issue arises</p> <p>Prefer newsletters over E-Resources (e.g., website)</p> <p>Unsure if the school have a website</p> <p>Website can be used to access information regarding upcoming health activities</p>	<p><i>'We have got a Facebook page... I have notice parents voicing their opinion.'</i> (S.E.1 Parent 15)</p> <p><i>'I like having a letter because I like to put it on my fridge... sometimes you forget to check your Facebook if you don't have time but if it's there in front of you, you can kind of have a glance at it and see what's on today.'</i> (S.E.2 Parent 4)</p>
Healthy Lifestyle encouragement	<p>Afterschool sports clubs</p> <p>Children walking to school without parents as they are older</p> <p>Cooking class</p> <p>No cost for in-school activities</p> <p>Daily mile</p> <p>Food from around the world workshops</p> <p>Garden club</p> <p>Healthy menu</p> <p>Healthy snacks activities and activities</p> <p>Parent happy with activity encouragement at school</p> <p>Consideration of religion</p> <p>Rewards system for healthy behaviour</p> <p>Sports day</p> <p>Walking to school</p> <p>School efforts impacting on healthy habits at home</p>	<p><i>'The after-school club like health and fitness are always free, but it's just if it's maybe something that's run by somebody else out with the school, then they will charge.'</i> (S.E.3 Parent 12)</p> <p><i>'Because of our religious beliefs we have certain things we don't want [child's name] involved in, and they always check... like karate and things like that... they always phone to check... they're very good at phoning.'</i> (S.E.4 Parent 14)</p> <p><i>'So that does encourage them... my wee girl has done it before and she's like that "I need to take an apple or something" and she says "Mum, I want to get a point".'</i> (S.E.5 Parent 1)</p>
Efforts to encourage parent involvement	<p>Asks for volunteers</p> <p>Asks parents to attend extracurricular events</p> <p>Involve parents in Kerb Craft (event in which parents walk with children to teach them road safety)</p> <p>Parent council</p> <p>Involve parents in health eating activities</p> <p>Attending parents evening to discuss their child's development</p> <p>Involving parents in health curriculum</p> <p>School requests parent volunteers on "bank basis"</p> <p>Fundraising (bake sales, raffles and foodbanks)</p> <p>Sports day</p> <p>World of work week where parents attend school to discuss their jobs.</p>	<p><i>'I can remember some things like, how kid's bodies are changing... they did ask parents to come in and ok the curriculum part they were doing in school.'</i> (S.E.6 Parent 9)</p> <p><i>'...for parties they send out letters and ask you if you can get involved to let them know and they will use you for school trips or discos, I know they're looking for extra hands...'</i> (S.E.7 Parent 6)</p>
Recommendations to improve health activities at school	<p>Healthy buffet</p> <p>More promotion of healthy diets</p> <p>More extracurricular activities to promote PA</p>	<p><i>'If they're doing a healthy couple of days in the dinner hall where they will have I don't know, kinda like a buffet to encourage them to try different foods that are a lot healthier for you.'</i> (S.E.8 Parent 8)</p>

Note. PE = physical education.

Mothers also provided recommendations to improve the promotion of health activities at school including hosting a healthy buffet and the possibility of providing a variety of different foods to promote healthy eating in children (quote S.E.8 Parent 8). Furthermore, Mothers recommended increased extracurricular clubs and activities to promote PA time.

The participants discussed school efforts to encourage parents to be involved in health activities. Parents were invited to discuss the health curriculum and encouraged to take part in healthy eating activities with their child. Some schools asked for volunteers on a “bank basis” where they would request the participation of interested parents when required. These extracurricular events included parent council events, parents’ night, and sports day. The schools’ consideration of religion towards diet and sporting activities was positively recognised (quote S.E.4 Parent 14), as those with specific religious beliefs reported that they were often contacted to check that diet and sport-related activities were appropriate for their children.

The mothers discussed ways in which the schools communicated with regards to school-based health activities (e.g., letters and newsletters, school websites, the school’s Facebook page, via notes in the child’s homework diary, information days; quote S.E.1 Parent 15). The mothers preferred printed-out information (e.g., newsletters) over e-resources (e.g., websites), as they were less likely to forget about upcoming events if they were on display (e.g., on the fridge). Some mothers did not know whether their child’s school had a website (quote S.E.2 Parent 4) and suggested they mostly received information via their child rather than the schools.

4.3.4 Recommendations to Improve Parent Involvement in School-based Health Activities

A host of recommendations were provided including: increasing communication, new methods of encouraging parent involvement, improving current parent recruitment strategies, and improving the promotion of health activities at school (see Table 4-4).

Table 4-4 Recommendations to improve parent involvement in school-based health activities

Second-order theme	First-order theme	Example Quotes
Increasing communication	Hold discussion groups	<i>'It would be nice if like the parent's council could just have something to get everybody involved... not just for the parent council but for anybody to come. There's not really a thing that people can like go to, to voice an opinion. So, it would be probably easier... if they have like maybe a meeting that anybody could come to.'</i> (R.1 Parent 4)
	More information on parent involvement needs in school	
	Provide parent with more information on the clubs available at school	
	Ask parents to come in during PE time to promote clubs	
	Parent council meetings open to all parents	
New methods of encouraging parent involvement	Coffee morning to allow parents to connect	<i>'...if the parents and the school work together and came up with a program together... then I think it would be more successful.'</i> (R.2 Parent 11)
	Text messages could be sent to encourage parents	
	Involving parents and school staff could change relationships	
	Informal open afternoon for parents to show support for the school	
	Open days or activities to be involved in	
	Parent-child joint activities	<i>'You need to have someone that's quite positive about it and really up for it to show other people, do you know what you can actually learn and experience. Then it can be like I never actually knew this, are you aware of this, this is something we can actually take forward.'</i> (R.3 Parent 16)
	Parent and teachers could design and parent involvement program together	
	Pay the parent	
	Family school trips	
	Fundraising to bring parents together	
	Involve parents in health activities at home	
Should have a parent champion to encourage parent involvement	<i>'But yeah have more things on at the evening and more thing on in the weekend.'</i> (R.4 Parent 12)	
Parent input could make events more successful		
Improving upon current parent recruitment strategies	Provide parents with information on meetings beforehand	<i>'But yeah have more things on at the evening and more thing on in the weekend.'</i> (R.4 Parent 12)
	Providing feedback options for parents (e.g., suggestion box and questionnaires)	
	Provide sufficient and effective notice	
	Have various times of events to accommodate all parents	
	Schools should ask parents if they want to be involved	
	School should take over organizing events (commonly the parent council do this)	
	Teachers could do more to encourage parents	
	Parents should remain in communication with each other	
	Parents should be able to support the school in their decisions without having to be involved	

Note. PE = physical education.

The need for more effective communication was consistently emphasised. Most notably, mothers considered an increase of information both in relation to parent involvement and health activities at school, to be of the utmost importance. Mothers recommended increasing inclusivity of parent council meetings as a way of increasing information (quote R.1 Parent 4).

Encouraging parent involvement was also recommended by the participants, and recommendations were offered including: hosting coffee mornings, text message systems, parent-child joint activities, school trips and home-based activities. Mothers also suggested that parents and teachers could work together to design a parent involvement programme (quote R.2 Parent 11). Ways in which parents themselves could encourage parent involvement in school-based health activities were highlighted including involving a parent champion (quote R.3 Parent 16) and encouraging more communication between parents. In terms of improving upon current parent recruitment strategies, mothers recommended providing parents with more information of meetings beforehand, as well as providing sufficient notice of these meetings and school events. Moreover, participants suggested providing parents with various event times to accommodate all parents would increase recruitment (quote R.4 Parent 12).

4.4 Discussion

These findings revealed that mothers face multiple barriers to their involvement in school-based health activities including: single parent status, unpredictable working patterns, lack of confidence to feedback to the school and not feeling liked or supported by parents within the parent council. Previous research suggests that conflicting commitments and a lack of time are barriers for all parents' involvement in school activities (Murray et al., 2014), however the unpredictability of these mothers schedules alongside their fears and lack of confidence seem to be related to their specific experiences. Therefore, it could be suggested

that the barriers these mothers face are exacerbated by the effects of their low SES. Some mothers did not want to be involved and viewed the school and home as separate environments, whereas others wanted to be involved but felt that the school did not encourage their involvement. Whilst mothers with low SES face some similar barriers to parents who are more affluent (Murray et al., 2014), the current results suggest that some mothers with low SES have lower motivation and experience more numerous barriers to being involved in school-based health activities.

The current findings accord with previous work regarding a lack of confidence amongst mothers with low SES, which can be overlooked by schools (Lavee and Benjamin, 2015). Self-efficacy levels of mothers with low SES have previously been highlighted as a barrier to involvement, as parents of limited educational backgrounds frequently lack the confidence to interact with teachers (Kim, 2009). They may also be vilified or blamed for not conforming to standards set by more affluent parents (Gillies, 2006). Demand for parent involvement has often been left unscrutinised in relation to the advantage provided to parents of specific social groups and the demands it imposes on socially vulnerable parents (Theodorou, 2007). Thus, schools should review whether their standard way of working with parents favours more affluent parents and whether changes can be made to increase the inclusivity of parent-related activities.

SDT (Ryan and Deci, 2000b) could offer a theoretical explanation regarding the low levels of parental involvement in mothers within our study, as these participants did not feel competent in the school environment, lacked relationships with other parents and staff, and did not know how to autonomously feedback to the school. For example, Parent 13 within our study expressed how lack of friendships within the school meant she did not get involved in school activities. “Well there's not many friends I have in that school... like, mums. I just pick up the kids and bring them back.” SDT would suggest that such negative experiences

may have impacted on their need satisfaction and their subsequent motivation to be involved (Ryan and Deci, 2000a). Indeed, a study which examined parents' motivation to be involved in schools suggested that higher autonomous motivation in mothers' was associated with higher levels of involvement (Grolnick, 2015). Therefore, SDT could provide a theoretical framework which supports the needs of hard-to-reach parents' in future school-based health interventions.

Social Identity Theory (SIT) (Tajfel and Turner, 1979) may also explain the influence of social groups on these mothers. SIT suggests that a person's self-concept derives from the groups to which the individual belongs. An individual will compare their own ingroup against other outgroups, tending to view members of competing groups negatively to increase their own self-esteem. If the parent council has a strong group identity as an exclusive 'clique' they would be likely to view less involved parents negatively and may discriminate against them. Parent 4 raised this issue, "It always seems to be the same people that are attending. It's always the people that's close to the school, so then you don't want to attend... There are a lot of people that are really cliquy... they're in the Parents' Council and they get everything first." Parent 2 felt similarly regarding this issue, "I don't think they like me... The Parent Council has needed new members and I did consider it but I didn't go... I know half of the mums wouldn't vote me in." This could explain why some mothers felt excluded and disliked by the parent council, which acted as a barrier to their involvement in school-based health activities. Nonetheless, alongside barriers to involvement we identified positive influences which encouraged the mothers to be involved in health activities.

Personal active ingredients were discussed including the aid of extended family as a way of remaining involved in school activities, which has previously been highlighted as a facilitator of involvement in previous research (Bol and Kalmijn, 2016). The influence of their child was also noted as an active ingredient to involvement via perceiving potential

benefits to their child's health and opportunities to improve parent-child relationships. The benefits of parent involvement for children have been recognised in previous research (Hesketh, Waters, Green, Salmon, & Williams, 2005), however the current data suggest that some mothers with low SES seem particularly unaware of the positive influence they could have by being involved in school activities with their child. Therefore, when schools are running family-based health activities, it would be prudent to emphasize the relevant benefits parent participation could have for pupils. Indeed, providing parents with good reasons as to why they should participate or attend parental opportunities has been found to be a successful strategy for building bridges between low-income parents and schools (Jennings, 1992).

The school's efforts regarding health activities was appreciated by the participants, however some aspects of communication could have been improved, as some mothers were unaware the school had a website and some felt the messages were mainly delivered via their child. Indeed, school websites are frequently cited as a useful means of parent-school communication (Piper, 2012). Mothers also felt the school could improve upon their communication regarding parent involvement, as some mothers felt that the school failed to follow up when they expressed interest in being involved.

As a result of this research, there are a series of suggestions which could be used by schools, policy-makers and researchers seeking the involvement of mothers with low SES in school-based health activities. Parents suggested joint parent-child activities, school trips and home-based activities would be positive ways to increase their involvement in health activities. Our findings also highlight that using a variety of methods to communicate with parents regarding health activities could encourage less engaged parents to get involved (e.g., discussion groups, newsletters, homework diaries, social media, text messages). Schools should also consider the timing of events, the notice they provide to parents, and encourage other family members' participation to improve the home-school connection for families and

parents with complex and conflicting demands. Mothers in the current study also recommended parents and teachers planning health activities together, having a parent champion for health activities, and parents inputting in the promotion sports clubs. Indeed, the aforementioned recommendations echo previous research relating to parental involvement in health projects more broadly (Clarke et al., 2015; Raftery, Grolnick, & Flamm, 2012; Patino-Fernandez, Hernandez, Villa, & Delamater, 2013) and align with best practice recommendations to involve end-users in the design of school-based health initiatives (Craig et al., 2008; Patino-Fernandez et al., 2013). There are however, some recommendations which reflect findings that seem to be more specific to parents with low SES who are already less involved. In particular, the data suggest schools could focus more on nurturing these parents' belief that their involvement in school-based health activities could make a worthwhile contribution to their own and their child's wellbeing. Furthermore, the parent councils who are frequently responsible for organising events at the schools were discussed as a barrier to parent involvement. Mothers described feeling excluded from the parent council and as such, schools should make efforts to the promote inclusivity and representation of families with SES within parent councils. Furthermore, it would prudent to ensure that such committees do not become an overly powerful group of parents who run events without considering input from teachers and a diverse range of parents. Such methods are likely to increase parents feelings of autonomy, competence and relatedness, thus increasing their motivation to be involved (Grolnick, 2015). However, whilst parents suggested valuable methods to increase parent involvement, the cost implications of such activities would need to be considered to ensure parents with low SES would not be excluded.

There are several strengths within the current study. Due to our face to face recruitment methods, we interviewed 16 mothers with low SES, who were not usually

involved in school-based activities. As such these mothers who were unlikely to participate in research or school-based activities, were recruited and their views were captured. However, this research is subject to limitations. Interviews were conducted in one region of the UK, therefore the themes identified may not be reflective of mothers' views in other locations and father's views are not represented. Indeed, the majority of research on parent involvement in school-based health activities focuses on mothers as the parent most likely to be the primary caregiver (Hill and Taylor, 2004). Future research could explore the involvement of parents in school-based health activities on a family level, taking into consideration the perspectives of fathers, siblings and extended family.

4.4.1 Conclusion

Despite decades of research, there is still a lack of interventions which effectively impact on children's health behaviours (e.g., Love et al., 2018) and a clear method of improving the impact of school-based health activities, is the inclusion of caregivers and a home-based focus within the interventions (Bleich et al., 2018). Furthermore, school-based health interventions are often attended by the most affluent and motivated parents (Clarke et al., 2015, Ruiter et al., 2015). Such interventions should address the inequities with the aim of including parents with low SES who are typically uninvolved. As such these results offer valuable insight to schools, practitioners and researchers to encourage uninvolved parents to participate in school-based health activities.

Thesis Study Map

Study	Objectives and Key Findings
<p>Study 1: An insight into mothers with low socioeconomic status' involvement in Scottish primary school health education activities</p>	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recruit less-involved mothers with low SES • Interview these mothers to establish barriers to their involvement in school-based health education and gain insight and recommendations on how to engage families with low SES • Based on the findings, propose strategies schools can use to increase parent involvement in future health-related activities <p>Key Findings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mothers with low SES state similar barriers to being involved when compared to previous research; however, with added barriers including lack of confidence, feelings of being disliked by the parent council and unpredictable working schedules. • Emphasis was placed on increased communication with school staff and variation in the timing of events • Mothers recommended school staff should organise events more instead of the parent council
<p>Study 2: The effects of socioeconomic status on parent and child dyads moderate-to-vigorous physical activity and body mass index</p>	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine the relationship between parent and child MVPA and BMI in a sample of children (4-11 years old) using wrist-worn accelerometers. • Explore mediating processes by which SES influences child MVPA and BMI z-score through their parents MVPA and BMI.
<p>Study 3: Relationship between parent and child dyads physical activity using novel acceleration metrics</p>	
<p>Study 4: Exploring the feasibility of a cluster-randomised control trial to improve children's 24 h movement behaviours and dietary intake: HH</p>	

CHAPTER 5 STUDY 2

The effects of socioeconomic status on parent and child dyads moderate-to-vigorous physical activity and body mass index

5.1 Introduction

Global obesity rates have tripled over the past four decades with 41 million children under the age of 5 and over 340 million between the age of 5-19 years being classed as overweight or obese in 2016 (World Health Organization, 2018b). Although the causes of obesity are multifactorial, the link between obesity and physical inactivity is well established (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2016, World Health Organization, 2018b). Many countries allocate considerable resources to the treatment of obesity-related disorders that can account for between 0.7% and 2.8% of a countries total healthcare expenditure (Withrow and Alter, 2011). As physical inactivity and weight status are modifiable, it is crucial to identify factors that are associated with PA behaviour and BMI in order to improve upon the factors which have positive effects.

Current national and international recommendations encourage youth to undertake at least 60 mins of daily MVPA as a preventative measure of obesity (Australian Government, 2018; Canadian Society for Exercise Physiology, 2018; Department of Health and Social Care, 2019; U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2018). Available data from both self-reported and objective assessments of PA indicate that children are failing to meet these recommendations (Hallal et al., 2012, Sallis et al., 2016). An important determinant of HWB is SES as it can influence an individual's exposure to several risk factors across the lifespan (Marmot, 2005). Children who grow up in areas with low SES have a higher risk of CVD, unhealthy behaviours (Laaksonen et al., 2008), all cause-mortality (Bukman et al., 2014) and higher obesity prevalence rates (NHS Digital, 2006) when compared to those who grow up in areas with higher SES.

Little is known about the mechanisms by which SES impacts on children's PA and BMI. It is clear that parental influence plays a major role in determining the weight of their children, with evidence from several upper-middle and high income countries (e.g., Australia,

Mexico, Norway, Germany, and the US) suggesting that parental overweight status is a risk factor for childhood overweight (Gibson et al., 2007, Hernández-Valero et al., 2007, Elder et al., 2010), existing as early as preschool age (Kitsantas and Gaffney, 2010). Additionally, parents have been described as gate-keepers for PA-related opportunities with their support to be active and their own PA being shown to affect the activity behaviours of their children (Brouwer et al., 2018). Nonetheless, studies have reported no significant relationship in parent and child PA (Jago et al., 2010, Erkelenz et al., 2014).

Multiple theories suggest that an individual's health and behaviour is influenced via multidimensional environmental conditions and not solely by one factor (e.g., parents). For example, the socio-ecological model proposes that an individual (e.g., a child) can be influenced by various systems including the microsystem (e.g., family), exosystem (e.g., school) and macrosystem (e.g., culture and social conditions such as SES) (Bronfenbrenner, 1986). Therefore, it is important to understand how parents BMI and PA may affect children's BMI and PA. Furthermore, SES can affect the BMI and PA of adults due to: the financial resources available for food and exercise-related expenditure, the education levels and understanding of diet and exercise related issues and the location of an individual's residence (e.g., proximity to fast food outlets, safe spaces to exercise) (Lee, Cardel and Donahoo, 2019). Moreover, parents are known to play a significant role in influencing children's health behaviours via role modelling eating habits, weight status and PA levels (Xu, Wen and Rissel, 2015, Scaglioni et al., 2018). Therefore, it is likely that SES impacts on children's health via their parents' health behaviours.

Previous research has tended to use subjective measures of PA (Trost and Loprinzi, 2011), pedometers (Stearns et al., 2016), and differ according to the indicators of PA used (e.g., MVPA, total PA) (Craig, Cameron, & Tudor-Locke, 2013). The use of such methods increases the ambiguity of findings as subjective measures of PA are prone to recall bias

(Chinapaw et al., 2010) whereas pedometers have been found to be inaccurate in assessing the distance covered and energy expended (Ndahimana and Kim, 2017). Considerable differences in weekday and weekend parent and child PA have been found (McMinn et al., 2013). Failing to examine the relationship between parent and child PA using separate analyses for weekday and weekend data is apparent in research which may therefore fail to capture the extent of this relationship (Stearns et al., 2016). Accelerometry is the gold standard for measuring free-living PA in adults and children (Esliger et al., 2011). Nevertheless, in the limited studies which employ accelerometer devices to measure PA, ambiguous WTC, or failure to report WTC at all, is evident (Strutz et al., 2018).

Previous accelerometer research findings are commonly based on data derived from hip-mounted devices (Fuemmeler, Anderson and Mâsse, 2011). In contrast to wrist-mounted devices, such placement can result in poor compliance (McLellan, Arthur and Buchan, 2018). Indeed, research has found greater wear time compliance with wrist-placement devices in comparison to hip-worn devices, regardless of WTC (Fairclough et al., 2016, McLellan, Arthur and Buchan, 2018). Given this increased compliance rate evident from wrist-worn accelerometers, a number of researchers have advocated placing accelerometers at the wrist to evaluate PA given the potential of capturing more data which may be more representative of habitual activity levels (Troiano et al., 2014). Due to the growing popularity and suitability of the wrist as an accelerometer placement site (Fairclough et al., 2016), it is important to establish the relationship between SES and parent and child MVPA from wrist-worn accelerometry data. Tests of the difference and direct correlations between SES and parent and child MVPA and BMI are not enough to fully understand these relationships. Statistical mediation analysis describes how SES as an independent variable “X” affects the dependent variable “Y” (Child MVPA and BMI z-score) through an indirect effect of the mediating variable “M” (Parent MVPA and BMI). Therefore, the purpose of this study was twofold.

Firstly, to examine the relationship between parent and child MVPA and BMI in a sample of children (4-11 years old) using wrist-worn accelerometers. Secondly, to explore mediating processes by which SES influences child MVPA and BMI z-score through their parents MVPA and BMI. Our hypotheses were that SES would be related to children's MVPA and BMI z-scores indirectly via parental MVPA and BMI.

5.2 Methods

5.2.1 Participants

Recruitment involved the first author visiting the parent's evenings (where parents meet with their child's teacher at school to discuss their child's progress) of six primary school's known by the 1st author after institutional ethical approval was granted. Children (4-11 years old) who attended the schools approached for this study ($n = 6$), and one of their parents from Lanarkshire and Glasgow, Scotland, were recruited. Each family chose which parent participated in the study during the recruitment phase. Parental attendance at these events is normally high and parents are directly contacted by teachers if they do not attend. As such we hoped to recruit a diverse range of parents from such events, including those who may be less likely to volunteer to participate in school-based research activities. Information sheets (see Appendix 2A) and consent paperwork (see Appendix 2B) was then handed out to parents at parent's evenings by the first author to complete on behalf of themselves and their child. The SIMD decile scores of the schools ($n = 6$) ranged from 2-7 (4.17 ± 2.32) with a score of 1 indicating high levels of deprivation and a score of 10 indicating low levels of deprivation (Scottish Government, 2016b). Data collection took place between October 2018 and May 2019.

5.2.2 Anthropometric measures

Objective measures of mass and stature of children and parents were undertaken at school. Mass was measured barefoot to the nearest 0.1kg with an electronic scale (Seca

Digital Scales, Seca Ltd, Birmingham, UK) whilst stature was measured barefoot to the nearest 0.1cm using a stadiometer in accordance with standard procedures (Cole, Freeman and Preece, 1995). BMI was then calculated as the mass in kilograms divided by the square of the stature in meters. Thereafter, BMI z-scores for each child were determined and children were classified as either healthy weight or obese/overweight relative to the UK 1990 BMI population reference data (Cole, Freeman and Preece, 1995). Using software provided by the Child Growth Foundation (Pan and Cole, 2010), the following definitions were applied for healthy weight (BMI z-score <1.04 , below the 85th percentile) and overweight/obese (BMI z-score ≥ 1.04 , above the 85th percentile) children. Parent BMI was classified relative to the WHO classifications with BMI scores <18.5 defined as underweight, 18.5 to <25 defined as normal weight, 25 to <30 defined as overweight, excluding obese, 30 to <40 defined as obese excluding morbidly obese, and ≥ 40 defined as morbidly obese (World Health Organization, 2018a).

5.2.3 SES Variables

Several variables were collected via the parent consent form (see Appendix 2B) to quantify the SES of parents. Home postcodes were collected in order to calculate residential deprivation scores. Information regarding household income, parental occupation and the parent's highest education qualification achieved was also collected.

5.2.3.1 Residential deprivation (Area-SES)

The home postcodes were reported in order to calculate the area-SES of parent and child dyads based on residential SIMD decile scores (Scottish Government, 2016b). SIMD is a measure of area-based multiple deprivations, which is centred on 31 indicators across six individual domains including: current income, employment, housing, health, education, and skills and training. In order to examine the differences in MVPA and BMI based on SIMD,

the median SIMD observed was 5 and from this, area SIMD was categorized as low and high based on the median split. SIMD will be referred to as area-SES hereon in.

5.2.3.2 Household income

Parents were asked to report their annual household income. The median gross salary in Scotland for all employees was £23,833 in April 2018 (Aiton, 2018) which we used to categorize high and low household income.

5.2.3.3 Occupation

Parents were asked to detail their current occupation status. From this, parent occupation was then classified into three separate categories including: unemployed/stay at home parent, student/retired, and employed/self-employed.

5.2.3.4 Parent education

Parents were asked to detail their highest education qualification to date. Based on the information provided, four separate categories for parent education were created including: secondary school qualification or less, UK college qualification (e.g., Higher National Certificate), UK University qualification (e.g., Bachelor's degree), and UK University Postgraduate qualification.

5.2.4 PA

Parent and child dyads were provided with two ActiGraph GT3X+ (ActiGraph, LLC, Pensacola, FL, USA) accelerometers and instructed to wear the device at all times (i.e., 24 h per day), except during any water-based activities, for a minimum of 7 days on the non-dominant wrist (confirmed by the parent/child). Verbal and written instructions for care and placement of the devices were provided to parents. Finally, all devices were synchronized with Greenwich Mean Time and initialized to capture data at 80Hz prior to distribution.

5.2.4.1 Accelerometry data processing

Accelerometer data were downloaded using ActiLife v6.13.3 (ActiGraph, Pensacola, FL, USA) and saved in raw format as gt3x files. The gt3x files were subsequently converted to time-stamp free .csv files which were exported into R (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria, <https://cran.r-project.org/>) and processed using the GGIR package v1.9.1. GGIR removed abnormally high values, detected non-wear time (van Hees et al., 2013a) and auto-calibrated the raw accelerometer signals using local gravity as a reference (van Hees et al., 2014). Finally, GGIR calculated ENMO over 5 sec epochs expressed in milli-gravitational units (mg). Participant files were removed from further analysis if files had a post-calibration error ≥ 0.01 g and there were less than 4 days (including 1 weekend day) of valid wear (defined as ≥ 10 h per day) across the day from 6am-10pm. Time spent inactive was defined as time accumulated below 50 mg, including sleep, for both children and adults (Rowlands, Plekhanova, et al., 2019) whereas time spent in MVPA for both children and adults was defined as the time accumulated above an acceleration of 201 mg for children and 101 mg for adults (Hildebrand, van Hees, Hansen, & Ekelund, 2014). Time spent in LPA was defined as time spent above 50 mg and below the relevant MVPA threshold.

5.2.5 Statistical Analyses

All analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics v.23 (IBM, Armonk, NY). Independent samples *t* tests and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) were employed to assess the difference in means of MVPA and BMI based on varying factors including gender, area-SES and parent occupation. For child MVPA age and gender were used as covariates. For child BMI z-score, gender was controlled for as a covariate. To determine the strength of the relationships between parents and their children regarding accelerometry data as well as BMI, separate pearson correlation coefficients were

conducted for variables including: parent and child MVPA on all days (i.e., the entire week), weekdays and weekend days, parent BMI, child BMI z-score, area-SES, household income, parent occupation and parent's highest education qualification achieved. As area-SES had the greatest response rate of the SES variables collected and is based on multiple indicators including income, occupation and education, we chose to run area-SES in our mediation analyses to represent SES.

To test the indirect effects of area-SES on children's MVPA and BMI z-score via their parents MVPA and BMI, we used a regression-based package known as PROCESS (Hayes, 2012) to run mediation analyses with 10,000 bootstrap samples. Separate models were ran to examine the influence of area-SES on children's MVPA via their parents MVPA, and the influence of area-SES on children's BMI z-score via their parents BMI. PROCESS provides the total indirect effect and the separate direct effects through each mediator whilst controlling for effects of all other mediators via bootstrapping. Such analysis is used when a researcher seeks to test hypotheses regarding how a direct effect of X on Y operates via an indirect mediating variable M. Such analyses suggest that X affects Y because X affects the mediator variable M. As such, this causal effect transmits X's effect to Y through the effect of M on Y in sequence of the form $X \rightarrow M \rightarrow Y$ (Hayes and Rockwood, 2017). The beta coefficients indicate the gradient of the regression line as the strength of the relationship, and the lower and upper bound 95% confidence intervals (CI) that do not encompass zero indicate significant relationships at the .05 level. Bootstrapped CI were used to determine the significance of the indirect effect. Within PROCESS analyses, the size of the unstandardized Beta Coefficients and CI levels provide an indication of the strength of the relationship between variables. Hayes (2013) concludes that, whilst multiple measures of effect sizes are easily obtained using PROCESS, they should be interpreted with extreme caution and only create a reasonable reflection of the effects found when using very large samples ($n = >2000$).

As such, it was decided to omit effect sizes for this study. The assumptions for t-tests include normality of the dependent variable and homogeneity of variance (i.e., measured using Levene's tests of equality of variance). These assumptions were met. The assumptions associated with the ANOVA's and ANCOVA's include: the dependent variable is continuous, the independent variables include two or more groups, independence of groups and the dependent variable is normally distributed. Whilst there were some violations of normality, due to the nature of the data, it was important not to manipulate the data and thus, keep the data as collected to reflect the pairing of parent-child dyad data. Additionally, ANOVA's and ANCOVA's are robust to violations of normality (Blanca, Alarcón, Arnau, Bono and Bendayan, 2017). Regression analyses assumptions are associated with our use of PROCESS mediation analyses which include: linearity of the independent and dependent variables, normal distribution of the residuals, homoscedasticity of the residuals, uncorrelatedness of the residuals, absence of multicollinearity and appropriate scale properties. Assumptions were met, excluding normal distribution, however PROCESS estimates robust standard errors via bootstrapping which are robust to violations of normality.

5.3 Results

Children ($n = 201$; $n = 103$ boys) aged 8.41 ± 1.98 years and one of their parents ($n = 151$ female) aged 38.48 ± 6.91 years consented to participate in the study. A participant flow chart is provided in Figure 5-1. When employing a wear time inclusion criterion in which participants must have worn the device for ≥ 16 h per day (from 0-24 hr.) for 4 days (including 1 weekend day), 79 children and parents were excluded as they did not meet these criteria. As this reduced our sample considerably, we chose to include parent and child dyads who wore the device for 4 days (including 1 weekend day), for ≥ 10 h each day from 6am – 10pm.

Figure 5-1 CONSORT flow diagram of the recruitment, adherence and analysis process.

Subsequently, 47 children and parents failed to meet the WTC and therefore, due to inclusion of parent and child dyads only, a further 14 adults and children were excluded as their dyad counterpart failed to meet the WTC. A final sample of 113 children ($n = 58$ girls; 8.83 ± 1.78 years) and their parent ($n = 86$ female; 40.17 ± 6.61 years), were included in the MVPA analyses (56.22%). Findings revealed that the average wear time for children and parents were 19.64 ± 4.92 h and 19.98 ± 4.59 h respectively. Children wore the device on average 5.58 ± 0.91 days during the week and 1.92 ± 0.27 days on the weekend. Parents wore the device for 5.30 ± 1.04 days during the week and 1.89 ± 0.32 days on the weekend. No files were removed due to post-calibration error. LPA and sedentary time were also calculated for parents ($n = 52$) and children ($n = 77$). Children accumulated 695.28 ± 58.52 mins of inactive time and 140.911 ± 28.89 mins of LPA on average per day over the monitoring period. Parents accumulated 728.69 ± 68.93 mins of inactive time and 142.18 ± 40.55 mins of LPA on average per day during the monitoring period.

We found significant differences in age between parents who met the WTC and those who did not ($p < .01$), with parents who met the WTC being older (40.17 ± 6.61 years vs. 36.33 ± 6.28 years). Children who met the WTC (8.83 ± 1.87 years) were also significantly ($p < .01$) older compared to those who did not (7.89 ± 2.16 years). In relation to gender homogeneity in our sample of parent and child dyads who met the WTC, 46.9% were the same gender ($n = 53$). Descriptive statistics are presented in Table 5-1 for MVPA.

A significant difference in children's all day MVPA was observed between boys and girls, with boys participating in more MVPA than girls on all days ($p < .05$). Boys were also more active than girls for weekday MVPA ($p < .01$). No other significant differences in children or parents MVPA were observed for gender or SES variables.

Table 5-1 Sample characteristics of child and parent participants regarding MVPA mean differences on all days (AD), weekdays (WD) and weekend (WK) days.

	MVPA min							
	Child				Parent			
	N (%)	AD (SD)	WD (SD)	WK (SD)	N (%)	AD (SD)	WD (SD)	WK (SD)
Total Participants (N) = 113 dyads								
Characteristics								
Gender	113				113			
Male	55 (48.70)	63.15 (25.66)	64.50 (26.27)	60.64 (32.32)	27 (24.00)	98.65 (51.17)	101.85 (54.57)	86.81 (47.80)
Female	58 (51.30)	53.40 (20.99)	52.40 (20.61)	56.11 (30.80)	86 (76.00)	94.46 (37.87)	96.06 (39.69)	90.20 (44.27)
CI LL - UL (95%)		1.48 – 18.97*	3.49 -21.17**	-5.95 – 17.32		-17.44 - 25.82	-17.23 - 28.81	-24.32 - 17.54
SIMD (area-SES)	101				101			
< Decile 5	49 (48.50)	60.01 (26.72)	59.59 (26.00)	61.31 (36.55)	49 (48.50)	98.65 (41.34)	100.27 (43.70)	92.99 (45.65)
≥ Decile 5	52 (51.50)	56.06 (21.84)	56.24 (23.52)	56.52 (27.57)	52 (51.50)	94.77 (42.87)	96.14 (44.83)	90.53 (46.84)
CI LL - UL (95%)		-5.57 – 13.37	-6.30 – 12.83	-7.77 – 17.48		-12.77-20.52	-13.37-21.62	-15.82- 20.74
Household income	52				52			
< £23, 833	8 (15.40)	62.75 (20.07)	61.17 (18.23)	66.58 (31.62)	8 (15.40)	112.30 (64.77)	118.40 (68.02)	92.47 (54.92)
≥ £23, 833	44 (84.60)	59.27 (25.87)	59.39 (26.78)	58.66 (30.06)	44 (84.60)	91.67 (35.39)	91.24 (36.95)	92.32 (41.95)
CI LL - UL (95%)		-18.74 – 21.16	-21.56 – 18.86	-16.55 – 32.13		-33.87-75.12	-30.06- 84.38	-46.42 – 46.72
Parent occupation	105				105			
Unemployed/ Stay at home parent	9 (8.60)	54.15 (21.46)	53.19 (25.09)	56.74 (26.97)	9 (8.60)	88.43 (52.49)	92.93 (53.25)	73.68 (44.34)
Student/ Retired	5 (4.80)	67.50 (13.56)	73.53 (13.58)	51.58 (19.45)	5 (4.80)	102.08 (68.12)	110.63 (73.80)	73.23 (46.41)
Employed/ Self-employed	91 (86.70)	56.75 (24.24)	56.93 (24.28)	57.23 (32.19)	91 (86.70)	93.30 (37.39)	94.93 (39.58)	88.73 (44.28)
Parents' highest level of education	90				90			
Secondary school or less	15 (16.70)	56.60 (27.86)	55.93 (30.28)	58.03 (30.25)	15 (16.70)	93.16 (37.04)	98.01 (41.72)	81.56 (34.59)
UK college qualification	30 (33.30)	55.82 (21.76)	56.28 (23.01)	55.44 (27.09)	30 (33.30)	99.12 (45.86)	102.13 (49.13)	88.74 (43.68)
UK University Undergraduate degree	32 (35.60)	54.06 (22.47)	54.76 (23.34)	51.88 (24.63)	32 (35.60)	85.71 (32.40)	86.71 (34.85)	82.13 (37.27)
UK University Post-graduate degree	13 (14.40)	61.16 (17.66)	61.79 (15.66)	63.98 (38.72)	13 (14.40)	90.51 (39.13)	87.83 (36.23)	100.11 (52.89)

Note. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$.

Descriptive statistics for BMI are presented in Table 5-2, with 185 children and 119 parents having provided objective measures of BMI. Sixteen children refused to have their mass and stature recorded whereas 64 parents self-reported their mass and stature. One mother's measures were subsequently excluded from the analysis due to pregnancy and 17 parents refused to self-report their mass and stature. Only objective measures of BMI were included in the final analyses. No significant differences were observed when comparing the BMI z-scores of children who did and did not meet the WTC ($p = .06$), although this was approaching significance. Additionally, no significant differences were found when comparing the BMI of parents who met the WTC and those who did not ($p = .90$). From objective BMI data ($n = 119$) parents were classified as underweight ($n = 1$), normal weight ($n = 36$), overweight excluding obese ($n = 45$), obese excluding morbidly obese ($n = 32$), and morbidly obese ($n = 5$). From the objective BMI z-score of child participants ($n = 185$), 122 children were deemed healthy weight, whilst 63 were classified as being overweight/obese.

Significant differences were observed between boys and girls BMI z-scores, with boys having significantly higher scores than girls ($p < .05$). Additionally, children with low area-SES were found to have significantly higher BMI z-scores than those with higher area-SES ($p < .05$) when controlling for gender. Whilst no significant differences were observed for parent BMI regarding gender, significant differences were observed for area-SES parent education, and household income (all $p < .05$). With regards to area-SES (5.03 ± 2.81 decile), parents from a lower area-SES ($< \text{Decile } 5$) had significantly higher BMI's than those from more affluent areas ($\geq \text{Decile } 5$).

Table 5-2 Sample characteristics of child and parent participants with BMI/BMI-Z-Score mean differences.

	N			
	Child		Parent	
	<i>n</i> (%)	M (SD)	<i>n</i> (%)	M (SD)
Total Participants (<i>n</i>) = 113 dyads				
Characteristics				
Gender	185		119	
Male	95 (51.40)	.83 (1.18)	29 (24.40)	28.56 (4.29)
Female	90 (48.60)	.44 (.98)	90 (75.60)	28.26 (6.00)
CI LL - UL (95%)		.07 - .71*		-1.73 – 2.34
SIMD (area-SES)	167		106	
< Decile 5	91 (54.50)	.84 (1.16)	58 (54.70)	29.59 (6.17)
≥ Decile 5	76 (45.50)	.43 (1.04)	48 (45.30)	27.02 (4.79)
CI LL - UL (95%)		-.08 - .75*		.46 – 4.69*
Household income	89		49	
< £23, 833	16 (18.00)	.83 (1.21)	8 (16.30)	31.42 (7.77)
≥ £23, 833	73 (82.00)	.39 (1.12)	41 (83.70)	26.78 (4.65)
CI LL - UL (95%)		-.22 – 1.02		-1.91 – 11.18
Parent occupation	172		114	
Unemployed/ Stay at home parent	17 (9.90)	.95 (1.06)	15 (13.20)	27.85 (4.82)
Student/ Retired	8 (4.70)	1.00 (.86)	5 (4.40)	29.02 (5.54)
Employed/ Self-employed	147 (85.50)	.59 (1.12)	94 (82.50)	28.42 (5.87)
Parents' highest level of education	144		93	
Secondary school or less	24 (16.70)	.73 (1.25)	16 (17.20)	30.48 (6.22)
College degree	58 (40.30)	.74 (1.15)	40 (43.00)	29.55 (6.08)
Undergraduate degree	46 (31.90)	.59 (1.07)	27 (29.00)	25.90 (4.47)
Post-graduate degree	16 (11.10)	.38 (.64)	10 (10.80)	25.82 (3.10) *

Note. * $p < .05$.

Additionally, there was a significant difference between parent education groups and their BMI as determined by one-way ANOVA ($F(3,89) = 4.01, p = .01$) in which a Tukey post-hoc test revealed that parent BMI was significantly higher in parents with a secondary school or less qualification when compared to parents who had a bachelor's degree ($p < .05$). Parents with a UK college qualification had a significantly higher BMI than parents with a UK University degree ($p < .05$).

Parent and child MVPA for all days was not related ($r = .14, p = .15$), and neither was parent and child MVPA on weekdays ($r = .10, p = .28$). Parent and child MVPA were significantly related on weekend days ($r = .28, p < .01$). BMI/BMI z-score and MVPA were not significantly related for either parent participants on all days ($r = -.08, p = .54$), weekdays ($r = -.08, p = .53$), and weekend days ($r = -.10, p = .41$) or child participants on all days ($r = -.11, p = .27$), weekdays ($r = -.10, p = .30$), or weekend days ($r = -.09, p = .35$). The objective BMI/BMI z-score of parent and child dyads ($n = 114$) were significantly related ($r = .40, p < .001$). Parent BMI and household income were negatively related ($r = -.45, p < .001$), as were parent BMI and area-SES ($r = -.30, p < .01$), and parent BMI and parent education ($r = -.32, p < .01$). Children's BMI z-score was negatively related to area-SES ($r = -.19, p < .05$), however there were no significant associations between child BMI-z-scores and the additional SES variables.

The regression mediation analyses used the unstandardized regression coefficients bootstrap estimates (B) of the direct and indirect effects together with bias corrected and accelerated 95% CI. Model one (see Figure 5-2 Model A) tested the indirect effect of area-SES on the BMI z-score of child participants via the BMI of parent participants (SIMD score as the independent variable, BMI z-score as the dependent variable and parent BMI as the mediator) which explained 47.73% of the variance in BMI z-score ($R^2 = .23, F(3, 97) = 9.54, p = .00$).

Figure 5-2 Mediation models examining the direct effects of SIMD on Child BMI via parent BMI, and child MVPA on weekdays, weekend days, and all days via parent MVPA on weekdays, weekend days, and all days. Model A used child gender as a covariate. Models B-D used child gender and child age as covariates. Beta unstandardized path coefficients were used. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$; WD = Weekday; WK = Weekend; AD = All days (the entire week).

Area-SES was significantly related to parent BMI ($B = -.58, SE = .19, p < .01$), which predicted child BMI z-score ($B = .06, SE = .02, p < .01$). The direct effect of area-SES on child BMI z-score was significant ($B = .08, SE = .04, p < .05$). There was also a significant negative indirect effect of area-SES on the BMI z-score of child participants via the BMI of parent participants ($B = -.04, SE = .02, 95\% \text{ CI} = -.07 \text{ to } -.01$). Therefore, the higher the SIMD score of dyads (being from more affluent area-SES in Scotland) the lower the BMI z-score of child participants via their parents BMI.

Model two (see Figure 5-2 Model B) tested the indirect effect of area-SES on child weekday MVPA via parent's weekday MVPA (SIMD score as the independent variable, child weekday MVPA as the dependent variable and parent weekday MVPA as the mediator) which explained 31.58% of the variance in child weekday MVPA ($R^2 = .10, F(3, 97) = 2.66, p < .05$). Area-SES was not related to parent weekday MVPA ($B = -1.31, SE = 1.58, p = .41$), which did not predict child weekday MVPA ($B = .07, SE = .05, p = .21$). No significant direct effect of area-SES on child weekday MVPA ($B = -1.18, SE = .85, p = .17$) or indirect effect of area-SES on child weekday MVPA via parent weekday MVPA ($B = -.09, SE = .14, 95\% \text{ CI} = -.43, .11$) were observed.

Model three (see Figure 5-2 Model C) tested the indirect effect of area-SES on child weekend MVPA via parent weekend MVPA (SIMD score as the independent variable, child weekend MVPA as the dependent variable and parent weekend MVPA as the mediator) which explained 35.63% of the variance in child weekend MVPA ($R^2 = .13, F(3, 97) = 3.49, p = .01$). Area-SES was not related to parent weekend MVPA ($B = -.81, SE = 1.63, p = .62$), however parent MVPA on weekend days predicted child weekend MVPA ($B = .20, SE = .07, p < .01$). The direct effect of area-SES on child weekend MVPA was not significant ($B = -1.12, SE = 1.09, p = .31$), similarly to the indirect effect of area-SES on child weekend MVPA via parents' weekend MVPA ($B = -.16, SE = .30, 95\% \text{ CI} = -.75, .45$).

No significant direct or indirect effects were found between area-SES on child MVPA for all days via parent MVPA for all days (see Figure 5-2 Model D). SIMD as the independent variable, child MVPA for all days as the dependent variable and parent MVPA for all days as the mediator explained 30.98% of the variance in child MVPA for all days ($R^2=.10$, $F(3, 97) = 2.55$, $p < .05$). Area-SES was not related to parent MVPA on all days ($B = -1.29$, $SE = 1.50$, $p = .39$), which did not predict child MVPA for all days ($B = .09$, $SE = .06$, $p = .11$). The direct effect of area-SES on child MVPA on all days was not significant ($B = -1.18$, $SE = .84$, $p = .17$), similarly to the indirect effect of area-SES on children's MVPA for all days, operating via their parents MVPA for all days ($B = -.12$, $SE = .16$, 95% CI = $-.50$, $.12$).

5.4 Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that both children and parents spent a large proportion of their time during the day inactive. Parent and child MVPA were significantly related on weekend days, but not for all days or weekdays. There were no significant indirect effects of area-SES on child MVPA via their parent's MVPA. Additionally, no significant differences between parent or child MVPA when comparing those from high and low SES were observed. For BMI, we found that parents and children with low SES had higher BMI's in comparison to those with higher SES. As expected the BMI/BMI z-score of parent and child dyads were significantly related. There were significant negative direct and indirect effects of area-SES on the BMI z-score of child participants via the BMI of parent participants. Thus, the level of deprivation where the families resided was related to parent BMI, and parent BMI was related to their child's BMI z-score. Our findings suggest that whilst child participation in MVPA is somewhat related to parental MVPA, it is not linked to SES, whereas children's BMI is related directly to SES and indirectly influenced by SES via

parents' BMI. Such results may be useful for the implementation of health interventions targeting children living in areas of deprivation.

Parent and child MVPA was only found to be related on weekend days, in which children are known to accumulate the least amount of daily MVPA (Brooke et al., 2016). As children spend a considerable amount of time during their weekdays at school away from parents, parents are less likely to influence the PA levels of their children during the week in comparison to the weekend. Some studies have examined the weekday-weekend variations in the relationship between parent and child activity, suggesting that this relationship is stronger during weekends when compared to weekdays (Sigmundová et al., 2018), and parent and children engage in more PA on weekend days (Dunton et al., 2012, Sigmund et al., 2015). Nevertheless, studies examining the relationship between parent and child PA typically fail to include separate analyses for weekday and weekend data (Jago et al., 2010, Stearns et al., 2016), therefore our findings are timely. In the current study there were no significant effects of SES in relation to parent and child MVPA. SES has been found to be related to PA levels in adult (Trost et al., 2002) and child (Drenowatz et al., 2010) populations, although recent research has raised questions regarding this relationship (Beenackers et al., 2012, Stalsberg and Pedersen, 2018). Equivocality in this area of research may arise from a limited quantity of studies, weak research designs, the use of self-reported measures of PA (McNeill et al., 2017) and variation in the methods employed to measure SES. Nonetheless, as children from lower-income families are less likely to attend sessions of structured out-of-school PA than those from wealthier families, children from lower-income families have been found to be just as active (Voss et al., 2008). A possible explanation for this and for our findings may be because children living in deprived areas participate in more unstructured outdoor free-play than children from more affluent families (Sallis, Prochaska, & Taylor, 2000). Further research is warranted nonetheless to confirm this assumption.

Parents of low SES were found to have a higher BMI. We also found significant direct and indirect effects of area-SES on child BMI z-scores, indicating that residing within areas of high deprivation may influence children's BMI both directly and indirectly via parent BMI. Previous findings have found that SES is strongly associated with the occurrence of obesity in child and adult populations (Aitsi-Selmi et al., 2013). Poor dietary behaviours are associated with living in lower SES areas (McLaren, 2007). With a greater number of unhealthy food outlets located in more deprived areas, it is unsurprising that children residing in such areas are most likely to be overweight or obese (Cetateanu and Jones, 2014). Children's exposure to obesogenic family environments such as household eating habits, are considered environmental factors that contribute to health inequalities (Darmon and Drewnowski, 2008). A recent Growing up in Scotland Report from the Scottish Government (Scottish Government, 2018) found that socioeconomic circumstances caused the prevalence of overweight and obesity to vary in 10 year old's, with 25% of children living in the least deprived areas found to be overweight or obese compared to 39% of children living in the most deprived areas. Moreover, a study exploring the relationship between children's BMI, parent obesity and SES, found that the average BMI of boys whose mothers were unemployed was higher than the BMI of boys whose mothers were employed (Tchicaya and Lorentz, 2014). Nevertheless, research indicates that the co-occurrence of multiple health behaviours including PA, arises at the family level, and that interventions aiming to improve the health of children should focus on families as a whole instead of individuals (Niermann, Spengler and Gubbels, 2018). When comparing settings (i.e., inside the home and outside the home) research has shown that associations in mother-child MVPA were stronger when both were at home together (Song et al., 2017). Collectively, the findings of previous research and ours provide practical implications for interventions aiming to improve children's activity levels and weight status. Taken together, this research highlights the effects SES can have on

children's health outcomes via parental weight status. As such this indicates that family-centred, home-based interventions in areas of deprivation are important avenues to health improvement.

Notable strengths of this study include the use of ActiGraph GT3X+ devices deployed on the wrist in both parents and their child to measure MVPA. Specifically, in our sample, parents and children wore the devices for a substantial and similar amount of days, and within each day, devices were worn for a significant period. As such, our findings regarding the relationship of parent and child MVPA should be confidently interpreted. The use of mediation analyses to interpret area-SES variables which indirectly effect the MVPA of parent and child dyads is a strength of this study. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to examine the mediating effect of area-SES on children's MVPA and BMI z-scores operating via their parents MVPA and BMI. However, this study was not without limitations including its cross-sectional design and lack of longitudinal data prohibits drawing conclusions about causality. This study was conducted between October and May in which variation in PA may occur due to seasonal change, however, a review conducted found that no conclusion can be made regarding this influence due to the lack of studies conducted and incomparable definitions of season (Rich, Griffiths and Dezateux, 2012). Missing accelerometry data (i.e., the participant did not wear the device) or failure to meet the WTC reduced the sample size used in subsequent analysis. Providing no financial incentives or not being able to go back into the schools to further distribute the devices may explain the failure to meet the WTC. The exclusion of multiple participants in research exploring parent and child activity is fairly common (Solomon-Moore et al., 2018) and in order to encourage continued wear of the devices, incentives may be required for parents and children. Missing data, particularly for both household income and objectively measured BMI in parents was evident. Finally, we were unable to conduct separate analyses on different genders across

parent and child dyads, and longitudinal analyses on the effects of children's increasing age on parent and child PA over time due to our limited sample and study time-frame which should also be considered a limitation. Research suggests that the PA relationships are more pronounced in mother-child dyads than father-child ones, both on weekdays and at weekends (Jacobi et al., 2011, Sigmund et al., 2015). Nevertheless, studies examining the relationship between parent and child dyads have not clearly confirmed gender-specific PA associations. Additionally as children grow older and reach 10-11 years of age, children's cognitive decision making abilities increase and they begin to assert a degree of independence from their parents (Jago et al., 2009). As such, future research should aim to explore the differences between father-child and mother-child MVPA in relation to the influence of SES and the age of the child. Whilst our sample size is relatively small, and therefore may affect the generalizability of our findings across populations, we would argue that our study only included objective MVPA and BMI data. Thus, our findings may be interpreted with some confidence, especially in comparison to previous research in this field which employs both self-reported measures for PA and BMI.

5.4.1 Conclusion

This study, to the best of our knowledge, is the first to examine the mediating effects of SES on parent and child dyads MVPA and BMI. We found a significant relationship between parent and child MVPA on weekend days only. Whilst parent and child PA is more likely to be related when parents and their child spend time together (e.g., weekends, afterschool), MVPA is known to make up a small percentage of time spent in activity which may explain the lack of significant effects related to area-SES. Our findings demonstrate both a significant negative indirect effect of area-SES on child BMI z-score via parent BMI and a significant direct effect of area-SES on child BMI z-score which has not been explored in previous research. As such, future research should look to explore the effects of area-SES on

parent and child BMI and MVPA in further detail. Gaining an in-depth perspective of these relationships may inform the development of interventions which aim to improve children's health-related outcomes through the involvement of their parent.

Thesis Study Map

Study	Objectives and Key Findings
<p>Study 1: An insight into mothers with low socioeconomic status' involvement in Scottish primary school health education activities</p>	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recruit less-involved mothers with low SES • Interview these mothers to establish barriers to their involvement in school-based health education and gain insight and recommendations on how to engage families with low SES • Based on the findings, propose strategies schools can use to increase parent involvement in future health-related activities <p>Key Findings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mothers with low SES state similar barriers to being involved when compared to previous research; however, with added barriers including lack of confidence, feelings of being disliked by the parent council and unpredictable working schedules. • Emphasis was placed on increased communication with school staff and variation in the timing of events • Mothers recommended school staff should organise events more instead of the parent council
<p>Study 2: The effects of socioeconomic status on parent and child dyads moderate-to-vigorous physical activity and body mass index</p>	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine the relationship between parent and child MVPA and BMI in a sample of children (4-11 years old) using wrist-worn accelerometers. • Explore mediating processes by which SES influences child MVPA and BMI z-score through their parents MVPA and BMI. <p>Key findings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekend parent and child MVPA was significantly related. • Parent and child BMI were also significantly related. • There was a significant negative direct effect of SES on child BMI. • a significant negative indirect effect of SES on child BMI via their parents BMI was observed.
<p>Study 3: Relationship between parent and child dyads physical activity using novel acceleration metrics</p>	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine whether the intensity or volume of PA predicts BMI in children and adults • Explore parent-child associations between these metrics and BMI.
<p>Study 4: Exploring the feasibility of a cluster-randomised control trial to improve children's 24 h movement behaviours and dietary intake: HH</p>	

CHAPTER 6 STUDY 3

Relationship between parent and child dyads physical activity using novel
acceleration metrics

6.1 Introduction

The link between obesity and physical inactivity is well established (World Health Organization, 2018b). Current recommendations encourage youth to undertake at least 60 mins of daily MVPA (Australian Government, 2018) but self-report and objective assessments of PA indicates that children are failing to meet these recommendations (Hallal et al., 2012, Sallis et al., 2016). Therefore, identifying the primary determinants of children's PA is an important public health issue.

Parent-child PA has been of interest for decades. Greater parental MVPA is associated with increased child MVPA (Fuemmeler, Anderson and Mâsse, 2011) although earlier findings suggest there is no link between the time parents and children engage in MVPA (Jago et al., 2010). Parent-child PA research is limited due to an over-reliance on subjective measures of PA, (Troost and Loprinzi, 2011) use of pedometers, (Stearns et al., 2016) and varying activity outcomes (e.g., MVPA, total PA) (Craig, Cameron and Tudor-Locke, 2013). Accelerometers are the gold standard method for measuring free-living PA in adults and children (Esliger et al., 2011) with ActiGraph (Pensacola, FL, USA) accelerometers commonly used by researchers (Wijndaele et al., 2015). Accelerometers can be worn continuously on sites including the wrist and hip (Fairclough et al., 2016). Advantages of wrist placement include the facilitation of long-term compliance, (Nyberg et al., 2009) the examination of low-intensity PA, and classifying sleep behaviours (Ekblom et al., 2012).

Accelerometer-derived data is usually expressed as time spent within laboratory produced cut-points but these are dependent on the calibration sample and protocol used (Troiano et al., 2014). Algorithms which have been validated in a specific group (e.g., children) may not be valid for another age group (e.g., adults) due to differing PA patterns. Traditional methods of quantifying PA from accelerometers preclude the comparison

between children and parents because of the use of these population and laboratory-specific generated cut-points. Activity metrics which do not rely on calibration protocols, capture the intensity distribution and are more independent of overall activity are required to facilitate comparisons between studies.

The use of the IG metric alongside AvAcc to capitalise on the increasing availability of accelerometer data has recently been proposed (Rowlands et al., 2018). AvAcc provides a measure of the volume of activity whereas the IG describes the intensity distribution of acceleration. The benefits of reporting these metrics lie in their suitability for comparison across studies with raw acceleration data (Rowlands et al., 2018). When examining whether independent relationships were evident for AvAcc and IG with measures of adiposity in type 2 diabetic adults and adolescent girls, only AvAcc was independently and negatively associated with percent body fat and BMI in the adult sample (Rowlands et al., 2018). In adolescent girls, IG was independently and negatively associated with both percent body fat and BMI-z score. AvAcc was independently and positively associated with percent body fat. Another study examined whether AvAcc and IG were independently associated with several indicators of HWB in children (Fairclough, Taylor, Rowlands, Boddy, et al., 2019). Unlike AvAcc, IG was found to be negatively associated with BMI z-score, waist-to-height ratio and a composite MS risk score, and positively associated with cardiorespiratory fitness (Fairclough, Taylor, Rowlands, Boddy, et al., 2019). Such results suggest that both metrics could be utilised instead of laboratory-derived population- and device-specific activity thresholds, when examining the relative importance of intensity and volume of activity for a specific population and/or health outcome.

Whilst these metrics afford researchers the ability to compare accelerometer data across populations, no study has examined the relationship between these metrics in parent-child dyads. Therefore, this study aimed to examine whether the intensity or volume of PA

predicts BMI in children and adults and explore parent-child associations between these metrics and BMI.

6.2 Methods

6.2.1 Participants

Upon receiving ethical approval from the University's Research Ethics Committee, a sample of 4-11-year-old children ($n = 201$) and one of their parents were recruited from six schools in Lanarkshire and Glasgow, UK. Parents must have provided completed information sheets (see Appendix 2A) and consent paperwork (see Appendix 2B) prior to participation in this study.

6.2.2 Measures

Children ($n = 87$) and parents ($n = 52$) had their mass and stature measured objectively. Participants mass was measured barefoot to the nearest 0.1kg on electronic scales (Seca Digital Scales, Seca Ltd, Birmingham, UK), while stature was measured barefoot to the nearest 0.1cm using a portable stadiometer (Seca Digital Scales, Seca Ltd, Birmingham, UK) as per standard procedures (Cole, Freeman and Preece, 1995). Parents ($n = 31$) self-reported their mass and stature as they were unable to attend the school on data collection days. One mother's mass and stature were objectively measured but excluded from analysis as she was pregnant. Children ($n = 3$) and parents ($n = 6$) refused to either self-report their mass and stature or have it measured. From the mass and stature data provided, BMI was calculated. Thereon, BMI z-scores of child participants was determined and classified as healthy weight or obese/overweight relative to the UK 1990 BMI population reference data (Cole, Freeman and Preece, 1995). Adult BMI was classified relative to the WHO classifications (World Health Organization, 2018a).

Participants wore an ActiGraph GT3X+ accelerometer on their non-dominant wrist. Each monitor was synchronised with Greenwich Mean Time and initialized to use a sample

rate of 80HZ. Participants were instructed to wear the device for 24 h each day for seven days, except during water-based activities. Home postcodes were collected to calculate the SES of participants, based on the SIMD (Scottish Government, 2016b). SIMD is a measure of area-based multiple deprivations across six individual domains including current income, employment, housing, health, education, and skills/training.

6.2.3 Accelerometer processing

Data was downloaded in 5-s-epoch lengths using ActiLife v.6.13.3 (ActiGraph, Pensacola, FL) and saved in raw format as .gt3x files. These files were converted to time-stamp free .csv files, exported into R v3.5.2 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria, <https://cran.r-project.org/>), and processed using GGIR package v1.9.1. These raw triaxial accelerometer signals are auto-calibrated in GGIR using gravity as a reference, after detecting abnormally high values and non-wear time (Migueles, Rowlands, et al., 2019). GGIR calculates ENMO (1 g) averaged over 5 s epochs and expressed in mg.

Participants were excluded from analysis if their accelerometer files showed: post-calibration error greater than 0.01 g, < 3 days of valid wear (defined as ≥ 16 h per day) (Rowlands et al., 2016) or wear data was not present for each 15 min period of the 24 h cycle. The default non-wear setting whereby invalid data were imputed by the average at similar time-points on different days of the week was used. Therefore, outcome variables were calculated based on the entire 24 h cycle for all included participants.

PA was expressed as AvAcc across the day (mg), time accumulated in MVPA and time spent SED. Time spent in MVPA was defined as the time accumulated above an acceleration of 201 mg for children and 101 mg for adults (Hildebrand, van Hees, Hansen, & Ekelund, 2014). Inactive time was defined as time accumulated below 50 mg including sleep (Rowlands et al., 2018). The IG of the accelerations experienced over a 24 h period was determined in GGIR using the argument 'iglevels = TRUE.'

6.2.4 Analyses

AvAcc was used to describe overall activity and the IG used to describe the distribution of activity across the intensity categories. Initial examination of the data revealed that no school-level clustering was evident within the dataset (intraclass correlation = 0.01 to 0.05). Therefore, correlation coefficients examined the associations between parent-child activity outcomes as well as parent BMI and child BMI-z score. As there was evidence of a linear association with child BMI-z score, linear regression analyses were undertaken to examine the extent of which parental inactive time and BMI predicted child BMI-z score. Models were adjusted for potential covariates including parental BMI, household SIMD and the number of valid days of parent-child accelerometer wear time.

Finally, multiple linear regression analyses were used to examine whether the IG and AvAcc metrics were associated with BMI/BMI z-score. Variables were centred before entry into the regression analyses with a variance inflation factor (VIF) of > 5 used to indicate the presence of multicollinearity. Statistical analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS statistical software for Windows version 25 (IBM, Armonk, NY). The `loneway` command in Stata V.13 (Stata Corp. 2013. Stata Statistical Software: Release 13. College Station, Texas, USA: StataCorp LP) was used to examine if clustering was evident within the dataset. Regression analyses assumptions are associated with our use of PROCESS mediation analyses which include: linearity of the independent and dependant variables, normal distribution of the residuals, homoscedasticity of the residuals, uncorrelatedness of the residuals, absence of multicollinearity, and appropriate scale properties. Assumptions were met, excluding normal distribution, however, it was important not to manipulate the data by log-transforming the figures to allow the data to remain the reflective of parent-child dyad data and to avoid reporting a false-positive.

6.3 Results

Children ($n = 201$; 8.41 ± 1.98 years) and one of their parents (38.48 ± 6.91 years) were recruited. Dyads ($n = 4$) were not provided with accelerometers due to their child being absent from school on the day of testing, and one leaving before being provided with the accelerometer, thus 196 dyads were provided with accelerometers. Dyads were excluded from analyses as either the child or parent participant lost their accelerometer ($n = 3$), the accelerometers were not worn ($n = 10$) or the device malfunctioned ($n = 2$). Furthermore, child ($n = 3$) and parent ($n = 4$) participants had device malfunctions which resulted in the exclusion of a further 7 dyads. Thus, 174 parent-child dyads were eligible for subsequent analysis. Of these 174 parent-child dyads, 117 parents and 104 children met the WTC of 3 days (≥ 16 h). Of these participants, 27 parents and 14 children were excluded due to their respective dyadic partner failing to meet the WTC. This resulted in available data of 90 parent-child dyads suitable to be analysed (44.78%). Parents who met the WTC were found to be significantly older (40.29 ± 6.67 years) than those who did not (37.02 ± 6.78 years). Similarly, child participants who met the WTC were significantly older (8.87 ± 1.67 years) than those who did not (8.05 ± 2.13 years). A significant difference in child gender was observed in those who did and did not meet the WTC, with 51/59 girls meeting the WTC and only 39/45 boys meeting the WTC.

Descriptive characteristics and activity outcomes are presented in Table 6-1. Bivariate correlations between accelerometer-derived parent-child activity outcomes are presented in Table 6-2. Findings revealed no significant associations between any of the parent and child activity outcomes. For girls, BMI-z was positively associated with parent inactive time ($r = 0.32$, $p < 0.05$) and parent BMI ($r = 0.41$, $p < 0.01$). For boys, parent BMI was negatively associated with their inactive time ($r = -0.044$, $p < 0.01$) and positively associated with their LPA ($r = 0.36$, $p < 0.05$). Linear regression models used to predict child BMI-z score are

presented in Table 6-3. Parental inactive time, when adjusted for parent BMI, SIMD and number of valid days of accelerometer wear predicted girls BMI-z score ($p < 0.05$), however, this was not observed in boys. Parent BMI predicted both girls ($p < 0.01$) and boys ($p < 0.05$) BMI z-score when adjusted for parent inactive time, SIMD and number of valid days of accelerometer wear. Table 6-4 outlines the associations between AvAcc and IG with BMI measures in parents and children. Findings show that for parents, AvAcc and IG were not associated with BMI. Additionally, no independent effects were observed between AvAcc and IG and between MVPA and AvAcc.

Table 6-1 Descriptive characteristics for continuous variables

Variables	Male (<i>n</i>)	Female (<i>n</i>)	Male <i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Female <i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)
Child Age (y)	39	51	8.90 (1.67)	8.84 (1.69)
Child AvAcc (mg)	39	51	52.73 (22.06)	44.55 (10.97)
Child LPA (min.d ⁻¹)	39	51	85.69 (25.46)	90.42 (17.79)
Child MVPA (min.d ⁻¹)	39	51	73.49 (37.54)	57.92 (22.24)
Child inactive time <50 mg (min.d ⁻¹)	39	51	1151.67 (85.69)	1150.25 (50.35)
Child IG	39	51	-1.91 (0.15)	-2.04 (0.15)
Child Stature (cm)	38	49	134.94 (11.04)	135.61 (12.19)
Child Mass (kg)	38	49	31.48 (6.71)	31.80 (8.24)
Child BMI z-score	38	49	0.45 (1.02)	0.07 (1.43)
Parent Age (y)	16	73	42 (8.90)	39.92 (6.09)
Parent AvAcc (mg)	17	73	26.33 (5)	30.14 (6.79)
Parent LPA (min.d ⁻¹)	17	73	128.44 (35.86)	164.74 (39.61)
Parent MVPA (min.d ⁻¹)	17	73	90.08 (34.34)	104.19 (40.91)
Parent inactive time <50mg (min.d ⁻¹)	17	73	1223.67(58.36)	1174.28 (71.68)
Parent IG	17	73	-2.48 (0.23)	-2.53 (0.20)
Parent Stature (cm)	15	68	175.69 (6.30)	163.14 (7.28)
Parent Mass (kg)	15	68	82.53 (14.21)	70.54 (15.49)
Parent BMI	15	68	26.81 (4.88)	26.56 (5.86)

Note. Min.d⁻¹ = mins per day

Table 6-2 Correlations between parent and child accelerometer-derived activity outcomes and BMI.

Variables	<u>Girls (n = 51)</u>						<u>Boys (n = 36)</u>					
	Inactive time (min.d ⁻¹)	LPA (min.d ⁻¹)	MVPA (min.d ⁻¹)	AvAcc (mg)	BMI-z	IG	Inactive time (min.d ⁻¹)	LPA (min.d ⁻¹)	MVPA (min.d ⁻¹)	AvAcc (mg)	BMI-z	IG
Parent inactive time <50 mg (min.d ⁻¹)	0.03	-0.11	-0.06	-0.05	0.32*	-0.01	0.13	-0.10	-0.08	-0.07	0.27	-0.03
Parent LPA (min.d ⁻¹)	-0.05	0.09	0.03	0.05	-0.27	-0.02	-0.18	0.14	0.19	0.21	-0.27	0.18
Parent MVPA (min.d ⁻¹)	-0.03	0.16	0.11	-0.09	-0.26	0.06	-0.07	0.07	-0.02	-0.04	-0.16	-0.09
Parent AvAcc (mg)	-0.06	0.17	0.11	0.10	-0.27	0.53	-0.08	0.70	-0.02	-0.05	-0.20	-0.10
Parent IG	-0.10	0.11	0.06	0.06	-0.001	0.03	0.13	-0.13	-0.20	-0.22	-0.24	-0.19
Parent BMI	0.21	-0.11	-0.12	-0.14	0.41**	-0.116	-0.44**	0.36*	0.27	0.23	0.32	-0.20

Note. * = p<0.05; ** = p<0.01; Min.d⁻¹ = mins per day.

Table 6-3 Linear regression models predicting child BMI-z score by gender

Exposure	Girls (<i>n</i> = 51)					Boys (<i>n</i> = 36)				
	Coefficient	95% CI	T	P	Model R2	Coefficient	95% CI	T	P	Model R2
Parent inactive time (min.d ⁻¹)*	0.006	0.01, 0.01	2.24	0.03	0.30	0.001	-0.005, 0.006	0.20	0.85	0.171
Parent BMI**	0.10	0.03, 0.17	2.75	0.009	0.30	0.13	0.01, 0.24	2.30	0.03	0.35

Note. Min.d⁻¹ = mins per day; * Models were adjusted for parental BMI, SIMD and number of valid days of accelerometer wear time; ** Models were adjusted for parent inactive time, SIMD and number of valid days of accelerometer wear time.

Table 6-4 Associations between two activity metrics with BMI measures in parents and children

Variables	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3		Independent effect (Model 3)
	Coefficient	95% CI	Coefficient	95% CI	Coefficient	95% CI	
Adult BMI							
Adult AvAcc (mg)	-0.09	-0.30, 0.12	-0.05	-0.26, 0.16	-0.004	-0.24, 0.23	x
Adult IG	-4.16	-10.71, 2.39	-3.58	-9.80, 2.65	-3.53	-10.40, 3.34	x
Girls BMI z-score							
Girls AvAcc (mg)	-0.03	-0.07, 0.01	-0.03	-0.08, 0.008	-0.03	-0.09, 0.03	x
Girls IG	-1.69	-4.62, 1.24	-1.92	-5.04, 1.20	-0.36	-4.72, 4.01	x
Boys BMI z-score							
Boys AvAcc (mg)	-.008	-0.03, 0.008	-0.007	-0.02, 0.009	0.003	-0.02, 0.02	x
Boys IG	-3.14**	-5.34, -0.94	-2.57*	-4.94, -0.20	-2.84	-5.74, 0.73	x

Note. * = $p < 0.05$; ** = $p < 0.01$; Model 1 unadjusted. Model 2 adjusted for age, gender and SIMD. Model 3 adjusted for alternative activity metric. Whether associations between an activity metric were independent of the other metric is noted in the final column (i.e., x or \checkmark).

In boys' significant associations between IG and BMI z-score were observed in the unadjusted model, and when adjusted for age and SIMD. However, when the model was adjusted further for the alternative metric, this significant association was not evident. No independent effects were observed between AvAcc and IG and no significant associations were observed between boys BMI z-score and AvAcc. For girls, no significant associations were observed between AvAcc and IG with BMI z-score. No independent effects were observed between the two metrics. In all cases, VIF did not exceed 5 although the independent effects between MVPA and AvAcc could not be determined due to a high VIF (>5).

6.4 Discussion

This is the first study to examine parent-child activity using novel accelerometer-derived metrics. Findings revealed no significant associations between parent-child activity. Whilst girls BMI z-score was found to be positively associated with parent inactive time and parent BMI, this was not observed for boys. As such, our findings suggest that parent-child activity is not related although a significant relationship was evident between parent BMI and BMI z-score but for girls only. Whilst the sharing of genetic and behavioural factors between parents and children could result in a similar propensity for obesity status, the association of parent-child BMI can vary by child's sex and age (Silventoinen et al., 2010). Both the son's and daughter's BMI has been reported to be significantly related to father's BMI, while a daughter's BMI was significantly related to the mother's BMI only (Shafaghi et al., 2014). Our sample is largely made up of female participants (mothers (81.1%) and daughters (56.7%)) which may explain the stronger observed association between mothers BMI and daughters BMI z-score compared to that of the sons BMI z-scores (Liu et al., 2013). Indicative of our results, it would be expected that unhealthy parental BMI would be associated with unhealthy child behaviours, with children of active parents being less likely

to be overweight/obese (Lee et al., 2019). Indeed previous studies have observed associations of higher parental BMI with their children viewing more TV (Steffen et al., 2009) and, similarly to our findings, engaging in less PA (Kosti et al., 2008). Parental BMI reflects their health behaviours and home environment, which in turn, may influence their children's health behaviours such as PA. Specifically, higher maternal BMI is related to increased SED behaviours (Sijtsma, Sauer and Corpeleijn, 2015) and reduced fruit consumption (Morello et al., 2012) in children. Overall, these results indicate that unhealthy levels of parental activity and BMI can negatively influence their children's weight status. This may place children at greater risk of becoming an obese adult as well as developing conditions including type 2 diabetes mellitus and the MS at a younger age (Elizondo-Montemayor et al., 2010).

No significant associations were found for AvAcc, IG and MVPA with BMI in adult participants or BMI z-score in children. Previous research exploring the associations of AvAcc and IG with BMI have found that the volume of activity (AvAcc) is negatively associated with adolescent girls' percent body fat, type 2 diabetic adults' percent body fat and BMI, and children's BMI (Rowlands et al., 2018, Buchan, McLellan, et al., 2019). Additionally, these studies suggest that the intensity distribution of activity (IG) is negatively associated with BMI z-score in children and adolescent girls. Our study found an association between the intensity distribution of activity and BMI z-score in boys, but not girls or adults. When the model was adjusted further for the alternative metric, this significant association was not evident. No independent effects between the metrics were observed in adults or children.

Research surrounding the associations between parent-child activity is ambiguous. For instance, Jago et al., (2010) found no association between parent-child activity among a sample of 10- to 11-year-old children and their parents (Jago et al., 2010). By contrast, others have found that parent activity levels are positively correlated with child activity levels, with

children of more active parents more likely to have higher activity levels than children of less active parents (Freedson and Evenson, 1991, Fuemmeler, Anderson and Mâsse, 2011). Whilst it seems obvious to suggest that parents are more likely to influence their child's activity when they are in one another's company, difficulty in interpreting the relationship between parent and child activity is apparent. The difficulties in interpreting the relationship between objective parent-child PA is most likely due to studies employing different accelerometer devices, placement sites and cut-points used to quantify time spent in activity intensities. In their laboratory validation study, Hildebrand et al., (2014) required both adult and child participants to wear ActiGraph GT3X + and GENEActiv devices on their hip and wrist to compare raw accelerometer outputs after completing eight structured activities (Hildebrand, van Hees, Hansen, & Ekelund, 2014). Although accelerometer outputs appeared compatible when attached to the same location in adults, inconsistent differences were evident between device placement and brand of accelerometers in children.

Deploying wrist-mounted accelerometers will likely result in higher compliance rates when deployed on the hip (Troiano et al., 2014). Indeed, the 2011–2012 and 2013–2014 cycles of the NHANES required participants to wear accelerometers on their non-dominant wrist based on improved user compliance, improved ability to measure sleep, and for capturing more upper extremity movements which may not have been captured using a hip-mounted device (Esliger et al., 2011, van Hees et al., 2014, Fairclough et al., 2016). Greater compliance will provide researchers with confidence that activity estimates are more representative of habitual activity however, activity levels themselves vary when comparing hip and wrist placement (Noonan et al., 2017). A study examining the activity estimates of children wearing wrist- and hip-mounted ActiGraph GT3X+ accelerometers found that the wrist device detected more mins in LPA, MPA, VPA and MVPA whereas the hip detected more SED behaviour (McLellan, Arthur and Buchan, 2018). Furthermore, the cut-points used

to determine time spent in activity intensities can also lead to contrasting results with findings suggesting that time spent in MVPA for a sample of 419 children aged 3-6 years can vary from 39 to 269 mins per day depending on the cut-points used (Bornstein et al., 2011). Therefore, comparing findings between studies deploying different accelerometer methodologies is challenging and may in part explain the ambiguity in findings of studies examining parent-child activity.

The cross-sectional nature of this study is a limitation, as is the recruitment of participants from only two locations in Scotland which may limit the generalizability of our findings. We recognise the limitations of including self-reported BMI data, however, we believe that in doing so, we avoid inclusion bias and the exclusion of participants who have additional valid data. The use of only one health outcome measure is acknowledged. Further work examining the IG and AvAcc with additional health outcomes in parents and children is encouraged. A strength of this study is the examination of the utility of the IG and AvAcc metrics with BMI and BMI z-score in parent-child dyads for the first time. Finally, the use of stringent accelerometer inclusion criteria meant that outcome variables were based on the entire 24h cycle rather than estimating time awake which provides confidence in our outcomes. By reporting these novel metrics, future work may be able to directly compare their findings to ours without the limitations of using widely different accelerometer processing methods.

6.4.1 Conclusion

Our study revealed no significant associations in parent-child activity using the AvAcc and IG metrics. However, we found that girls BMI z-score was positively associated with parent inactive time per day and parent BMI. These findings were not observed for boys. Further research is warranted to explore the effects of parental weight and activity status on male and female child participants to understand these relationships in more detail.

Thesis Study Map

Study	Objectives and Key Findings
Study 1: An insight into mothers with low socioeconomic status' involvement in Scottish primary school health education activities	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recruit less-involved mothers with low SES • Interview these mothers to establish barriers to their involvement in school-based health education and gain insight and recommendations on how to engage families with low SES • Based on the findings, propose strategies schools can use to increase parent involvement in future health-related activities <p>Key findings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mothers with low SES state similar barriers to being involved when compared to previous research; however, with added barriers including lack of confidence, feelings of being disliked by the parent council and unpredictable working schedules. • Emphasis was placed on increased communication with school staff and variation in the timing of events • Mothers recommended school staff should organise events more instead of the parent council
Study 2: The effects of socioeconomic status on parent and child dyads moderate-to-vigorous physical activity and body mass index	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine the relationship between parent and child MVPA and BMI in a sample of children (4-11 years old) using wrist-worn accelerometers. • Explore mediating processes by which SES influences child MVPA and BMI z-score through their parents MVPA and BMI. <p>Key findings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekend parent and child MVPA was significantly related. • Parent and child BMI were also significantly related. • There was a significant negative direct effect of SES on child BMI. • a significant negative indirect effect of SES on child BMI via their parents BMI was observed.
Study 3: Relationship between parent and child dyads physical activity using novel acceleration metrics	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine whether the intensity or volume of PA predicts BMI in children and adults • Explore parent-child associations between these metrics and BMI. <p>Key findings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The activity metrics were not associated with parent BMI, and no independent effects were observed between the metrics. • Associations between boys IG and BMI z-score were observed. • No independent effects were observed between the two metrics and no significant associations were observed between boys BMI z-score and AvAcc. • For girls, no significant associations were observed between AvAcc and IG with BMI z-score and no independent effects were observed between the two metrics.
Study 4: Exploring the feasibility of a cluster-randomised control trial to improve children's 24 h movement behaviours and dietary intake: HH	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore the feasibility of HH from qualitative investigations with teachers and pupils • Examine preliminary effects of the HH pilot intervention on children's 24 h activity patterns and dietary behaviours.

CHAPTER 7 STUDY 4

Exploring the feasibility of a cluster-randomised control trial to improve children's 24 h movement behaviours and dietary intake: Happy Homework

7.1 Introduction

Childhood obesity has reached epidemic levels in many countries (Tremblay, Katzmarzyk and Willms, 2002). Overweight youth are at an increased risk of remaining overweight into adulthood (Reilly et al., 2003), with insufficient PA being shown to relate to higher weight status and poorer health outcomes in children. PA guidelines suggest that children aged 5–17 years should accumulate at least 60 mins of MVPA daily (Department of Health and Social Care, 2019). Yet, findings from a Global Matrix comparing 15 countries indicate that children are failing to meet these recommendations (Tremblay et al., 2014), particularly those with low SES (Gidlow et al., 2006).

Recent 24 h movement guidelines were developed in Canada (Tremblay et al., 2016) and Australia (Australian Government Department of Health, 2019), which represent a paradigm shift in thinking about movement behaviours. Such recommendations have altered from focussing on a single movement behaviour (e.g., MVPA) to an integrated movement behaviour model. This model includes recommendations that children should participate in at least 60 mins of daily MVPA, view no more than 2 h of recreational ST, sustain adequate sleep durations of between 9-11 h per night and maintain consistent bed and wake times. Children meeting all three recommendations have the lowest odds ratio for obesity in comparison to those not meeting such recommendations (Carson, Tremblay, et al., 2016).

Development of effective interventions that encourage children to meet the 24 h movement guidelines is a key priority for public health researchers. However, the majority of interventions aiming to promote healthy behaviours in children are implemented whilst children are at school (Dobbins et al., 2013, Hegarty et al., 2016). Although some have shown positive effects including children engaging in more MVPA and less ST (Dobbins et al., 2013), new research suggests such interventions are not proving to be effective in reducing childhood inactivity (Love, Adams and Sluijs, 2018). Furthermore, low levels of

PA, high levels of ST, and short sleep durations are all associated with increased food intake and poor diet quality in children (Beaulieu et al., 2016, Chaput and Dutil, 2016, Thivel et al., 2019), with poor diet being a key driver of childhood obesity (Faught et al., 2016). Therefore, future school-based interventions should consider a multidimensional intervention strategy (e.g., PA, sleep, and diet) across settings (e.g., school and home) to achieve sustained effects across the whole day (Love, Adams and Sluijs, 2018, Wyatt et al., 2018).

Whilst children spend a considerable amount of their day at school, the home is considered a fundamental environment for health promotion, with parents regarded as the most important influence on children's obesogenic health behaviours (Story, Nanney and Schwartz, 2009). Home-based interventions are logistically impractical and tend to be unsustainable (Duncan et al., 2011), however using schools to communicate with children in order to encourage healthy behaviours in the home may be a feasible approach. Nevertheless, improving the health of children, including those most in need, via a school-home intervention would be challenging as parents recruited for school-based interventions tend to be the most affluent and motivated parents (Clarke et al., 2015).

Parents with low SES and low educational involvement recommend a flexible intervention approach which can be adopted at any time, and includes home activities, to improve their involvement in school-based health promotion (Donnelly et al., 2019). Within previous attempts to promote healthy lifestyles using homework components in school-based interventions, homework components assumed secondary importance to the school-based component with some studies reporting positive effects upon PA, fitness and eating habits (Christodoulos et al., 2006, Manios, Kafatos and Kafatos, 2006, Marcus et al., 2009, Kriemler et al., 2010, Eather, Morgan and Lubans, 2013, Eyre et al., 2016). Nonetheless, interventions deploying homework tasks such as AFLY5 (Kipping et al., 2014), amongst others, have demonstrated no effect upon increasing PA, reducing SB or increasing fruit and vegetable

consumption (Reilly et al., 2006, Abraham and Michie, 2008, Aadland et al., 2019).

Comparing the contributions of such homework interventions is difficult as studies tend to employ multiple approaches, some are limited by low statistical power (Tercedor et al., 2017), whilst others have used self- or proxy-measures to quantify PA (Fitzgibbon et al., 2005, Manios, Kafatos and Kafatos, 2006). Furthermore, studies deploying accelerometers use varying devices and cut-points which makes it difficult to quantify and compare the magnitude of effect (Marcus et al., 2009, Kriemler et al., 2010).

The use of novel metrics including AvAcc and IG from raw accelerometry data could enable comparisons to be drawn from studies that use different accelerometer devices (Rowlands et al., 2018). AvAcc provides a measure of the volume of activity whereas the IG describes the intensity distribution of accelerations (Rowlands et al., 2018). Together these metrics detail both the volume and intensity of activity undertaken across the monitoring period using all of the acceleration data. Both metrics could be used instead of laboratory-derived population and device-specific activity thresholds (Rowlands et al., 2018). Additionally, recently proposed activity metrics identify the minimum acceleration value above which a person's most active mins, for example 30 mins (M30_{ACC}), 60 mins (M60_{ACC}) or 2 mins (M2_{ACC}) is accumulated (Rowlands, Sherar, et al., 2019). The active mins can be accumulated in any way across the day in line with PA recommendations (Department of Health and Social Care, 2019). These novel metrics may help facilitate the pooling of accelerometer data across studies employing different devices and make use of the entire data set (Rowlands, Sherar, et al., 2019).

Healthy Homework, to the best of our knowledge, is the only effective intervention which adopts a compulsory curriculum-based approach to health homework (e.g., family walks) alongside in-class teaching (Duncan et al., 2011, 2019). Positive intervention effects for weekday PA at home, weekend PA, BMI, and fruit consumption were found.

Encouragingly, the greatest improvements in PA occurred in children from the most socioeconomically deprived schools. Whilst these results are promising, a significant limitation of this study is that PA was measured using pedometers which have been found to be inaccurate in assessing EE and are unable to distinguish time spent in activity intensities (Ndahimana and Kim, 2017). HH, a curriculum-focussed intervention, was designed based upon recommendations from parents of low SES, in order to be flexible around the lives of parents and children, requiring no equipment or access to facilities (e.g., sports centres), and was theoretically grounded in order to increase children's motivation and adherence to the intervention (Ryan and Deci, 2000a, Donnelly et al., 2019). To the best of our knowledge, this is the first school-based obesity prevention homework intervention which focusses on improving 24 h movement behaviours, including sleep, and also aims to improve diet quality in children. This study was informed by the findings outlined in Chapters 4-6 in that, the recommendations obtained from mothers who were typically uninvolved in school-based health activities and of low SES informed both the rationale and design of HH. Based on these recommendations, home-based tasks were designed to allow parents to be involved without attending the school and parent and child joint activities were built into the HH programme to promote parent involvement in children's school-based health activities. Furthermore, findings from Chapter 5 observed that parent and child MVPA were only associated on weekend days, typically whilst they were together. Therefore, the influence parents have on children's activity may only directly exist when engaging in joint activities. Findings from both Chapters 5 and 6 however found significant relationships between parent BMI and child BMI, including an indirect effect of SES on child BMI via their parents. Parent BMI was also found to influence boys inactive time in Chapter 6. In line with the curriculum and such findings, a dietary component, in addition to PA tasks, were incorporated into HH activities as the previous findings from Chapters 5 and 6 suggest that

diet may be a more influential factor on children's weight when compared with PA. The aim of this study was two-fold: (1) explore the feasibility of HH from qualitative investigations with teachers and pupils and (2) examine preliminary effects of the HH pilot intervention on children's 24 h activity patterns and dietary behaviours.

7.2 Methods

7.2.1 Participants and Recruitment

A convenience sample of four primary schools from Lanarkshire, Scotland, who had been involved in previous studies coordinated by the primary investigator, were recruited. Once ethical approval from the University Ethics Committee was granted, the schools were approached to discuss their involvement in the study, with the Head teacher (see appendices 3A and 3B) and classroom teachers (see appendices 3C and 3D) receiving informed consent paperwork. One class per school was selected by the Head teacher based on the pupils ages (9-12 years old), and informed consent paperwork was issued to each child (see Appendices 3E and 3F) in the four classes ($n = 128$; 69 girls) and their parent (see Appendices 3G and 3H). Families also received additional paperwork regarding device information (see Appendix 3I). Due to a low return-rate of consent from one school class, an additional class from this school was selected by the Head teacher and additional informed consent paperwork ($n = 30$) was issued. The reason for the low-return rate from one school was unclear. In total, 158 children across 5 classrooms were provided with informed consent paperwork. The flow of pupil participants throughout the study can be found in The CONSORT Flow diagram (see Figure 7-1). Schools ($n = 4$) were randomised into intervention ($n = 3$) and a control ($n = 2$) classroom groups. As such, teachers within their respective classrooms were allocated to the intervention ($n = 3$) and control ($n = 2$) arms of the study. Schools were blinded to this information until pre-intervention measures were collected.

7.2.2 Pilot programme

The HH pilot intervention included homework activities which aimed to improve activity-related behaviours over the whole day (i.e., movement, sleep, yoga, dance, walking, fitness, games and competitions) and key dietary-related components (e.g., fruit and vegetables, soft drinks, sugars, snacking, energy in foods, food from around the world and kitchen hygiene) in the form of weekly workbooks (see Appendices 3J and 3K for examples). HH PA tasks were decided upon based on The WHO recommendations for activity in children aged 5-17 years which suggest that most of children's daily activity should be aerobic, and vigorous-intensity activities should be incorporated including activities which strengthen muscle and bone at least 3 times per week (World Health Organization, 2018a).

Figure 7-1 CONSORT flow diagram of the recruitment, adherence and analysis process of pupils.

Additionally, 24 h movement guidelines were also implemented into the design of HH tasks, in that children should aim to break-up time spent sedentary by moving, with recreational ST limited to no more than 2 h, and that children would aim to sustain adequate sleep durations of between 9-11 h per night, maintaining consistent bed and wake times (Tremblay et al., 2016). HH activities were then mapped in-line with the Scottish Curriculum for Excellence (CfE) for primary school children, taking into consideration their four developmental capacities: (1) successful learners, (2) confident individuals, (3) responsible citizens and (4) effective contributors (see Table 7-1). The Experiences and Outcomes of the HH intervention embody the attributes and capabilities of the four capacities, with the experiences relating to the learning experience and development of these capacities, and the outcome referring to what is to be achieved. The CfE does not provide explicit recommendations for the choice of activities, but rather a focus on mental, emotional, social and physical wellbeing which widens knowledge about choices in life and the costs and benefits attached. Therefore, the development of the HH intervention was informed from the SDT (Deci and Ryan, 1985) which aimed to develop children's motivation to lead healthier lifestyles by meeting their three basic psychological needs: autonomy, competence and relatedness (See Table 7-2). Satisfying children's basic psychological needs has been shown to be predictive of PA participation and general positive behaviours associated with wellbeing (Breslin et al., 2017).

It has been suggested that the limited effects of previous school-based interventions could be attributed to the use of 'top-down' approaches whereby researchers drive intervention design with limited input from school stakeholders (Rütten et al., 2019). The WHO has indicated that actions to prevent childhood obesity should be implemented across multiple settings and incorporate a wide range of stakeholders (World Health Organization, 2012). As such, the HH intervention was developed under the guidance of local authority primary school Head teachers ($n = 4$).

Table 7-1 HH provisional 8-week plan with curriculum underpinning.

Week	Activity	CfE Experiences and Outcomes
1	Yoga / Fruit & Vegetables	Cooperation and competition HWB 2-23a: While working and learning with others, I improve my range of skills, demonstrate tactics and achieve identified goals.
2	Fun Fitness/ Energy in foods	Evaluating and appreciating HWB 2-24a: By reflecting on my own and others' work and evaluating it against shared criteria, I can recognise improvement and achievement and use this to progress further Movement skills, competencies and concepts HWB 2-22a: I practise, consolidate and refine my skills to improve my performance. I am developing and sustaining my levels of fitness.
3	Dance / Soft Drinks	Physical activity and sport HWB 2-25a: I am experiencing enjoyment and achievement on a daily basis by taking part in different kinds of energetic physical activities of my choosing, including sport and opportunities for outdoor learning, available at my place of learning and in the wider community. Physical activity and sport HWB 2-26a: I have investigated the role of sport and the opportunities it may offer me. I am able to access opportunities for participation in sport and the development of my performance in my place of learning and beyond. Social wellbeing HWB 2-11a: I make full use of and value the opportunities I am given to improve and manage my learning and, in turn, I can help to encourage learning and confidence in others.
4	Walking / Snacks	Food and the consumer HWB 2-37a: I can understand how advertising and the media are used to influence consumers.
5	Games/ Sugar	Food and the consumer HWB 2-36a: By investigating food labelling systems, I can begin to understand how to use them to make healthy food choices. Physical activity and sport HWB 2-25a: I am experiencing enjoyment and achievement on a daily basis by taking part in different kinds of energetic physical activities of my choosing, including sport and opportunities for outdoor learning, available at my place of learning and in the wider community.
6	Competition/ Cooking & kitchen hygiene	Cooperation and competition HWB 2-23a: While working and learning with others, I improve my range of skills, demonstrate tactics and achieve identified goals.
7	Movement/ Food from around the world	Food and the consumer: HWB 2-34a: Through exploration and discussion, I can understand that food practices and preferences are influenced by factors such as food sources, finance, culture and religion.
8	All together now!	Physical activity and health HWB 2-27a: I can explain why I need to be active on a daily basis to maintain good health and try to achieve a good balance of sleep, rest and physical activity. Physical activity and health HWB 2-28a: I can explain the links between the energy I use while being physically active, the food I eat, and my HWB

Table 7-2 HH provisional 8-week plan with theoretical underpinning.

Week	Activity	Monday	Wednesday	Friday
1	Yoga / Fruit & Vegetables HWB 2-23a	Theory: SDT – Autonomy and relatedness Goal: Provide parents and children with the opportunity to invent a short game together which allows them to stretch off (understanding the importance of this prior to activity) and pick Yoga poses to try. This session aims to intrinsically motivate the pupils by involving their parent, providing a game situation, and allowing them to choose poses.	Theory: SDT – Autonomy, relatedness and competence Goal: For parents and children to challenge themselves to execute the movement effectively, and possibly increase the intensity to a Yoga pose of their choice. This session aims to align with the pupil and parents integrated regulation by promoting participation in the activity at a time which fits into their daily routine/lifestyle.	Theory: SDT – Autonomy and relatedness Goal: Increase identified regulation in pupils and parents by providing them with the opportunity to learn about some of the benefits of participating in activities to reduce anxiety and help with sleep.
2	Fun Fitness/ Energy in foods HWB 2-24a HWB 2-22a	Theory: SDT – Autonomy Goal: Encourage children to participate in a fitness session by making it fun and relevant to what they are doing in class. This session aims to intrinsically motivate the pupils by encouraging them to pick out words and note them down and involving their parents. Through this we aimed to have the children and parents enjoy the tasks, and aim to relate them back to the EatWell Guide.	Theory: SDT – Autonomy, relatedness and competence Goal: This session aims to align with the pupil and parents integrated regulation by promoting participation in the activity at a time which fits into their daily routine/lifestyle – and encourages habitual activity by proving prompts to continue the activities on days which are not prescribed by the sessions and refer to the EatWell Guide for inspiration of healthy choices.	Theory: SDT – Autonomy, relatedness and competence Goal: This session continues with the themes of enjoyment. It incorporates aspects from session 1 and 2 this week, by furthering a competitive element and encouraging activity promotion over the weekend. Through encouraging enjoyment, these sessions ultimately aim to instil intrinsic motivation in both the parents and pupils to encourage habitual physical activity.
3	Dance / Soft Drinks HWB 2-25a HWB 2-26a HWB 2-11a	Theory: SDT – Autonomy Goal: This session aims to encourage integrated regulation in both the parents and children by providing them with information on the need for activity and healthy nutrition which can easily be instilled into their lifestyles following simple everyday steps.	Theory: Autonomy and relatedness. Goal: This session aims to offer the intervention a wider family context and allows children and parents to choose some dances they feel they may enjoy, promoting internal motivation.	Theory: Autonomy, relatedness and competence. Goal: This session encourages the family to work together to learn dances the parents will not be familiar with. This also allows the children to feel competent in their tasks.
4	Walking / Snacks HWB 2-37a	Theory: SDT – Relatedness Goal: The aim of this session was to focus on increasing identified regulation in pupils and parents by providing them with the opportunity to learn about some of the benefits walking and opting for healthier snack options as opposed to high-sugar snacks.	Theory: SDT – Autonomy Goal: This session aims to encourage integrated regulation in both the parents and children by providing them with options to increase their activity which can easily be instilled into their lifestyles following simple everyday steps.	Theory: SDT - Competence Goal: This session promotes internal regulation by not only highlighting the simple steps pupils can take to be more active, but also the simple steps families can take to make healthier choices overall.
5	Games/ Sugar HWB 2-36a HWB 2-25a	Theory: SDT – Relatedness Goal: The aim of this session is to encourage Identified regulation in the pupils and parents by emphasizing the importance of splitting up sitting time and providing ways to do so.	Theory: SDT – Autonomy and competence Goal: This session focuses on the participant’s intrinsic motivation by making a day-to-day tasks fun and a way to break up sitting time.	Theory: SDT – Autonomy and relatedness Goal: The aim of these sessions work on participants integrated regulation allowing them to see the values and need of unstructured daily activity and how they can integrating it into their lifestyle.
6	Competition/ Cooking & kitchen hygiene HWV 2-33a HWB 2-36a	Theory: SDT – Autonomy, competence and relatedness Goal: This session focuses on the participant’s intrinsic motivation by splitting up sitting time or screen time with fun and exciting activities.	Theory: SDT – Relatedness and competence Goal: The aim of this session is to encourage identified regulation in the participants by emphasizing the importance of splitting up sitting time and providing ways to do so.	Theory: SDT – Autonomy, competence and relatedness Goal: The aim of these sessions work on participants integrated regulation allowing them to see the values and need of keeping active throughout the day and ways of encouraging the whole family/friends to do so also.
7	Movement/ Food from around the world HWB 2-34a	Theory: SDT – Autonomy and relatedness Goal: Focus on participants identified regulation by providing knowledge of the importance of the sleep and activity.	Theory: SDT – Autonomy, competence and relatedness Goal: This sessions aims to increase intrinsic motivation by uses games as a fun way to stay active and brings in fun aspects from week 1.	Theory: SDT – Autonomy, competence and relatedness Goal: The session continues working on the intrinsic motivation of parents to encourage more fun activity over the weekend and with as many people as possible.
8	All together now! HWB 2-27a HWB 2-28a	Theory: SDT – Autonomy and relatedness Goal: Increasing identified regulation by increasing individual’s knowledge of the importance of the activity – especially when outdoors.	Theory: SDT – Competence and relatedness Goal: Increasing intrinsic motivation by incorporating fun aspects from Week 2 that they feel competent in.	Theory: SDT – Autonomy, competence and relatedness Goal: Zoning in on integrated regulation – seeing the values and need of the activity and integrating it into your lifestyle (trying to encourage this after the intervention itself ends).

From these provisional HH activities, the Head teachers chose their preferred six weeks during a meeting with the lead researcher and additional classroom teachers. The HH intervention was also informed by recommendations from parents of low SES, ensuring that home-based joint parent and child activities can be implemented with flexibility and no financial burden on families, and in turn, involving families in health curriculum.

HH workbooks were provided to children on a Monday, Wednesday, and Friday to encourage habitual involvement in the activities over an 8-week period, which included 2 Easter holiday weeks. Additional activities and health promotion reminders were provided in the workbooks for the subsequent days in which the child did not receive HH (e.g., weekends). Parents were required to sign off each activity that they completed with their child in the parent sign off box located at the bottom of each page within the HH workbook. The teachers were provided with a logbook to record the specific days in which the children completed HH activities to measure the fidelity of HH based on parental signatures. If the child completed their weekly HH activities, they would receive a happy face sticker on their HH workbook at the end of each week. Happy face stickers were distributed as a small reward for the completion of HH activities each week to encourage pupils to complete their homework. Previous research has shown that the use of small rewards encourage adherence and is thought upon favourably by parents (Buchan, Donnelly, et al., 2019, Donnelly et al., 2019).

7.2.3 Quantitative Enquiry

7.2.3.1 *Anthropometrics.*

At school, mass was measured barefoot to the nearest 0.1kg with an electronic scale (Seca Digital Scales, Seca Ltd, Birmingham, UK) whilst stature was measured barefoot to the nearest 0.1cm using a portable stadiometer (Seca Stadiometer, Seca Ltd, Birmingham, UK) in accordance with standard procedures (Cole, Freeman and Preece, 1995). BMI was then

calculated as the mass in kilograms divided by the square of the stature in meters. Thereafter, the BMI z-score was determined and children were classified as healthy weight (BMI z-score <1.04 , below the 85th percentile) or overweight/obese (BMI z-score ≥ 1.04 , above the 85th percentile) relative to the UK 1990 BMI population reference data (Cole, Freeman and Preece, 1995) and using software provided by the Child Growth Foundation (Pan and Cole, 2010).

7.2.3.2 *ActiGraph GT3X+*.

Each child was provided with an ActiGraph GT3X+ (ActiGraph, LLC, Pensacola, FL, USA) accelerometer and instructed to wear the device 24 h per day for 7 days, except during any water-based activities, on the non-dominant wrist (confirmed by the child). Written instructions for care and placement of the monitors were provided to parents. All devices were synchronised with Greenwich Mean Time and initialized to capture data at 80Hz prior to distribution.

7.2.3.2.1 *ActiGraph GT3X+ data processing.*

Accelerometer data were downloaded using ActiLife v6.13.3 (ActiGraph, Pensacola, FL, USA) and saved in raw format as gt3x files. The gt3x files were subsequently converted to time-stamp free .csv files which were exported into R (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria, <https://cran.r-project.org/>) and processed using the GGIR package v1.9-2. GGIR removed abnormally high values, detected non-wear time (van Hees et al., 2013b) and auto-calibrated the raw accelerometer signals using local gravity as a reference (van Hees et al., 2014). Finally, GGIR calculated Euclidean Norm Minus One (ENMO) over 5 sec epochs expressed in mg. Participant files were removed from further analysis if files had a post-calibration error greater than 0.01 g or there were less than 3 days (including 1 weekend day) of valid wear (defined as ≥ 16 h per day). The following activity outcomes reported included: AvAcc across the monitoring period (mg), the IG, M60, M30,

M2, time accumulated in MVPA and time spent inactive. Time spent in MVPA was defined as the time accumulated above an acceleration of 201 mg (Hildebrand, van Hees, Hansen, & Ekelund, 2014) whereas time spent inactive was defined as time accumulated below 50 mg (Rowlands et al., 2018).

7.2.3.3 *ActivPAL4™*.

The *ActivPAL4™* micro (PAL Technologies Ltd., Glasgow, UK), was used to quantify SB's including sitting time, standing time, stepping time, MVPA stepping time, sit-to-stand transitions, sitting ≤ 30 mins, sitting ≤ 60 mins and sitting > 60 mins during free-living. This device has previously been shown to be a valid measure of body posture and for quantifying SB (Aminian and Hinckson, 2012). The *ActivPAL4™* was placed in a small flexible nitrile sleeve to waterproof the device and was attached to the children's right thigh using dressing. Children were instructed to wear the device for 24 h per day across a 7-day period.

7.2.3.3.1 *ActivPAL4™* data processing.

Raw *ActivPAL4™* data were processed using Processing PAL software (Version 1.3) using the Events.csv files from the *ActivPAL4™*. To quantify sleep and non-wear time the default setting in Processing PAL was used which uses an algorithm developed and validated to detect sleep and non-wear for continuous (24 h) wear protocols (Winkler et al., 2016). Initially, the algorithm finds prolonged periods that are most likely to be sleep or non-wear. Sleep/non-wear bouts were identified as the longest bout per 24 h period (from noon-to-noon each day) that lasts ≥ 2 h, or any very long bouts lasting ≥ 5 h. As sleep can register as multiple periods of sitting/lying interspersed with genuine or erroneously detected posture changes and stepping, the algorithm then examines surrounding bouts and determines whether they are more likely to be additional sleep/non-wear (i.e., limited movement) or waking wear (i.e., more movement). Bouts were 'surrounding' if any portion was within a

15 min window before or after a sleep/non-wear bout. All bouts in the sleep window were classed as sleep/non-wear when the window contains any of these: a sitting/lying or standing bout that is long (≥ 2 h), or moderately long (≥ 30 min) with very few (≤ 20) steps in between a sleeping/non-wear bout or, posture changes without intervening steps. The algorithm repeats this step until no more sleep/non-wear is detected. Data were included in the analyses if the child provided a minimum of 3 valid days of recording which included 1 weekend day. Valid days were defined as a day with ≥ 10 h of wear time during identified waking h's (Tudor-Locke et al., 2015).

7.2.3.4 *DILQ*

The DILQ has been validated in 7-9 year old children (Edmunds and Ziebland, 2002), and has been used in 6-11 year old children. The 23-item DILQ uses words and pictures to encourage the child to recall and describe a range of activities from the previous day (24 h recall method), including everything they had to eat and drink (Edmunds and Ziebland, 2002) (see Appendix 3L). Write and draw questions regarding what the child had to eat are embedded within other items that take the child through a range of daily activities, providing context which helps the child to recall what they ate the day before (Edmunds and Ziebland, 2002). For analyses, a point was awarded for each fruit and vegetable recalled by the child as part of their diet the previous day and the number of daily servings of fruit and vegetables were totalled; a point was awarded for each fruit and vegetable recalled by the child as part of their diet the previous day.

7.2.3.5 *ST Questionnaire*.

ST can take different forms including: TV, video games, computer and mobile device (Hale and Guan, 2015), therefore children were asked to report how many h's they engaged in ST on weekdays (before school and after school) and weekend days (morning and evening) for mobile phone/tablet use, TV, and playing computer/video games which did not require

them to be active (i.e., sitting down) (see Appendix 3M). Self-reported methods for quantifying ST have shown acceptable reliability and validity in children (Hardy et al., 2013). Children's average self-reported ST for 'weekday' was multiplied by 5, and 'weekend' ST was multiplied by 2 to create a weekday and weekend ST outcome and added together to calculate overall weekly ST.

7.2.3.6 Family Involvement Questionnaire.

The 46-item FIQ-E version (Manz, Fantuzzo and Power, 2004) is a validated multidimensional self-report scale measuring the frequency of family involvement in education (Semke et al., 2010). The FIQ-E's items are rated on a 4-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (rarely occurs) to 4 (always occurs), and examines three distinct factors of parent involvement: (1) home-school communication (e.g., talk to teacher about classroom rules), (2) home-based learning (e.g., read with child), and (3) school-based involvement (e.g., volunteer in the classroom). For the purposes of the current study, only items from the home-based learning subscale (e.g., help with homework, read with child, limit TV, etc.) were completed by parents to obtain demographic information surrounding the involvement of parents who were participating in HH activities (see Appendix 3N). The FIQ-E has demonstrated good factorial fit according to conventional criteria and excellent internal consistency ($\alpha = .91-84$) (71).

7.2.3.7 SES

Home postcodes were obtained from each family involved in the study in order to calculate the SES of children via the SIMD online calculator (Scottish Government, 2016b). This demographic outcome was used in subsequent analyses as a covariate. The SIMD identifies areas of deprivation across Scotland in a consistent way, ranking small areas from most deprived (ranked 1) to least deprived (ranked 6,976) which is then converted into a relative decile score between 1 and 10 (1 being the most deprived areas and 10 being the least

deprived areas). Scores for each area are calculated based on objective indicators across 6 domains: (1) residents' income, (2) employment, (3) housing, (4) health education, (5) skills and training, and (6) geographic access to services and telecommunications. SIMD scores for all locations in Scotland were publicly available at the time of the research.

7.2.4 Qualitative Enquiry.

In order to explore the experiences of teachers involved in the HH intervention and the feasibility of HH, the teachers who delivered HH ($n = 3$) participated in individual interviews. Furthermore, to explore the experiences of pupils who participated in the HH intervention, 5 pupils from each of the 3 intervention arm classes ($n = 15$) were randomly selected by the researcher and took part in WDST groups. All interviews were conducted by the primary investigator who had previous experience collecting qualitative data of a similar nature over a four-year period. All interviews were recorded using a digital recorder and transcribed verbatim.

7.2.4.1 *Teacher participation.*

Individual interviews were conducted with the teachers who delivered HH ($n = 3$), which were arranged at their convenience. A semi-structured interview guide with open-ended questions were used to ensure consistency across interviews. The interview guide (see Appendix 3O) covered the following topics: implementation of general homework and previous HWB homework, completion of HH tasks, perceptions of HH tasks and recommendations to improve HH. Prior to data collection, the interview guide was assessed and discussed between the primary investigator and the director of studies, in which collective consensus was agreed that the guide was suitable. The interviews took place in a private area of the school and lasted 25.59 ± 5.60 min. All three teachers within the two intervention schools handed out all eight weeks of HH (6 curriculum-time weeks and 2 Easter holiday weeks). Given the sensitivity of observing teacher practice within the classroom, it

was not feasible to observe whether the HH workbooks were being handed out by the teachers. Therefore, teachers were asked to complete fidelity forms, which also detailed pupil's completion of HH.

7.2.4.2 WDST Groups.

Prior to data collection, the WDST group interview guide was assessed and discussed between the primary investigator and the director of studies, in which collective consensus was agreed that the guide was age appropriate, aligned with SDT outcomes and therefore supported the study aims (see Appendix 3P). The WDST method provides children with alternative ways of expression and enables a deeper exploration of children's thoughts and perceptions by not limiting children to verbal communication (Noonan, Boddy, Fairclough, et al., 2016). WDST group interviews were informed by Noonan and colleagues procedures practical checklist (Noonan, Boddy, Fairclough, et al., 2016). At the beginning of WDST interview, children were asked to introduce themselves and share their favourite topic to learn in class as an ice breaker task. This was used to provide children with the opportunity to experience talking aloud to the group, and to establish an environment in which sharing and listening was valued (Gibson, 2012). Children were then provided with post-it note[©] paper and a pencil and asked to write down '5 words to best describe PA to someone else'. Children were then asked to explain the meaning of their responses and place their responses post-it notes[©] on to the board and discuss these as a group. Following this, children were asked to draw an environment where they were most likely to participate in PA. By doing this, children could express their perceptions of PA visually, and subsequently, the research team could determine whether HH activities were included in such drawings. The drawing took the focus away from direct questioning and consensus, to that of a more child-centred approach that better allowed for the lived experience to be shared (Horstman et al., 2008). During the write and draw activity the primary investigator separately engaged children in informal

conversations to allow them to articulate what they were drawing and why. Once children had completed their drawings the WDST group continued with more detailed open-ended questioning concerning their experiences of HH and the satisfaction of their three basic psychological needs: relatedness, autonomy, and competence. These questions aimed to elicit from children whether HH satisfied their basic psychological needs as intended. By adopting this interactive and dual method approach (i.e., WDST), we hoped to prompt detailed perceptions of children's PA and HH that may not have been identified if singular methods based approaches (e.g., focus groups) has been used (Dockett and Perry, 2005). Each WDST group ($n = 3$) consisted of 5 children from the same school, selected randomly from the consenting children by the primary investigator. The interviews took place in a quiet area in the school where the pupils could be overlooked but could not be overheard and lasted on average 40.84 ± 10.43 min.

7.2.5 Data Analysis

7.2.5.1 Quantitative Data.

All analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics v.23 (IBM, Armock, NY). Independent sample t tests and one-way ANCOVA's (when two or more independent groups were present) examined the differences in means and adjusted means including: BMI z-score, AvAcc, IG, MVPA, M60, M30, M2, sitting time, standing time, stepping time, MVPA stepping time, number of sit-to-stand transitions, sitting (≤ 30 mins), sitting (≤ 60 mins), sitting (>60 mins), sleep duration, ST, and total fruit and vegetable consumption score between intervention and control groups at baseline and post-intervention time points. Statistical significance was set at 0.05. The 95% CI's for the mean differences for each group are presented with the partial eta squared values (η_p^2) reported as effect size estimates. In accordance with Green and colleagues (Green, Salkind and Jones, 1996) , 0.01, 0.06 and 0.14 were interpreted as small, medium and large effect sizes, respectively. The assumptions for t -

tests include normality of the dependent variable and homogeneity of variance (i.e., measured using Levene's tests of equality of variance). These assumptions were met. The assumptions associated with the ANOVA's and ANCOVA's include: the dependent variable is continuous, the independent variables include two or more groups, independence of groups, and the dependent variable is normally distributed. Whilst there were some violations of normality, due to the nature of the data, it was important not to manipulate the data and thus, keep the data as collected to reflect the pairing of parent-child dyad data. Additionally, ANOVA's and ANCOVA's are robust to violations of normality (Blanca et al., 2017).

7.2.5.2 Qualitative Data.

Deductive-inductive thematic analysis allowed for themes to be identified and extracted from the teacher and child qualitative data driven by the research aims, as described by Braun and Clarke (Braun and Clarke, 2006). To ensure credibility in the analyses, the director of studies, who was not present during data collection, independently reviewed the data at several stages of the analyses.

7.2.5.2.1 *Individual interviews.*

Thematic analysis was used in order to systematically represent teacher's experiences of the HH pilot programme (Braun and Clarke, 2006). We followed the 6 steps of thematic analyses which include: (1) Familiarisation with the data, (2) Generating initial codes, (3) Searching for themes, (4) Reviewing themes, (5) Defining and naming themes, and (6) Producing the report (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The primary investigator conducted the interviews and then listened to the audio files of the interviews and transcribed these. In doing so, the primary investigator became intimately familiar with the data. In generating initial codes, it is important to consider the research aims as coding will depend on whether the themes are data- or theory-driven (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Teacher interviews were conducted in order to answer specific questions regarding the HH pilot programme including

teacher perspectives of implementing HH, their preferred weeks, and recommendations to improve HH. As such, when analysing teacher data, a deductive approach was applied to our thematic analysis in order to explore teacher perceptions of HH, however the researcher was open to additional emergent themes. Following this, commonalities were sought and the themes generated. A review of these themes was then conducted and from this, themes were pooled together and defined. This process was conducted between the primary investigator and the director of studies. Upon agreement of the final themes, such themes were produced as detailed in our results.

7.2.5.2.2 WDST groups.

This approach generated three separate sources of data: (1) a frequency count (show activity), (2) visual data (write and draw activity) and (3) verbatim data (tell activity and children's write and draw narratives). One stage did not inform the next, rather a mixed analysis approach was taken. For the 'show' data, children's responses were totalled. Narratives were transcribed verbatim, classified as a written 'report', and subsequently attached to each individual drawing. 'Tell' data was analysed through an inductive-deductive process which was framed by the three basic psychological needs as per SDT, using these as a thematic framework, with researchers also open to emergent themes surrounding HH. The reports and drawings were then used in combination to categorise 'marks' on paper in relation to specific themes. For example, a drawing containing a child participating in a game of football with friends would require marks for more than 1 theme (both activity and social interaction). Data from these sessions included the nature of the children's PA, the active ingredients associated with their PA and social interactions facilitated due to their engagement in PA. The three data sources were triangulated and pooled together, in which thematic analysis was conducted, drawing and narratives presented, and pen profile analysis conducted. This method has been shown as an effective way of presenting data to researchers

that have an affinity with both quantitative and qualitative enquiry (Ridgers, Knowles and Sayers, 2012, Knowles et al., 2013).

7.3 Results

All four schools contacted agreed to participate. A total of five classrooms and their classroom teachers and pupils were recruited for this study. From the 158 children recruited for this study, 71 children ($n = 31$ girls) and their parent returned consent documents, and by being present on the day of pre-testing, 68 children and their parent (42.41%) were included in the study. Of the parents who completed FIQ-E ($n = 69$), 58% ($n = 40$) were classified as 'involved' and 42% ($n = 29$) were classified as 'less involved' using the median split of the FIQ-E scores. A significant difference between the intervention and control groups regarding parent involvement ($p < 0.05$) was observed. In the intervention group, the average parent involvement score was 2.80 ± 0.35 ($n = 38$), whereas for the control group, the average FIQ-E score was 3.04 ± 0.40 ($n = 30$) meaning that families within the control group were more involved in home-based learning. The average SIMD score of the families recruited to this study was 5.38 ± 2.76 . No significant differences were observed for SIMD when comparing children involved in the control and intervention groups. Analyses was undertaken to split families into low SIMD based on residing in an area with a SIMD decile score of ≤ 2 ($n = 16$; 23%) and high SIMD based on residing in an area with a SIMD decile score of ≥ 3 ($n = 55$; 78%) groups. Of the children who participated in this study, 28 (41%) met the wear-time criteria of a minimum of 3 days (including 1 weekend day) of valid wear (defined as ≥ 16 h of wear-time per day) for ActiGraph devices ($n = 18$ intervention arm). Furthermore, 49 (72%) met the wear-time criteria of a minimum of 3 days of recording (including 1 weekend day) of valid days (defined as a day with ≥ 10 h of wear-time during identified waking h's) for ActivPAL4™ devices ($n = 28$ intervention arm) at baseline. The descriptive characteristics of the study sample at baseline and post-intervention are shown in Table 7-3.

Table 7-3 Descriptive characteristics for anthropometric, ActiGraph, ActivPAL and questionnaire data of children' by arm group at baseline and post-measure.

Variable	<u>Intervention</u>		<u>Control</u>	
	Baseline Mean \pm SD (<i>n</i>)	Post-Measure Mean \pm SD (<i>n</i>)	Baseline Mean \pm SD (<i>n</i>)	Post-Measure Mean \pm SD (<i>n</i>)
Anthropometrics				
BMI (kg/m ²)	18.13 \pm 3.80 (38)	18.17 \pm 3.95 (36)	18.89 \pm 3.02 (30)	18.78 \pm 3.10 (27)
Stature (cm)	143.84 \pm 9.47 (38)	145.74 \pm 9.42 (36)	141.91 \pm 6.25 (30)	142.73 \pm 6.09 (27)
Mass (kg)	37.81 \pm 10.05 (38)	38.89 \pm 10.30 (36)	38.15 \pm 7.59 (30)	38.48 \pm 8.23 (27)
ActiGraph				
Sedentary time (min.d ⁻¹)	1188.99 \pm 35.77 (18)	1178.77 \pm 44.14 (18)	1163.97 \pm 47.57 (10)	1154.68 \pm 57.99 (10)
AvAcc (mg)	41.04 \pm 10.61 (18)	42.47 \pm 13.34 (18)	44.19 \pm 9.54(10)	43.35 \pm 13.38 (10)
IG	-1.98 \pm 0.13 (18)	-1.98 \pm 0.16 (18)	-1.97 \pm 0.13 (10)	-2.07 \pm 0.14 (10)
MVPA (min.d ⁻¹)	130.96 \pm 29.59 (18)	137.44 \pm 35.73 (18)	147.31 \pm 30.07 (10)	149.96 \pm 48.13 (10)
M60 (mg)	196.79 \pm 68.82 (18)	201.78 \pm 89.12 (18)	205.55 \pm 43.65 (10)	202.65 \pm 69.27 (10)
M30 (mg)	324.74 \pm 120.92 (18)	335.42 \pm 150.97 (18)	337.61 \pm 94.14 (10)	325.32 \pm 142.21 (10)
M2 (mg)	1401.65 \pm 412.21 (18)	1443.73 \pm 484.86 (18)	1450.99 \pm 361.25 (10)	1247.05 \pm 455.29 (10)
ActivPAL				
Valid days	6.61 \pm 0.50 (28)	7.91 \pm 1.27 (22)	6.62 \pm 2.09 (21)	7.36 \pm 1.96 (11)
Waking time (h's/day)	13.81 \pm 0.82 (28)	13.95 \pm 1.05 (22)	13.86 \pm 0.91 (21)	13.98 \pm 0.56 (11)
Sitting time (h's/day)	9.08 \pm 0.82 (28)	8.67 \pm 1.05 (22)	8.68 \pm 0.88(21)	8.59 \pm 0.78 (11)
Standing time (h's/day)	2.56 \pm 0.55 (28)	2.79 \pm 0.59 (22)	2.83 \pm 0.65(21)	2.99 \pm 0.70 (11)
Stepping time (h's/day)	2.17 \pm 0.46 (28)	2.49 \pm 0.49 (22)	2.35 \pm 0.60 (21)	2.40 \pm 0.46 (11)
MVPA Stepping time (h's/day)	1.11 \pm 0.26 (28)	1.30 \pm 0.30 (22)	1.16 \pm 0.34 (21)	1.22 \pm 0.26 (11)
Sit-to-stand transitions	86.82 \pm 16.89 (28)	81.55 \pm 13.76 (22)	86.57 \pm 20.91 (21)	93.00 \pm 13.89 (11)
Sit 0-30 mins (h's/day)	5.74 \pm 0.81 (28)	5.61 \pm 0.55 (22)	5.83 \pm 0.68 (21)	6.11 \pm 0.51 (11)
Sit 30-60 mins (h's/day)	2.08 \pm 0.67(28)	1.83 \pm 0.70 (22)	1.70 \pm 0.49 (21)	1.63 \pm 0.45 (11)
Sit 60 mins plus (h's/day)	1.26 \pm 0.68(28)	1.22 \pm 0.60 (22)	1.14 \pm 0.85 (21)	0.85 \pm 0.53 (11)
Sleep Duration (h's/day)	10.01 \pm 0.67 (28)	10.03 \pm 0.59 (20)	10.13 \pm 0.77(20)	9.86 \pm 0.43 (11)
Questionnaires				
Weekly ST (h's.min)	38.19 \pm 32.99 (36)	34.51 \pm 20.36 (33)	28.26 \pm 18:97 (29)	31.54 \pm 17.48 (27)
Fruit and vegetable consumption	1.54 \pm 1.46 (37)	1.50 \pm 1.50 (34)	2.43 \pm 3.63 (30)	1.30 \pm 1.54 (27)

Note. Min.d⁻¹ = mins per day

7.3.1 Changes in outcome measures

Differences found between the control group and intervention groups with between group differences always compared to the control group can be found in Table 7-4. Objective observations found significant intervention effects on PA including: stepping time and MVPA stepping time as well as less time (0-30mins) sitting when compared to the control group. Interestingly, a positive intervention effect for sleep duration was approaching significance ($p = 0.05$). Significant improvements were observed for the control group including IG and sit-to-stand transitions. The effect size for each outcome was large (≥ 0.14).

7.3.2 Pupils perceptions of their PA

Pupils were asked to provide general information surrounding their PA through the Write and Draw activity in order to explore whether HH was perceived to be embedded in their perceptions of PA. Data from these sessions included the nature of their PA, the active ingredients associated with their PA and social interactions facilitated due to their engagement in PA (see Figure 7-2). From their drawings, they discussed the nature of their PA being either structured such as attending clubs, or unstructured such as playing in their garden (see Appendices 3Q and 3R for examples). HH was not highlighted as an environment in which they are likely to engage in PA within their drawings. Pupils discussed various active ingredients associated with their participation in PA including enjoyment and choosing their favourite activity as well as limiting technology. During the write and draw activity, pupils discussed numerous social interactions with key individuals as a result of their participation in PA including their siblings, coach and team mates.

Table 7-4 Changes in outcome measures from baseline to post-intervention in the control and intervention groups.

Variable	Adjusted CI Difference (95% CI)	Effect size Partial eta squared
Anthropometrics		
BMI-z score	0.02	0.004
ActiGraph		
Sedentary time (min.d ⁻¹)	-11.62 (-50.74, 27.50)	0.02
AvAcc (mg)	-1.76 (-10.30, 6.77)	0.007
IG	-0.11 (-0.20, -0.02)	0.19
MVPA (min.d ⁻¹)	1.07 (-28.70, 30.85)	0.000
M60 (mg)	-8.13 (-52.85, 36.60)	0.006
M30 (mg)	-21.72 (-111.07, 87.62)	0.010
M2 (mg)	-236.06 (-530.60, 58.48)	0.10
ActivPAL		
Sitting time (h's/day)	0.29 (-0.46, 1.03)	0.02
Standing time (h's/day)	-0.07 (-0.47, 0.33)	0.004
Stepping time (h's/day)	-0.38 (-0.63, -0.13)*	0.25
MVPA Stepping time (h's/day)	-0.22 (-0.37, -0.07)*	0.24
Sit-to-stand transitions	10.76 (2.60, 18.91)	0.20
Sit 0-30 mins (h's/day)	0.50 (0.09, 0.91)	0.17
Sit 30-60 mins (h's/day)	-0.11 (-0.47, 0.26)**	0.01
Sit 60 mins plus (h's/day)	-0.30 (-0.76, 0.16)	0.06
Sleep Duration (h's/day)	-0.33 (-0.66, 0.00)**	0.13
Questionnaires		
Weekly ST (h's.min)	-1.21 (-11.27, 8.85)	0.001
Fruit and vegetable consumption	-0.54 (-1.19, 0.12)	0.04

Note. Min.d⁻¹ = mins per day; * = SIMD as covariate; ** = baseline BMI z-score as covariate; bold indicates significance

Figure 7-2 Pen profile of the Write and Draw data

7.3.3 HH fidelity and acceptability

We asked teachers to complete HH fidelity forms during the eight weeks of the intervention which detailed pupil completion of the tasks (see Table 7-5). Whilst two of these teachers from one school completed fidelity forms for their classes in full, the third teacher forgot to do so from week two and thereon, however based on our qualitative data, we are confident that all three teachers provided the full 8 weeks of HH intervention. Nevertheless, it is important to note we have missing data ($n = 19$; 48%) when examining pupil acceptability from week 2 of HH and thereon. From the completed logbooks, completion rates ranged from 58% in week 1 to 33% in week 8. Whilst the teachers suggested that there were higher completion rates in earlier weeks, they believed the novelty of the activities may have worn off, with lower completion rates over the later stages of the programme. Analysis of homework completion rates confirms that completion of HH activities decreased as the weeks progressed

Table 7-5 Completion of HH activities based on teacher's fidelity logbooks.

Weekly HH activities	Completion of weekly HH activities
	<i>n</i> (%)
Week 1 – Yoga	23 (58)
<i>Missing</i>	2 (5)
Week 2 – Fitness and nutrition	16 (40)
<i>Missing</i>	19 (48)
Week 3 – Dance and nutrition	16 (40)
<i>Missing</i>	19 (48)
Week 4 – Walking	11 (28)
<i>Missing</i>	19 (48)
Week 5 (Holiday week) – Games and colouring	11 (28)
<i>Missing</i>	19 (48)
Week 6 (Holiday week) – Games and colouring	11 (28)
<i>Missing</i>	19 (48)
Week 7 – Play	11 (28)
<i>Missing</i>	19 (48)
Week 8 – Games and nutrition	13 (33)
<i>Missing</i>	19 (48)

7.3.4 Positive outcomes associated with HH

Teachers and pupils provided information surrounding the positive outcomes associated with HH (Table 7-6). Teachers suggested that they enjoyed implementing HH activities into their classroom, and believed that this practice got the class into a routine, which was easy to implement as weekly HH and ran alongside other key areas of the curriculum as it was well-matched to the CfE. Teachers also discussed additional positives associated with HH including strengthened teacher-pupil and parent-child relationships, encouraging children to be more active, and engaging school-based activities with home-life.

7.3.5 Negative outcomes associated with HH

Teachers and pupils outlined negatives and barriers associated with HH including: parental attitudes to homework completion, additional commitments and parent employment (see Table 7-7). Pupils discussed specific additional commitments in which they associated with barriers to completion of HH activities including parent employment and being involved in extra-curricular clubs.

In relation to HWB homework the teachers said that prior to HH they either did not hand out any at all, had not ever considered it, or did not hand out a 'huge amount.' And each teacher suggested that as a result of HH they recognised the importance of HWB homework. Nonetheless, potential barriers to the effectiveness of HH emerged as the teachers suggested that HWB homework was not given the same importance as other areas of the curriculum and more broadly they did not consider the completion of homework to be a high priority to the school or the teachers (see Table 7-7).

7.3.6 Application of SDT in HH

During the 'tell' phase of WDST component, verbatim data was collected regarding the effectiveness of the application of SDT in HH. Specifically, pupils provided feedback surrounding the three basic psychological needs: (1) autonomy in HH (see Table 7-8), (2)

Competence in HH (see Table 7-9), (3) Relatedness within PA participation and interaction during HH (see Table 7-10) and (4) Relatedness regarding pupils perceived level of support during HH and parent-child relationships after HH (see Table 7-11). From our qualitative enquiry, it is suggested that HH was satisfied these basic psychological needs. Regarding autonomy, children indicated that they experienced having choice over the activities to do in HH. In relation to competence, children indicated that they felt capable and motivated by the activities set in HH, but did not feel the tasks were overly challenging.

Regarding relatedness, children highlighted that it was positive to see their parents being active and participating in some exercises for the first time. Furthermore, children indicated that HH activities brought their families together, especially those whose parents do not engage in activities with their children and spend time on their mobile phone.

7.3.7 Key recommendations to improve HH

Ultimately, teachers and pupils seemed keen to have HH continue, with teachers suggesting that, despite their previous involvement in the design of HH, we could work more closely with them on the content of HH in the future. Additionally, pupils suggested that they would like it continue receiving HH in order to remain active. Nevertheless, teachers and pupils provided us with key recommendations in order to improve HH (see Table 7-12). Specifically, teachers suggested that it should be handed out once a week and pupils recommended that HH should have less-structure and could therefore be completed on any day during the week.

Table 7-6 Teacher and pupils' positive perceptions of HH

Theme	Subtheme	Example quote
Teacher perceptions		
Content	Useful and appropriate content Activities well-matched to curriculum	<i>I was really keen to take part because when I looked at what the sort of activities... I thought they well-matched the curriculum and the age and stage of the children so I thought they would enjoy doing it – Teacher 1</i>
	Links HWB messages from school to home Challenges	<i>I quite like the idea of setting them active challenges or maybe trying to get them to be asleep by a certain time... So, I quite liked that idea and its maybe something I took from it the most was that actually setting them challenges to do at home might be quite useful - Teacher 2</i>
	Enjoyable for the children	<i>And the activities I thought were appropriate and enjoyable for the children - Teacher 1</i>
Preferred activities	Yoga	<i>I actually liked all of them for different reasons. I'd say the week I yoga, that ties into things I was saying before that I was trying to do about more mindfulness or maybe more relaxing... - Teacher 1</i>
	Dance	
	Walking	
	Workout week – spelling workout	
Encouraging habitual activity	Liked the idea of puzzles instead of work over the Easter Holiday period. Hoped HH kept the children thinking of HWB whilst on Holiday Completed well over the Easter Holiday period. Could have been made optional for children who go on holiday over the Easter Holiday period	<i>They really quite liked the colouring in and that seemed to be quite well done... well some of them weren't but you could tell most of them weren't rushed. So, you could tell they maybe had a wee proper go at it instead of just rushing it - Teacher 2</i>
Implementation	Class got into routine	<i>They would bring that in the following Monday and when they brought that in they'd get their sticker and get the new one out so the actual implementing it and routine wasn't a bother we kinda worked that in with our usual homework and it was quite good just having that as my fourth task every week and the kids knew what was coming up Teacher 1.</i>
	Teacher enjoyed implementation Explained well for the children	<i>And looking over it, it was all very well explained and the children didn't seem to have any issues with 'oh I don't know what I'm doing here' which is generally what we get – Teacher 2</i>
	Homework was provided for the teacher	<i>Part of me was like great, that's homework I don't need to worry about. I didn't really, to be honest, didn't have a big opinion on it – Teacher 3</i>
Teacher-pupil relationship	Making relationships stronger	<i>And to be able to have a chat with them on a Monday when I gave it out about what they were going to be doing and they were telling me 'well I've got dance club' or 'I'm doing this...' so I may be found out more about what they did outside of school [that] would've kept them active.... so, I was maybe finding more about how they stayed active outside of school which is a benefit and things they enjoyed doing - Teacher 1</i>
	Encouraging pupils to be more active	<i>I felt myself I probably made more of a point of trying to encourage the children to do it which is obviously a good thing to be encouraging them to be as active as possible so maybe bringing it into my mind more to encourage them to do it - Teacher 1</i>

Table 7-6 Teacher and pupils' positive perceptions of HH (continued).

Pupil perceptions		
Activities	Well planned	<i>No, it was quite well planned out. Like it was once every 2 days. So, you still had 2 days on the weekend if you weren't able to do it – Girl 7</i>
	Amount of homework given	
	Preferred active homework tasks	<i>I agree with everyone else the active ones make you more, want to go and be more active. The written ones, you're just sitting down writing... - Girl 8</i>

Table 7-7 Negative perceptions and barriers teachers and pupils perceived regarding HH.

Theme	Subtheme	Example quote
Teacher perceptions		
HH Stickers	Clashing views (class-by-class basis) Enthusiastic initially	<i>Initially they seemed quite enthusiastic about the stickers but then it kinda tailed off. But then, maybe the aged range they're at, the stickers aren't the same novelty for them - Teacher 2</i>
	Not an enticement Collecting back in HH workbooks was time-consuming	<i>I found it, the handing out of them fine. Em, the collecting in of it was more of a challenge I felt because em, we were collecting it in at the end of the week, and then I was having to check through them all and put the stickers on. It's maybe my issues and I could've planned it better but, I wanted to be the one to check them in order to check if they had the stickers. I found that I was getting myself quite flustered at the end of the week and trying to tick off who had handed it in and who hadn't handed it in and then checking to see that they had done all the activities. Yeah, I found that aspect quite time consuming. - Teacher 2</i>
Pupil perceptions		
Barriers	Lifestyle	<i>Cause some people would be like aw it's very good for my child because they don't do anything. So, I guess it's for like some people but not for others. Like some people might have like a really serious sport they do and they're training like every day of the week for like 4 hours or something so like when you come back it's like 'right I have to do it now' – Girl 6</i>
	Clubs Time-consuming Parent employment	<i>Its just sometimes sports get in the way. So, it was a good amount but it's just like sometimes stuff gets in the way... - Girl 7</i>
	Celebrations	<i>I think it was due the HH, I had my auntie and uncles wedding because I had to go out and get stuff for it a lot – Girl 1</i>

Table 7-8 Pupils perceived Autonomy in HH

Theme	Sub-theme	Example quote
Options in HH	Days	<i>I don't know if this makes sense but one night I got in really late and I had to do HH and I was like to my mum 'I have to do it' and she was like 'don't do it just now' and I was like 'no I have to'. And when I thought about it more I thought I'd just leave it till tomorrow and my mum was fine with that... – Girl 1</i>
	Time	<i>I like the ones that provided you with an option because if there was one you didn't really want to do at the time they you could have like the option to do another one so then if you, then when you want to do the other one you can do the other one as well – Boy 6</i>
	Activities – choice	<i>I prefer the ones like options. Em, so you have like more options you don't just need to do that it gives you like more opportunity to do that... if you had one option and you didn't like it you have one option you have to do but you might not like it a lot or as much. But if you have 2 options then you've got that one option you can go to say I really like that, or I don't like that. So, if you do more than 2 options, maybe like 4 or 5 options, you could do, it would make... if you liked all of them you might decide 'aw I want to do all of them' so you might be more active that night if you've got, if you don't do as much sports you could be like aw ill just do this one. It might not be as much but its more active you could do all of them if you wanted to be more active – Girl 6</i>
	Activities – prescriptive	<i>I think in some of the activities there is a choice between some and then in others like, it will tell you to go do this or that, like it was a set activities for some of them you had to do which would be good in some ways. Like some of them would be really good but some would be like not challenging but like made you have to go out your way to do it, and not like quick...- Girl 6</i>
Pressure to complete HH	No pressure	
	Pressure from teacher	<i>When the teacher didn't get a lot in she got quite annoyed and we felt pressured to do it – Boy 1</i>
	Competing interests/activities	<i>After sport... like if you have a club on. If it's like late on like 7 or 8 your mum or dads like it's a school night get to bed. And you're like having to do it. So, if there's more options you could be like that one's going to be quicker I could do that one – Boy 7</i>

Table 7-9 Pupils perceived Competence in HH

Theme	Subtheme	Example quote
Capability	Capable	<i>Em, I felt quite capable. Like your mum and dad might say aw you done that wrong but you're kinda in a smaller group so I felt more capable – Girl 3</i>
	Balanced level of difficulty	<i>Yeah. I don't want to say it was easy. Sometimes it was challenging but sometimes it was easy... I found the written ones easy, like relatively easy, but the like most of the active ones like the em, the alphabet exercise like I have quite a, like 7 letters in my name so that's a lot of exercise – Boy 6</i>
HH challenges	Fun Aimed at younger population Good idea Competitiveness	<i>I mean it wasn't, it didn't have to be that challenging like cause you kinda wanna win. The plank one was quite, it was like a fun challenge if you know what I mean – Girl 6</i>
Overcome HH challenges	Read over it – understand more Determined to try my best	<i>Cause the one that was like the sugar one, like the teaspoon. At first, we didn't really understand how much it was and what it was and sometimes some packets might not say like the certain amount on it. So, it's hard to like, it was like your favourite snacks to have, but some of your favourite snacks might not have it so it's good to see you're looking to see what ones are good for you. At first, we didn't really get it but after you done it, after you thought about it and read the question more it was getting more clear – Girl 6</i>
Sense of accomplishment	Proud Special occasions Completed all 8 weeks New skills	<i>I have like accomplished some skills that I wasn't able to do before like... – Girl 6</i>
	Interest in new activities Fun to complete compared to maths Made sure went back to compete all activities	<i>I wasn't really calm before and I wasn't really into yoga. But now I've tried it I actually quite like it – Girl 3</i> <i>That I had finished them. I missed one week because I wasn't in school I was away somewhere but obviously I couldn't hand it in but after the last week I just did that because I would've felt like I just left that one – Boy 6</i>

Table 7-10 Pupils perceived Relatedness: PA participation and interactions during HH

Theme	Subtheme	Example quote
Participate in PA with most	Siblings Cousins	<i>Most of the time I'll just do it with... em, my cousins, and em, I don't go to any clubs anymore. I used to go to loads but now I don't – Girl 1</i>
	Pet	<i>This sounds really really strange, but em, my aunties dog... he loves to chase after his ball and he loves to have a race because he's really really fast because he's a cocker spaniel and its really fun because you'll just run with him and he will give you this wee grin when you run past and he's got the ball and he will look up at you – Girl 2</i>
	Friends Dad	<i>Eh my dad... he's quite active and he's the only person in my family that comes cycling or running... I'm not entirely sure [why]... probably because we can go a lot longer distance that if I was just with my friends – Boy 1</i>
	Mum	<i>My mum because usually she drags me out of bed to go a run... because usually my friends don't want to come out to play. They just video-chat me. They are more social – Girl 4</i>
Parent/family participant in HH	Mum (majority)	<i>Yeah... usually my mum would work from home but my dad doesn't work from home at all... [Inaudible] – Boy 3</i>
	Dad	<i>My mum helped me with the last couple but my dad did the yoga one but he couldn't do it and he fell flat on his face [laughing] – Girl 3</i>
	Siblings Gran Cousins	
Experience of family participation in HH	Seeing parents active Competitiveness	<i>It was good, it was the first time I've ever saw either of my parents do the plank... I liked doing it – Boy</i> <i>With your parents it's making you more competitive to beat them. Em, and then it's like fun because you're having that time with them. So, it's fun to have more time doing stuff – Girl 6</i>
	Fun Sometimes not enough people to play games Took parent away from technology	<i>Yeah because my dad's always on his phone. He practically doesn't do anything with me so... he does the homework with me. Usually, daily he's on his phone and never really speaks to me. So, with the HH he actually does it with me and its better – Girl 4</i>
	Brought family together	<i>It was kinda like fun and happy cause like, my parents are like divorced and he came to do the homework with me because I asked him so I was kinda happy... yeah... happy because I like finally saw my mum and dad like together so like it was nice – Girl 4</i>

Table 7-11 Pupil perceived Relatedness: perceived level of support during HH and parent-child relationship after HH

Theme	Subtheme	Example quote
Supported/cared for	Encouraged to complete activities	<i>Yeah, I felt supported. When they did have the time to come over and help me they were telling me like, say it was the plank one, they would tell me that I could do it and I was able to do it – Girl 8</i>
	Parent wanted to join in Usually hates homework – felt happy spending time with family	<i>Yeah, because like they support you on your homework. Usually I don't want to do homework but when I had to do that, when I was doing it with them, I felt happy... because usually I hate homework.... because I spent time with my family and stuff like that – Girl 4</i>
	Helping to complete activities Boost of confidence	<i>I remember like for a couple of weeks id just be doing it myself because my mum and dad had to work but then they had like time to do one with me so I wasn't by myself doing it. My mum and dad were doing it. So, it wasn't just me doing it this time. And they helped me do it... and then like when you're doing a plank and them supporting you yeah like that. It boosts your confidence – Boy 6</i>
Relationship after HH	The same	<i>We got closer... because we were spending more time together... my dad comes out the back with me to play football... yeah, because he used to say he didn't have any time – Boy 4</i>
	Spend more time together now	<i>Em, yeah because when it was all done and stuff like that, they wanted to do more sports with me and stuff like that – Girl 4</i>
	Participate in sports together now Fall out over losing	<i>It makes you angry when you lose to your parents. It makes you fall out [laughing] – Boy 7</i>
	Get along better	<i>Well me and my dad kinda get competitive with each other. So, if I won against him he would always want to have a re-match or something like that. But yeah in the end if he won he'd be happy. But like it kinda depends how it goes. Like if he wins he will be really happy but he won't let go of it. But then it would kinda improve after it because we became like... just like we kinda got along a wee bit better – Girl 7</i>

Table 7-12 Key recommendations to improve HH

Theme	Subtheme	Example quote
Teacher recommendations		
Every day approach – normal		<i>The only thing I can really think of is... trying to make it a bit more, as part of their normal day. Things they might be doing kinda anyway. Em, I know that would probably be really hard to think of things like that. But the walking one was a really good example of that because they would be building that into their day anyway. And if they weren't, they might not see it as too onerous to try and to try and do. - Teacher 1</i>
Streamline implementation	Signing in one place	<i>You had them signing it Monday, Wednesday, Friday. I get that, but maybe just one day for the parents to sign it like on a Thursday just to say this is when it's done... obviously, with HWB you're trying to get them to do it on a daily basis but even if that is the case they're still only getting it signed on the Thursday night - Teacher 3</i>
	Hand out once a week	<i>Em, based on what we do with homework, we would give it out once a week and it would be expected, say you hand it out on Monday and collect in on Friday. Because generally speaking the homework we do is out on Monday in on a Friday. Um, so with the wee kinda activities Monday, Wednesday, Friday, rather than on Friday morning like 'you need to sign, you need to sign' like, wee things... - Teacher 3</i>
	Holiday challenges instead of homework	<i>Even a challenge instead of actual homework. You know so, 'your challenge this holiday weekend is to...' and then a generic be active for 15 mins and get it signed off - Teacher 3</i>
Teachers	Research team could work more closely with classroom teachers on content planning	<i>The only thing I would say is it might be worth em, depending on what age range your targeting at, so maybe you could discuss with us, with teachers or whatever, think about the level of certain things so like the games and things like that. Upper school and lower school will be interested in completely different things. Em, so that's an option if it's going to be games they want to play, we could maybe have some ideas of the activities they could do - Teacher 2.</i>
	Rewards specific to school	<i>So yeah probably finding on a school-by-school basis what they're reward systems like and behaviour systems - Teacher 1</i>
Continue promoting it		<i>Gee-wiz... em... I don't know. Em... I think it is just constantly flogging at it. I don't know. I think nowadays everyone just accepts everything to be done for them. So how will you manage to get people to recognise they need to take responsibility for their own development and their own HWB? Rather than it being something that is handed out to them. But I think you're kinda battling against the tide with it - Teacher 3</i>
Incorporate equipment		<i>I know that in P6 we do 'bikeability' so I don't know if anything involving bikes but then you have the whole equity thing if not everyone has a bike so there's issues like that - Teacher 1</i>
Pupil recommendations		
Increase autonomy support	Some activities – go out and play (less structured)	<i>I just feel like if we didn't have days when we had to do it, em, it would be a little bit better – Girl 1</i> <i>After sport... like if you have a club on. If it's like late on like 7 or 8 your mum or dads like it's a school night get to bed. And you're like having to do it. So, if there's more options you could be like that one's going to be quicker I could do that one – Boy 7</i>
	Any days (less structured)	
	More options – activities	
Increase autonomy in ways to completion HH activities	Ways to prove you have completed the activities	<i>I think we should have to like do something to show that we've done it. I know that like, I only got my mum to sign it once I done it but some people just go their mum to sign it so oh yeah I've done it... yeah to make people want to do it because they're so to their electronics or like if they've got a phone you could say like call a friend or text a friend to go out and play for 15 mins. So, say you called, say I called Anna, you could write like who did you go out with, who did you call, and then at school the next day, when you've told to prove you could ask Anna, did Zara actually call you – Girl 7</i>
	Digitally (computer-based)	

7.4 Discussion

The primary aim of this study was to explore the feasibility of HH, a randomised control trial to improve children's 24 h movement behaviours and dietary intake. The intervention was implemented by all three intervention teachers. From the 158 children who were provided with informed consent, a recruitment rate of 43% and retention rate of 93% was observed (Barber et al., 2016). Within those children that were retained from baseline to follow-up, the collection of valid measures varied by the outcome, compliance was highest for ActiGraph GT3X+ data (100%). Thereafter, high compliance for BMI (93%) and ST (92%), closely followed by the completion of the dietary intake questionnaire (91%) was observed. Thereon, 67% compliance of valid ActivPAL4™ accelerometer data was observed.

From the fidelity logbook, it was apparent that completion of the Yoga, Fitness and Nutrition, and Dance homework activities were greater than the Holiday Games, Walking and Play homework activities. From our qualitative enquiry with teachers and pupils, it was clear that adherence of HH activities reduced as the intervention progressed and that activity-related activities were preferred. Previous research in compulsory homework-based interventions have found similar outcomes (Duncan et al., 2019).

Incentives have been used to encourage participation in school-based interventions including rewards as employed in this study, but also financial incentives (Martin et al., 2014) and donations to charity (Hunter et al., 2015). Previous research has demonstrated good adherence to the intervention when participants have been provided with incentives such as monetary gifts to their school upon meeting intervention goals (e.g., achieving a 2% weight loss goal) (Yoo et al., 2017). Future school-based interventions may wish to consider the use of incentives where possible to enhance compliance to their study aims.

We also had missing data within our fidelity logbooks ($n = 19$; 48%) when examining pupil acceptability of HH due to one teacher failing to complete their logbook from week 2

onwards. Incomplete logbooks has been noted as a limitation in examining acceptability of the AFLY5 intervention which included a homework element (Campbell et al., 2015). A recent systematic review of measuring implementation fidelity of school-based obesity prevention programmes suggests that logbooks, amongst other methods (e.g., observations, questionnaires) were the most common methods of measuring fidelity (Schaap et al., 2018). However, there is no agreed consensus on the operationalisation of concepts and methods used for assessing fidelity in such programmes (Schaap et al., 2018).

The home environment is known to be one of the more challenging settings to implement interventions aiming to improve children's health outcomes, particularly in low SES groups (Knowlden and Sharma, 2012). This finding is echoed by Malden and colleagues (2019) who found a low level of implementation in the home environment (41%) and a low post-intervention survey response of only 15% in a feasibility cluster randomised control trial of an obesity prevention intervention. (Malden et al., 2019). Thus, HH was informed by research with less involved parents of low SES indicating that low-cost home-based activities including parent and child joint activities in the home environment can increase involvement (Donnelly et al., 2019). Families recruited to this study included families of low SES (23%) and less-involved parents (49%). Therefore, future interventions aiming to involve parents should take heed to the recommendations provided by less-involved parents of low SES to encourage their involvement alongside more affluent and more motivated parents.

From our qualitative investigation with teachers, it was suggested that being involved in the HH intervention strengthened teacher-pupil and parent-child relationships. Indeed, HH was found to have a substantial influence on family life by bringing parents and children together, and feeling more connected than before they participated in HH. Additionally, it was suggested that HH promoted the importance of healthy lifestyles, with its activities well-matched to the CfE. Teachers suggested HH improved their relationship with the pupils and

allowed them to engage with home-life through home-based HH challenges. However, parent attitudes and employment, as well as children's additional commitments (i.e., clubs and extra-curricular activities) were viewed by children as key barriers to completion of HH activities. Teachers indicated that whilst pupils are strongly advised to complete their homework, nothing can be made compulsory, and suggested that not enough importance was emphasised on HWB homework when compared to homework focussing on literacy and mathematics. Therefore, in order to gain the benefits associated with HH structural changes may be required to ensure that health-related homework tasks as seen by teachers, parents and children as a key area of learning.

The secondary aim of this study was to examine preliminary effects of the HH pilot on children's activity patterns, sleep and dietary behaviours. The preliminary effects of the HH intervention found significant increases in activity including stepping time, MVPA stepping time as well as significantly less time spent in SB (i.e., less time in sitting bouts (0-30mins)). Healthy Homework, to the best of our knowledge, is the only other compulsory school-based obesity prevention intervention which also observed significant intervention effects for weekday PA at home and weekend PA (Buchan, Donnelly, et al., 2019). However, studies which included homework within their intervention, however did not promote this as compulsory (e.g., Active Smarter Kids (ASK) intervention and AFLY5), showed no significant effects on executive functions affected by PA (e.g., cognitive flexibility), SB, or fruit and vegetable consumption (Kipping et al., 2014, Aadland et al., 2019). As such, both our qualitative and quantitative data indicate that future school-based interventions employing homework activities should work closely with school personnel to align the intervention with the curriculum and thus, promote such homework's as compulsory in order to achieve significant positive intervention effects.

The difference between the control and intervention group for sleep was negligible with the intervention group having longer durations of sleep than the control group. To the best of our knowledge, HH is the first school-based obesity prevention homework intervention which focusses on 24 h movement behaviours, including sleep. To this end, we cannot compare our findings regarding sleep with previous school-based obesity prevention homework intervention studies. Nonetheless, findings from a systematic literature review of interventions aiming to stimulate healthy sleep in school-aged children suggest that the lack of high quality studies in this field indicates that evidence for the effectiveness of any particular intervention strategy to stimulate healthy sleep in children remains inconclusive (Busch et al., 2017). Given the importance of sleep for health (i.e., activity and diet), future studies may wish to capture sleep data in order to strengthen the evidence surrounding the most effective strategy for improving this behaviour.

Similar to the findings reported in previous compulsory homework interventions aimed at improving health-related behaviours in children, we did not observe any meaningful intervention effects of HH on ST (Duncan et al., 2011, 2019). The AFLY5 intervention appeared to have a beneficial effect on ST (Kipping, Payne and Lawlor, 2008) and included one lesson about screen viewing entitled ‘Freeze my TV’ which involved analysing leisure time to identify ST and making a list of alternative activities. Currently, the CfE does not include a ST component and therefore, we would assume the children in our intervention did not receive a classroom lesson on ST. Furthermore, whilst we did not observe any significant intervention effects on fruit and vegetable consumption, effects have been observed in fruit and vegetable consumption in other compulsory health homework studies (Duncan et al., 2011, 2019). We believe that the intensity of the nutritional components within these studies were greater than HH, as children were encouraged to participate in one nutrition component each week. This may explain the lack of effect on children’s fruit and vegetable consumption

in our study. Future studies interested in improving children's fruit and vegetable consumption may need to incorporate more frequent and intense nutritional components.

There are several strengths associated with this study, particularly in relation to it being randomised at school-level to avoid class contamination effects. Additionally, the development of HH should be highlighted as a key strength. HH was developed with headteachers, and underpinned by a theoretical model of behaviour change, was multicomponent in nature, involved schools, families and involved compulsory homework activities. In doing so, our intervention has proven to be appropriate in the recruitment and retainment of parents of the lowest 20% area-SES, would typically be classified as 'less-involved'; an accomplishment in which many researchers struggle to achieve (Robinson, Adair, Coffey, Harris, & Burnside, 2016). Such methodological and theoretical decisions have shown to be most effective in school-based health improvement interventions (Day, Sahota and Christian, 2019). Indeed, recent research from Daly-Smith and colleagues (2020) using a multi-stakeholder experience-based design process to co-develop the 'Creating Active Schools' Framework presents a paradigm shift in order to guide experts of PA interventions to work 'with' schools, abandoning outdated and traditional approaches which simply implement such interventions 'on' schools (Daly-Smith et al., 2020). Whilst HH was feasible and acceptable for teachers to implement into the curriculum, teachers and pupils provided key recommendations to improve such acceptability for pupils and parents in future trials. Furthermore, in-depth, qualitative and quantitative data was collected across a number of outcomes from pupils, parents and teachers. Based on the qualitative inquiry with pupils, HH appeared to satisfy children's competence, relatedness and autonomy by providing choice of enjoyable and challenging tasks which brought families together, who typically didn't engage in PA together prior to HH.

We applied novel accelerometry metrics and strict wear-time criteria for both ActiGraph and ActivPAL outcomes, aiming to capture the participant's activity over a 24 h period to determine the preliminary effectiveness of the HH in improving PA and sleep behaviours. Limitations of this study include the small sample size, although it must be stated that this feasibility study was not intended to be adequately powered to make statistical inferences. Of the children who participated in this study, 28 (41%) met the wear-time criteria for ActiGraph devices ($n = 18$ intervention arm) whereas 49 (72%) met the wear-time criteria for ActivPAL4™ devices ($n = 28$ intervention arm) at baseline. Additionally, we did not obtain data from parents regarding their health outcomes. Furthermore, as we were not provided with fidelity information regarding completion of HH from one of our intervention classes, we were unable to adequately interpret the most completed weeks/activities.

7.4.1 Conclusion

In summary, HH activities were implemented into the curriculum successfully over the 8-week intervention period, and involved families of low SES with parents who would typically be categorised as 'less-involved'. Acceptability decreased throughout the course of the intervention, with qualitative investigations providing recommendations to improve HH acceptability. This feasibility study provides detailed information and insight, particularly surrounding the barriers to implementing HH, and key recommendations to improve its future development. HH activities which targeted the 24 h movement behaviours whilst satisfying children's basic needs during PA can result in improvements in stepping time, MVPA stepping time and time spent sitting. Few studies have implemented interventions in which homework activities play a significant role, yet such interventions may elevate pressure on schools. The implementation and exploration of such interventions aiming to improve children's 24 h movement behaviours are warranted to evaluate their effectiveness and sustainability long-term.

Thesis Study Map

Study	Objectives and Key Findings
<p>Study 1: An insight into mothers with low socioeconomic status' involvement in Scottish primary school health education activities</p>	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recruit less-involved mothers with low SES • Interview these mothers to establish barriers to their involvement in school-based health education and gain insight and recommendations on how to engage families with low SES • Based on the findings, propose strategies schools can use to increase parent involvement in future health-related activities <p>Key findings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mothers with low SES state similar barriers to being involved when compared to previous research; however, with added barriers including lack of confidence, feelings of being disliked by the parent council and unpredictable working schedules. • Emphasis was placed on increased communication with school staff and variation in the timing of events • Mothers recommended school staff should organise events more instead of the parent council
<p>Study 2: The effects of socioeconomic status on parent and child dyads moderate-to-vigorous physical activity and body mass index</p>	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine the relationship between parent and child MVPA and BMI in a sample of children (4-11 years old) using wrist-worn accelerometers. • Explore mediating processes by which SES influences child MVPA and BMI z-score through their parents MVPA and BMI. <p>Key findings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekend parent and child MVPA was significantly related. • Parent and child BMI were also significantly related. • There was a significant negative direct effect of SES on child BMI. • a significant negative indirect effect of SES on child BMI via their parents BMI was observed.
<p>Study 3: Relationship between parent and child dyads physical activity using novel acceleration metrics</p>	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine whether the intensity or volume of PA predicts BMI in children and adults • Explore parent-child associations between these metrics and BMI. <p>Key findings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The activity metrics were not associated with parent BMI, and no independent effects were observed between the metrics. • Associations between boys IG and BMI z-score were observed. • No independent effects were observed between the two metrics and no significant associations were observed between boys BMI z-score and AvAcc. • For girls, no significant associations were observed between AvAcc and IG with BMI z-score and no independent effects were observed between the two metrics.
<p>Study 4: Exploring the feasibility of a cluster-randomised control trial to improve children's 24 h movement behaviours and dietary intake: HH</p>	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore the feasibility of HH from qualitative investigations with teachers and pupils • Examine preliminary effects of the HH pilot intervention on children's 24 h activity patterns and dietary behaviours. <p>Key findings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A recruitment rate of 43% and retention rate of 93% was observed. • Compliance for ActiGraph GT3X+, BMI, ST and dietary intake questionnaire outcomes was high ranging from 91% to 100%, while 67% of the sample provided valid ActivPAL4™ data for both baseline and post-intervention. • HH was found to improve measures of PA and SB in children in 8 weeks • HH appears appropriate in satisfying the basic psychological needs of children

CHAPTER 8

GENERAL DISCUSSION

8.1 Summary of key findings

This general discussion chapter will examine the main themes outlined in this thesis.

The aim of the thesis was:

- To capture the perspectives of mothers from a low SES that are not typically involved in school-based health activities to inform the design of interventions which aim to encourage parent involvement in school-based health activities.
- To objectively examine the relationship between parent-child PA using robust, novel approaches.
- To examine the influence SES plays on children's PA and BMI through their parents PA and BMI.
- To design, implement and evaluate the fidelity of a health-related homework-based intervention theoretically underpinned and informed by end-user's experiences using mixed-method approaches.

Through a variety of methodological approaches, four studies were undertaken in order to achieve these aims. While the findings of each chapter have been discussed individually, this chapter aims to combine the main results from Chapters 4-7 (Studies 1-4), examine the overall conclusions of this thesis and make suggestions for future research. This thesis began by reviewing the literature surrounding childhood obesity and physical inactivity which led to a review of school-based interventions and the influence of parent involvement in such interventions. From this review, it is clear that parent involvement in school-based health interventions is limited to the most motivated of parents. Whilst studies have been conducted in order to understand the barriers parents face to become involved, these studies tend to represent parents who are already typically involved and are from higher SES.

Chapter 4 (Study 1) adopted a qualitative methodology to investigate mothers with low SES to establish the reasons and barriers to their involvement in school-based health

activities and propose strategies to increase their involvement in those activities. Interviews were conducted with mothers with low SES, who were typically not involved in school-based health activities. Through an inductive-deductive approach to hierarchical analysis, the key findings from study one revealed that there are several barriers resulting in mother's being less-involved, particularly due to issues surrounding the parent council and exclusivity of school-based events. Efforts made by the school to promote health activities and involve parents in such activities was revealed, alongside recommendations to improve upon these practices. Taken together, the findings of this study offer multiple ways in which future school-based health interventions can recruit and involve mothers with low SES.

Additionally, researchers should consider known active ingredients to parental involvement including: parents being made aware of the benefits to child health, children's enjoyment at their parent being active with them, and the inclusion of extended family (e.g., grandparents) in order to recruit less-involved parents with low SES to school-based health interventions (Donnelly et al., 2019). Through our exploration of perceptions of families with low SES alongside findings from previous research, the influence SES plays is evident. As such it was prudent thereon that the relationship between parents and their child's weight status and activity was also explored with SES in mind. As such, a second study was undertaken with the aim of exploring the relationship between parent and their children's weight and activity, as well as ways in which SES may influence this relationship.

Chapter 5 (Study 2) was a cross-sectional study which explored the relationship between parent and child MVPA and BMI in a sample of children (4-11 years old) using wrist-worn accelerometers, and to explore mediating processes by which SES influences child MVPA and BMI z-score through their parents MVPA and BMI. In this study we employed wrist-worn accelerometers, robust WTC and comparable cut-points in order to examine the relationship between parent and child activity. Our hypotheses were that SES

would be related to children's MVPA and BMI z-scores indirectly via parental MVPA and BMI. The key findings from study 2 were that weekend parent and child MVPA was significantly related. Parent and child BMI were also significantly related. There was a significant negative direct effect of SES on child BMI. Additionally, we observed a significant negative indirect effect of SES on child BMI via their parents BMI. This suggests that SES both directly and indirectly (via their parents BMI) negatively effects children's BMI and is therefore a key contributor to children's weight status. Additionally, parent and child MVPA were significantly related during the weekend. Nevertheless, there were no associations between SES and MVPA. Taken together, the findings of this study suggest that future interventions aiming to improve health outcomes in children should consider the influence SES can have. Additionally, parents are found to be most influential on their child's PA when they are more likely to be together (i.e., weekends) which should also be targeted in future interventions. Our hypothesis was accepted regarding SES being related to children's BMI z-scores indirectly via parental BMI. Regarding PA, no significant indirect effect of SES on children's MVPA via parental MVPA was observed. As previously discussed, use of cut-points can make it difficult to compare the activity outcomes of varying populations including adults and children and thus, parents and their child. With this in mind, and with recent advancements in accelerometry research, primarily raw novel metrics, it was important to explore the relationship between parent and child activity and weight further using more comparable measures.

Chapter 6 (Study 3) was a cross-sectional study which aimed to examine whether the IG or AvAcc was associated with BMI in children and adults and explored parent-child associations between PA and BMI. This study aimed to examine whether the intensity or volume of PA predicts BMI in children and adults and explore parent-child associations between these PA metrics and BMI. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to

examine parent-child activity behaviours using novel accelerometer derived activity metrics. The key findings revealed no significant associations between parent-child activity. Whilst girls BMI z-score was found to be positively associated with parent inactive time and parent BMI, this was not observed for boys. As such, our findings suggest that parent-child activity is not related although a significant relationship was evident between parent BMI and BMI z-score, but for girls only. No significant associations were found for AvAcc, IG and MVPA with BMI in adult participants or BMI z-score in children. Parent BMI was negatively associated with boy's inactive time. Parental inactive time, when adjusted, predicted girls BMI-z scores. The activity metrics were not associated with parent BMI, and no independent effects were observed between the metrics. Associations between boys IG and BMI z-score were observed in the unadjusted model, and when adjusted for age and SIMD. When the model was adjusted further for the alternative metric, this association was not observed. No independent effects were observed between the two metrics and no significant associations were observed between boys BMI z-score and AvAcc. For girls, no significant associations were observed between AvAcc and IG with BMI z-score and no independent effects were observed between the two metrics. Therefore, the findings of this study support the notion that parental activity levels do not influence their child's activity levels as has been reported elsewhere (Jago et al., 2010, Erkelenz et al., 2014).

Chapter 7 (Study 4) employed a mixed-methodology to explore the acceptability of a novel HH pilot based on findings from qualitative investigation of perspectives of teachers and pupils. This chapter also examined preliminary effects of the HH pilot based on children's PA, SB, sleep and dietary behaviours. Whilst study-specific findings have been outlined in detail within their respective chapters, noteworthy significant findings within this thesis are highlighted in the following sub-sections. The primary aim of this study was to explore the feasibility of a randomised control trial of the HH intervention which aimed to

improve children's 24 h movement behaviours and dietary intake. This intervention was enhanced by theoretical and curricular underpinning and was informed by the perspectives gained by the mothers involved in Chapter 4 (Study 1) of this thesis. A key finding of Chapter 7 (Study 4) was that the intervention was implemented by all three intervention teachers recruited. From the children who were provided with informed consent ($n = 158$), a recruitment rate of 43.04% and subsequent retention rate of 92.65% was observed. Within those children that were retained from baseline to follow-up, the collection of valid measures varied by the outcome with high compliance evident for the ActiGraph GT3X+ data (100%). High compliance rates for BMI (92.65%), ST (92.31%) and completion of the dietary intake questionnaire (91.04%) was also observed. Thereon, 67.35% and 31.88% compliance of valid ActivPAL4™ accelerometer data and FIQ-E's, respectively was observed. From the fidelity logbook, it was apparent that completion of the Yoga, Fitness and Nutrition, and Dance homework activities were greater than the Holiday Games, Walking and Play homework activities.

From our qualitative enquiry with teachers and pupils, it was clear that adherence of HH activities reduced as the intervention progressed and that activity-related tasks were preferred rather than the writing tasks. The tasks were theoretically underpinned by SDT, which is increasingly being applied to school-based health interventions (Girelli and Luccidi, 2016, Sebire, Kesten, et al., 2016, González-Cutre et al., 2018, Demetriou and Bachner, 2019). As a result of such theoretically underpinning of HH tasks, qualitative inquiry with children suggested that children's basic psychological needs were met. It's efficacy to change health behaviours, primarily regarding PA, and to a lesser extent dietary behaviours is largely acknowledged (Ntoumanis et al., 2020). Such change in behaviour is explained as SDT introduces the concept of basic psychological needs as central to understanding both the satisfactions and supports necessary for promoting high quality, autonomous forms of

motivation. Consequently, the design of health behaviour change interventions that enhance satisfaction of participants' basic needs is a matter of much interest in SDT studies for decades, including in the area of exercise and PA (Silva, Vieira, Coutinho, Minderico, Matos, Sardinha, and Teixeira, 2010). Findings from a recent systematic review and meta-analysis surrounding self-determined motivation and PA in children and adolescents found that overall levels of self-determined motivation had a weak to moderate, positive association with PA (Owen, Smith, Lubans, Ng, and Lonsdale, 2014). Corroborating these findings, a non-randomised control trial with children of low SES, examining the effect of a school-based intervention on PA and wellbeing found that a SDT-based intervention had a positive impact on children's MVPA and wellbeing (Shannon, Brennan, Hanna, Younger, Hassan and Breslin, 2018). The authors indicate that PA and wellbeing were enhanced through psychological needs satisfaction, suggesting that practitioners should consider supporting children's psychological needs in the PA environment through provision of activity choice, open-ended questions and positive constructive feedback (Shannon et al., 2018). Combined, existing research acknowledges that satisfying children's psychological needs predicts their motivation to engage in PA. As such, future school-based interventions aiming to improve children's health-related behaviours should strongly consider the adoption of SDT and in turn, needs-supportive approaches within their intervention to enhance motivation to subsequently engage in health-conducive behaviours.

The secondary aim of this study was to examine preliminary effects of the HH pilot on children's activity patterns, sleep and dietary behaviours. Key findings relating to this aim were that HH improved PA and SB's in children in 8 weeks with each outcome indicating a large effect size. The exploration of school-based interventions which use compulsory homework to encourage habitual positive health-related activities based on 24 h movement guidelines is warranted to evaluate their effectiveness and sustainability long-term.

8.2 Overview of strengths and limitations

Whilst study-specific limitations have been discussed within their respective chapters, it is important to highlight certain limitations within the thesis through a wider perspective across the whole programme of research.

8.2.1 Strengths

Data derived from subjective methods to measure PA and through the use of pedometers have found to differ according to the indicators of PA used, with such outcome variation apparent in research examining the efficacy of school-based interventions and parent-child activity levels (Troost and Loprinzi, 2011, Craig, Cameron and Tudor-Locke, 2013, Stearns et al., 2016). The use of such methods increases the ambiguity of findings as subjective measures of PA are prone to recall bias whereas pedometers have been found to be inaccurate in assessing the distance covered and energy expended (Chinapaw et al., 2010, Ndahimana and Kim, 2017). Novel accelerometry metrics were used in Chapters 5-7 (studies 2-4) of this thesis, to enhance the reproducibility of our findings and allow other researchers to compare their findings with ours. By doing so, this may offer easily comparable outcomes in order to evaluate the most effective methods used in school-based interventions. The use of a stringent accelerometer WTC provides a holistic representation of activity outcomes included in Chapter 6 (Study 3) and in Chapter 7 (Study 4). These activity outcomes were based on the entire 24 h cycle rather than estimating time awake. As such, this provides confidence in such findings by providing a representation of activity behaviours over a sustained period. By reporting these novel metrics which were processed using open-source software (GGIR) that is freely available, future work may be able to directly compare their findings to those of ours.

To test the indirect effects of area-SES on children's MVPA and BMI z-score via their parents MVPA and BMI, a regression-based package known as PROCESS was used in

Chapter 5 (Study 2) to run mediation analyses (Hayes, 2012). Separate models were ran to examine the influence of area-SES on children's MVPA via their parents MVPA, and the influence of area-SES on children's BMI z-score via their parents BMI. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study explore how SES can influence children's activity and weight status through their parent's activity and weight status. This is a particular strength of the study as, throughout the literature review, it is evident that SES plays a significant role in childhood obesity and inactivity.

8.2.1.1 Design of school-based intervention

Prior to the design of HH, recommendations from Chapter 4 (Study 1) from less-involved mothers with low SES were mapped in order to effectively incorporate such guidance into the development of an intervention which requires their involvement. As such, we were able to recruit a substantial number of less-involved parents with low SES to the intervention. HH PA homework activities were decided upon based on The WHO recommendations for children aged 5-17 years old which suggests that most of children's daily activity should be aerobic and that vigorous-intensity activities should be incorporated, including pursuits which strengthen muscle and bone, at least 3 times per week (World Health Organization, 2018a). HH activities were also mapped in-line with the Scottish CfE for primary school children, taken into consideration their four developmental capacities. The development of the HH intervention was also informed by SDT which aimed to develop children's motivation to be involved in healthier lifestyles by meeting their three basic psychological needs: autonomy, competence and relatedness. The intervention was also informed and guided by Head Teachers in the participating schools prior to the activities being provided to children. This is a particular strength as various modifications were made to the activities to ensure they were in line with the CfE, therefore suitable to be provided as homework for the curriculum area of HWB, and suitable for the overall age of the class.

8.2.1.2 Recruitment procedures

Due to our face to face recruitment methods in Chapter 4 (Study 1) and specific eligibility criteria, we interviewed 16 mothers with low SES who were not usually involved in school-based health activities. As these mothers were less-involved and with low SES, they were unlikely to participate in research or school-based health activities and as such, their perceptions were captured which have previously been overlooked in similar research projects. A comparable approach was used for the recruitment of parent-child dyads in Chapter 5 and 6 (Study 2 and 3) which involved a two-pronged approach that involved: (1) recruitment drive by speaking at parent-attended assembly's, handing out flyers and hanging posters around the school at events in which parents were attending and (2) recruiting at parents' evenings where parents who would typically not engage in school-based health activities would be in attendance. This method allowed for the inclusion of parents from a range of socioeconomic backgrounds who would not typically attend events exclusively advertised as research events or health activities and in doing so, enhances the generalizability of the findings. As such, researchers may wish to consider recruiting families at events which are likely to be attended by all parents within the school, instead of those who are typically most motivated and involved.

8.2.2 Limitations

8.2.2.1 Small sample size

In Chapters 5-7, failure to meet the stringent WTC reduced the sample size used in the analyses of activity outcomes. This is unsurprising and common in accelerometry research in adults and youth (Keadle et al., 2014, Smith et al., 2017). Indeed, accelerometry data reduction is notoriously challenging, with research outlining reasons for accelerometer non-wear which are multifactorial and include individual factors such as response to peer influence (e.g., removal of unit because it is 'uncool') and social desirability bias (e.g.,

wearing units only when participating in PA) as well as researcher/measurement factors (e.g., researcher directives to remove individual participation in contact sports or water activities) (Sirard and Slater, 2009, Kirby et al., 2012, Belton et al., 2013). Providing financial incentives, text reminders, or being able to go back into the schools to further distribute the devices may have enhanced compliance rates as others have suggested (Cain et al., 2013, McCann et al., 2016). The exclusion of multiple participants in research exploring parent and child activity is fairly common (Solomon-Moore et al., 2018) and in order to encourage continued wear of the accelerometer devices, incentives may be required for parents and children in order to utilize stringent WTC and boost compliance rates.

8.2.2.2 Generalisability

Interviews were conducted in Chapter 4 (Study 1) in only one region of the UK, therefore the themes identified may not be reflective of mothers' views in other locations whilst father's views were not represented. Additionally, in Chapter 5-7 (studies 2-4) our analyses of health behaviours including activity, sleep and dietary intake and the relationship amongst these with parents and their children were examined in one region of the UK, again limiting the generalisability of the findings. Finally, the cross-sectional design and lack of longitudinal data prohibits drawing conclusions about causality in Chapter 5 (Study 2) and Chapter 6 (Study 3).

8.3 Implications and future directions

Taken together, the four studies within this thesis provide clear implications for practitioners based on the findings from each study. Indeed, the findings from each Chapter within this thesis have their own recommendations and implications for practitioners, particularly in relation to improving the design and effectiveness of school-based interventions. In the following subsections within this section, a detailed interpretation of implications, with future directions for practice and research are provided.

8.3.1 Pressure on school infrastructure through curricula demands

As childhood obesity and the pressure of curriculum demands on school staff continues to increase concurrently, the need for further exploration of school-based health interventions to evaluate their effectiveness and sustainability long-term has never been so great. Indeed, childhood obesity has been referenced as one of the most serious public health issues of the 21st Century by The WHO (World Health Organization, 2018a). As such, school-based interventions have commonly been delivered in schools as they are seen as an ideal setting to engage with various children from different background and foster health-conducive behaviours (Kriemler et al., 2011, Demetriou and Höner, 2012, Dobbins et al., 2013, Lonsdale et al., 2013). Nevertheless, recent reviews suggest such interventions are in fact, not effective in fostering health-conducive behaviours (Love, Adams and Sluijs, 2018, Norris et al., 2019, Jones et al., 2020).

School staff are under increasing pressure from curriculum demands, for example, one study found that healthy lifestyle teaching has to be delivered in assembly time, rather than lesson time, due to lack of time in the curriculum (Day, Sahota and Christian, 2019). Indeed, limited time for delivery (particularly programme components not incorporated into the curriculum) is a barrier to the effective implementation of primary school-based healthy lifestyle interventions (Day, Sahota and Christian, 2019). As such, this pressure may result in these interventions not being implemented as intended. Future school-based interventions should consider following the MRC guidelines for developing and evaluating complex interventions (Craig et al., 2008, Senn et al., 2013). In particular, future work should develop and identify theory as the rationale for a complex intervention and use multiple methods for process evaluation prior to implementing a fully powered trial (Craig et al., 2008, Senn et al., 2013). Furthermore, to facilitate sustainability, programmes need to be integrated within the

curriculum and school policies long term with sustained support from head teachers and staff (Day, Sahota and Christian, 2019).

8.3.2 Fidelity of School-based health interventions

There is no agreed consensus on the operationalisation of concepts and methods used for assessing fidelity in school-based interventions (Schaap et al., 2018). A recent systematic review of measuring implementation fidelity of school-based obesity prevention programmes suggests that logbooks, amongst other methods (e.g., observations, questionnaires) were the most common methods of measuring fidelity (Schaap et al., 2018). Although the MRC guidelines has increased recognition of the importance of using multiple methods when conducting process evaluations (i.e., usually a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods including observations, logbooks and questionnaires), guidance for the amalgamation and analyses of such data is lacking (Steckler and Linnan, 2002, Campbell et al., 2015, Van den Branden et al., 2015, Sebire, Edwards, et al., 2016, Griffin et al., 2017). However, expecting teachers who are already under pressure to deliver interventions and complete logbooks may be unreasonable due to their existing demanding schedules. As such, those involved in the design of future school-based interventions should be encouraged to not only evaluate the effectiveness of the delivery of the intended intervention, but also to aim for this process to be easily-undertaken and incorporated into the classroom to minimize disruption and maximize implementation.

8.3.3 Multi-setting interventions involving stakeholders

Homework interventions may alleviate the ever-increasing pressures schools face. Indeed these interventions have shown to be effective in fostering health-conducive behaviours when implemented with a compulsory-curriculum design (Duncan et al., 2011, 2019). However, to the best of our knowledge little evidence exists concerning the efficacy of such interventions and in-turn, the exploration of their fidelity. Interventions which transcend

the home to school may be essential to promote health behaviours as such behaviours vary across the home and school settings. For example, children are known to accumulate the least amount of daily MVPA on weekend days (Brooke et al., 2016). Furthermore, parents are influential in supporting children's activity in various ways including providing transportation and equipment, as well as enrolling children in opportunities for PA, which represent instrumental parental support behaviours associated with increased PA in children (Mitchell et al., 2012). Therefore, the involvement of parents in interventions aiming to improve children's health behaviours is highly encouraged.

8.3.4 Parent involvement in school-based health activities

Parent involvement in school-based interventions which aim to improve children's health behaviours has shown promising results on children's health behaviours (Niemeier, Hektner and Enger, 2012). Indeed, it has been suggested that school-based health interventions involving parents are more effective than interventions without a parent component (Van Cauwenberghe et al., 2010). However, such interventions tend to involve the most motivated parents who typically are of higher SES (Clarke et al., 2015, Ruiter et al., 2015). Researchers typically struggle to engage with hard-to-reach parents who are often less motivated and of lower SES (Robinson et al., 2016). As such, a small proportion of the target group are exposed to the intervention, who are often those least in need of behaviour change (Mytton et al., 2013). Chapter 4 (Study 1) provides recommendations to increase the involvement of parents in school-based health interventions, suggesting that joint parent-child activities, school trips and home-based activities would be positive ways to increase such involvement.

Schools should also consider the timing of events, the notice they provide to parents, and encourage other family members' participation to improve the home-school connection for families and parents with complex and conflicting demands. Chapter 5 (Study 2) found

that parent and child weekend MVPA and BMI was significantly related, and a significant negative direct effect of SES on child BMI was found. Additionally, a significant negative indirect effect of SES on child BMI via their parents BMI was also found. Furthermore, whilst Chapter 6 (Study 3) found no significant associations between parent-child activity, girls BMI z-score was found to be positively associated with parent inactive time and parent BMI, this was not observed for boys. Before developing an intervention to effectively improve children's health behaviour including their PA through the involvement of their parent, understanding more regarding the relationship between parent and child activity and its effect on weight explicitly is required. Future school-based interventions require a multidimensional intervention strategy across both the home and school settings to achieve sustained effects across the whole day (Love, Adams and Sluijs, 2018, Wyatt et al., 2018).

8.3.5 Parent and child PA and new accelerometry metrics

Parents own activity and their support to be active is known to positively influence children's activity (Brouwer et al., 2018). Nevertheless, conflicting research suggests that significant relationships in parent and child PA do not exist (Jago et al., 2010, Erkelenz et al., 2014). The findings within this thesis pertaining to the relationship between parent and child PA highlights the disagreement exemplified in prior research outputs. Findings from Chapter 5 (Study 2) indicate that parent MVPA influences children's MVPA, however only on weekend days. When applying novel and comparable accelerometry metrics in Chapter 6 (Study 3), findings revealed no significant associations between any of the parent and child activity outcomes.

8.3.6 Recommendations for future practice

- To involve parents in future interventions, parent and child joint activities and homework activities seem to be an appropriate and recommended practice.

- Interventions should be integrated within the curriculum and school policies to facilitate long-term support from head teachers and school staff
- Homework interventions embedded within the curriculum should aim to provide children with autonomy in the tasks they complete and encourage families to recognise the importance of such tasks in the promotion of positive health-related outcomes.

8.3.7 Recommendations for future research

- Further process evaluation of multi-component school-based PA interventions are warranted. Researchers should aim to create short fidelity logbooks in which teachers can complete efficiently within their classroom routine to avoid loss of data
- Researchers should aim to design and evaluate homework interventions which aim to encourage positive HWB; transcending from school to home.
- Understanding the relationship between parent and child activity and its effect on weight explicitly is required, as previous findings from research exploring the relationship between parent and child activity has remained equivocal for decades.

8.4 Conclusion.

As this thesis comes to an end, the series of studies provided add original contributions to knowledge concerning the relationship between parent and child PA and BMI, as well as the influence SES plays in mediating this relationship. Insightful and unheard perspective of mothers with low SES, regarding their involvement in their child's school-based health activities is provided. This thesis adds to the existing evidence base surrounding the design and evaluation of school-based interventions by evaluating a curriculum-based homework intervention aiming to improve health outcomes in children through an SDT approach within Chapter 7, Study 4. This study is the first to evaluate children's activity using novel accelerometry metrics in an intervention of this nature. With these findings, and

the findings from both cross-sectional studies exploring parent and child dyad PA and BMI through novel analyses (i.e., mediation analyses and novel metrics), this thesis identifies the potential to deliver an effective homework school-based intervention, informed by theory, which has the potential to relieve the burden school staff face in the delivery of such interventions, and demonstrates positive effects on health-related outcomes for children. Before progression to a full-scale effectiveness trial, additional procedures should be considered to improve recruitment rates in both parents and children with low SES, increase compliance with outcome measures, and improve the implementation of the home-based components within interventions which aim to foster health-conducive behaviours in children.

CHAPTER 9

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CHAPTER 10

APPENDICES

Appendix 1A: Study 1 Recruitment flyer

LET'S CHAT ABOUT HEALTH
EDUCATION

Parents, we'd like to hear your views!

VISIT SAMANTHA AT HER STALL ON PARENTS EVENING
TO SEE RESULTS FROM OUR PREVIOUS STUDIES
INVOLVING PARENTS AND SCHOOLS FROM
LANARKSHIRE

FIND OUT ABOUT OUR UPCOMING RESEARCH INVOLVING
PARENTS. COULD YOU BE INVOLVED?

WE NEED YOUR VIEWS TO INFORM HEALTH EDUCATION
POLICY. INTERVIEWS CAN BE VIA TELEPHONE AND AT
YOUR CONVENIENCE!

UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND
UWS

Appendix 1B: Study 1 Information sheet**PARENT INFORMATION SHEET**

Dear Parent,

We are present at your child's parents evening, as agreed to by this school's Head Teacher, to carry out research into HWB education and what parents think about their involvement in this education.

There is limited research to suggest the best ways to involve parents, especially those who may already find it difficult to be involved in schools. Therefore, your opinions are important in order to add to research which may improve parent involvement in children's HWB education. We may also contact you after our study to ensure the results we have found are an accurate representation of your opinions, so please provide an email address if possible.

We hope you are interested in taking part, which will involve filling out a short questionnaire, as well as possibly taking part in a short interview with one of our researchers from The University of the West of Scotland. These interviews will either take place during parents evening before or after you have spoken with your child's teacher or at a later date and time which suits you. We will also be offering telephone interviews to parents should this be easier for you to take part in our interviews.

All the data from the questionnaires and interviews are confidential and only accessed by our research team. The results from this study will also be anonymised to ensure you cannot be identified.

If this study is of interest to you, please speak with one of our researcher's onsite who will be happy to fill out a short consent form with you.

Yours faithfully,

Samantha Donnelly (PhD Student University of the West of Scotland)

For any further information please contact me by telephone on [REDACTED] or by email at [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 1C: Study 1 consent form**PARENT CONSENT FORM: CONFIDENTIAL**

Parent/Guardian's name: _____ Date: _____

Age: _____ Gender: _____

Occupation: _____

Postcode: _____

Home phone: _____ Mobile: _____

Email address (if applicable): _____

Relationship to the child: _____

Age of child: _____ Gender of child: _____ School child attends: _____

Number of children living at home: _____

Highest education qualification achieved: _____

Family type (e.g., single-parent family): _____

Please tick the boxes as appropriate:I _____ (name) agree to participate in this research of parent involvement I understand the information sheet provided I agree to be contacted by the research team via telephone for an interview I understand that my participation includes: *-Providing information attached in this sheet (e.g., postcode, occupation, etc.)**-Filling out a family involvement questionnaire**-Participating in a parent involvement interview with regards to your child's HWB education (either at parents evening, via telephone, or face-to-face at a later date)*

Preferred day and time to be contacted using telephone numbers provided above:

Option 1: Day: _____ Time: _____**Option 2:** Day: _____ Time: _____Preferred interview method (please tick): Face-to-face interview Telephone interview

Signature _____ (parent)

Appendix 1D: Study 1 FIQ-E (School-based involvement sub-scale) (Manz, Fantuzzo and Power, 2004)

FAMILY INVOLVEMENT QUESTIONNAIRE- ELEMENTARY VERSION:
CONFIDENTIAL

Parent name: _____ School: _____

Directions: For each item, please circle how often (*Rarely, Sometimes, Often, or Always*) you perform the activity.

	<i>Rarely</i>	<i>Sometimes</i>	<i>Often</i>	<i>Always</i>
1. Suggest activities or trips to teacher	1	2	3	4
2. Attend parent workshops or training at school	1	2	3	4
3. Take child to school	1	2	3	4
4. Volunteer in classroom	1	2	3	4
5. Participate in fundraising activities at school	1	2	3	4
6. Go on class trips	1	2	3	4
7. Arrange times for classmates to come play	1	2	3	4
8. Talk to parents about school meetings and events	1	2	3	4
9. Pick child up from school	1	2	3	4
10. Talk to school personnel about job training	1	2	3	4
11. Parents at school support each other	1	2	3	4
12. Attend organized family–school association meetings	1	2	3	4
13. Meet with families outside of school	1	2	3	4

Appendix 1E: Study 1 Interview guide

Just to re-introduce myself, my name is Samantha and I am a PhD Student from The University of the West of Scotland. We are looking to interview parents about their involvement in healthy lifestyle education. In this interview I'd like for us to go into detail discussing your views and involvement in your child's education of having a healthy lifestyle, sticking to the issues surrounding diet, sitting time (including screen time) and physical activity (including sport, physical education, active playtime). We say this interview normally lasts around 45 mins. However, it may be shorter or longer, depending on the interview.

Your responses will be recorded but will be kept anonymous and everything you say will be kept confidential. Absolutely nothing you say will be reported to teachers or school management. You are free to stop participating at any point and do not have to answer every question.

Warm up question

So initially I'd just like to get some background information about you, your family and school your children go to.

Could you tell me a little bit about yourself and your family?

- *If they don't mention partner ask*> Is it yourself at home or do you have a partner?

- *If they don't mention employment ask*> what does yourself/ your partner do for work?

Could you tell me a little bit about the school your child attends (e.g., staff, pupils, initiatives)?

So, we are interested in lots of different families and the views of parents within these families, without making any judgements. This interview is in no way an assessment of you as a parent, and I really encourage you to be as honest as possible.

General School & Relationship

What would you say your relationship is like with the school?

- Would you say you trust the school? If so why, if not why not?
- How much communication is there between you and the school?
- Do you feel you can voice your opinion on your involvement with school's promotion and teaching of healthy lifestyles?
- Do you feel your opinion is heard? (if so, why and if not why not?)

What does the school do to encourage parents to get involved in the school?

- Have you attended any of these? If so why, if not why not?
- What could the school do to get you involved in more of these activities?

School healthy lifestyles and parent involvement

Now I'd like for us to go into detail discussing your views on your child's education of having a healthy lifestyle, again sticking to the issues surrounding diet, sitting time (including screen time) and physical activity (including sport, physical education, active playtime, etc.).

Can you tell me about what the school does to encourage the children to have healthy lifestyles?

- What programs, if any, do you know of that the school have in place to encourage healthy lifestyles?
- How did you hear about these programmes?
- Do these programmes come with costs to participate?
- What was your child's experience of this project/activity?
- What, if any effect did it have on your child?

So, as we know the school plays a really important role in helping your child understand what is required in order to have a healthy lifestyle, however, often the best way to promote a healthy, happy lifestyle is when schools and parents work together.

Are there any programs the school runs to encourage parents to get involved in the education of healthy lifestyles or similar activities (e.g., school trips, sports day help, baking, and talk about your job)?

- We understand parents are busy; however, the school does have... Is this a program which you would be interesting in attending?
- How did you hear about the programme/activity?
- What encouraged you to be involved?
- What was yours and your child's experience? (e.g., how enjoyable/helpful was it?)
- What, if anything, discouraged you from being involved?

In general, what, if anything, would you say makes you want to be involved in the school's promotion of having healthy lifestyles?

- Can you discuss this a little more?
- Is there anything else that makes you want to be involved in this?

What, if anything, would you prevent you from being involved in your child's education of healthy lifestyles?

- If anything, what could make this easier?

How much communication is there between you and the school regarding the education of healthy lifestyles and the topics covered in class?

- How do they generally pass on information to parents about healthy lifestyle education and projects?
- Do you think it is enough?
- Is there anything they could do to improve it?
- Are there opportunities for you to provide feedback or suggestions?

What do you think other parents could do to encourage parent involvement in children's education of healthy lifestyles?

School-parent relationship

What things would you like to see happen to encourage your involvement with the school with regards to your child's learning of healthy lifestyles?

-If schools provided these opportunities, would you participate?

Not all parents feel connected or involved with the school for whatever reason,

- What do you think the school could do to encourage the less involved parents at your school in to be more involved?
- What do you think the school could do in order encourage less involved parents to participate in healthy lifestyle projects at the schools?
- Is this something you think could also improve your own involvement?

So that was our last question, before we finish, is there anything else at all you would like to say about your involvement in your child's learning of healthy lifestyles?

We will be conducting a study later on this year, hoping to measure physical activity levels between parents and their child. Would you be interested in this study and agree to be contacted at a later date to possibly participate?

Ok great! Thank you for your time, we really appreciate it. We will be in touch with you with our results for you to confirm their accuracy with your opinions from today. [Obtain verification of email address at this point]. Also, just as reminder all your responses will remain confidential. Thanks again!

Appendix 2A: Study 2 and Study 3 Parent information sheet

PARENT-CHILD PHYSICAL ACTIVITY STUDY: INFORMATION SHEET

Dear Parent (primary caregiver),

A research team from the University of the West of Scotland is undertaking a study of parent-child physical activity levels, a project which has been approved by the University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee. The aim of this study is to gain an in-depth understanding of the relationship of parent-child physical activity levels through the examination of parent-child physical activity levels over a 7-day period. We aim to do this through the use of wrist-worn accelerometer devices and physical activity questionnaires. You and your child (**please only pick one child**) will be required to wear the wrist-worn device for 7 consecutive days (an accelerometer information sheet will be provided to you). We also ask that you keep track of you and your child's sleep duration and wear-time of the device over the 7 days (again this sheet will be provided to you) as well as a Physical Activity questionnaire. Your child will also fill out a Physical Activity questionnaire at the end of the study in their classroom.

We also know that there are many influencing factors which can determine the physical activity levels of parents and their child. Therefore, we also will ask you to fill out a short demographic form providing us with information such as your home postcode, highest education qualification achieved and occupation. A family involvement questionnaire will also be provided to you at the end of the study.

We will provide an accelerometer for you and your child. We ask that you ensure the accelerometer is worn each day by yourself and your child. **The accelerometer with a RED, CREAM, GREEN or WHITE strap is to be worn by the adult participant. The accelerometer with the BLACK strap is to be worn by the child participant.** Once you are provided with the accelerometer, we ask that you and your child wear it immediately, and thereon for 7 days. Once you and your child have worn the accelerometer for 7 full days, we ask you to return these accelerometers to the school, where you will be asked to hand back your pack with the accelerometers and questionnaires, as well as having your height and weight recorded. The accelerometer information sheet provided to you will detail the date we require you to return the accelerometers to the school office. As a research team, we sincerely hope that you agree for you and your child to participate in this project, but please ensure that your child is also happy to participate. While you are free to withdraw from the study at any time, we hope the study will be enjoyable, interesting and education for all!

Warmest regards,

Samantha Donnelly (PhD Student, University of the West of Scotland)

For any further information please contact me by telephone [REDACTED] or by email at [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 2B: Study 2 and Study 3 consent form**CHILD CONSENT FORM COMPLETED BY THE PARENT: CONFIDENTIAL**

Parent (Primary Caregiver's) name: _____

Age: _____ Gender: _____

Occupation: _____ Household income (approx.):

Postcode: _____

Home phone: _____ Mobile: _____

Email address (if applicable): _____

Relationship to the child: _____

Number of children living at home: _____

Highest education qualification achieved (e.g., college degree): _____

Family type (e.g., single-parent family): _____

Child's name: _____ School child attends:

Year child is in: _____ Classroom child is in: _____

Age of child: _____ Gender of child: _____

Please tick the boxes as appropriate:I _____ (name) agree to myself and my child's participation in this research I understand the information sheet provided to me I understand that myself and my child's participation includes: *-Providing information attached in this sheet (e.g., postcode, occupation, etc.)**-My child will wear an accelerometer for 7 days and bringing the accelerometer back to this school on the 8th day along with the documents provided to me which are to be returned.**-Filling out the relevant questionnaires**-My child will have their height and weight recorded*

Signature: _____ (parent)

Date: _____

Appendix 3A: Study 4 Head teacher information sheet

Dear Sir/Madam,

Researchers at The University of the West of Scotland will be conducting a study, examining activity behaviour profiles in children. Whilst researchers from around the world have assessed this, children (in particular those from Scotland) remain alarmingly inactive, failing to meet recommended guidelines.

We are aiming to examine if an 8-week homework programme focused on increasing activity in children can impact upon childhood inactivity in Scottish children. Whilst some research has found this to be unsuccessful, a study which examined the effect of compulsory healthy homework on children's activity found success!

In order to conduct a study of this nature, we require the recruitment of schools which receive the homework tasks and those which do not. Should you agree for your school to participate in this study, and are not chosen as the school which receives the homework, once the study has finished, we will be happy to provide your school with the results, and the homework programme.

We would require access to one class (9-10-year olds) and would examine the following at two time-points (1 week before the intervention and during the final week):

- Physical activity and sleep (using a wrist-worn device)
- Sedentary behaviours including screen-time (using a thigh worn device and self-reported by parents)
- Height and weight
- Questionnaires with teachers and parents
- Write, draw, show and tell sessions with pupils

We would also like to provide you, your teacher and the class identified with the opportunity to review the homework sessions and together, chose 8 preferred weeks. From this, the researchers will refine the sessions in line with choices from the schools. Studies of this nature allow schools to include parents in activities relating to aims within their school improvement plan, and can be enjoyable for all involved.

I hope to hear from you soon.

Warmest regards,

Samantha Donnelly (Primary Investigator)

PhD Student at the University of the West of Scotland

████████████████████

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 3B: Head teacher consent sheet**HEAD TEACHER CONSENT FORM: CONFIDENTIAL****PRIMARY SCHOOL:** _____**Please tick the boxes as appropriate:**

I _____ (name) agree for my school to be used for the purposes of this study

I understand the information sheet provided to me

I understand that the participation of my school includes:

- **Attendance of UWS Research staff at school to collect consent forms from interested parents and pupils**
- **Possible random selection to use homework tasks in one class**
- **Measures including height and weight, the distribution of 2 devices and a write, draw, show and tell session on activity with children from the class.**
- **Attendance at school to collect devices and questionnaires**

Signature: _____ (head teacher)

Date: _____

Appendix 3C: Study 4 Classroom teacher information sheet

Dear Class Teacher,

Researchers at The University of the West of Scotland will be conducting a study, examining activity behaviour profiles in children. Whilst researchers from around the world have assessed this, children (in particular those from Scotland) remain alarmingly inactive, failing to meet recommended guidelines.

We are aiming to examine if a 6-week homework programme focused on increasing activity in children can impact upon childhood inactivity in Scottish children. Whilst some research has found this to be unsuccessful, a study which examined the effect of a compulsory homework programme delivered by teachers to be effective!

In order to conduct a study of this nature, we require the recruitment of schools which receive the homework tasks and those which do not. Should your Headteacher agree for your school to participate in this study, however your school is not chosen as the school which receives the homework, once the study has finished, we will be happy to provide your school with the results, and the homework programme.

We would require access to your class and would examine the following at two time-points (1 week before the intervention and during the final week):

- Physical activity and sleep (using a wrist-worn device)
- Sedentary behaviours including screen-time (using a thigh worn device and self-reported by parents)
- Height and weight
- Questionnaires with teachers and parents
- Write, draw, show and tell sessions with pupils

We would also like to provide you and your class with the opportunity to review the homework sessions and together, chose 8 weeks preferred weeks. From this, the researchers will refine the sessions in line with choices from the schools.

We would also provide you with a log book to keep track of the homework programme and stickers which would go in the pupil's HH workbook.

We would design this programme with teacher's in-mind, providing as much support as each teacher would require. Your feedback is very important to us.

I hope to hear from you soon.

Warmest regards,

Samantha Donnelly (Primary Investigator)

PhD Student at the University of the West of Scotland

████████████████████

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 3D: Study 4 Teacher consent document

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

TEACHER CONSENT FORM: **CONFIDENTIAL**

PRIMARY SCHOOL: _____

Please tick the boxes as appropriate:

I _____ (name) agree to participate in this study

I understand the information sheet provided to me

I understand that the participation of myself and my pupils includes:

- **Attendance of UWS Research staff at school to collect consent forms from interested parents and pupils**

- Possible random selection to use homework tasks in your class
- Measures including height and weight, the distribution of 2 devices and a write, draw, show and tell session on activity with children from the class.
- Teacher questionnaire on the homework programme
- Keep track of pupils who complete task in logbook

Signature: _____ (teacher)

Date: _____

Appendix 3E: Study 4 Child information sheet

CHILD INFORMATION SHEET

A group of scientists from The University of the West of Scotland are doing an experiment to measure Scottish children's activity levels.

This experiment will measure:

- How active you are
- How long you sleep for
- Screen-time
- Your height and weight

This experiment will be split up into 2 time points:

1. Week 1
2. Week 7

You will take part in the study at both these time points.

To measure how much exercise you do, you will wear a device around the wrist you do not write with for 7 days. You will also wear a device attached to your thigh for the same 7 days.

We will take your height and weight during class time, and may also invite you to take part in a short write, draw, show and tell session all about activity!

You do not have to take part in this experiment, and you can drop out at any time.

Thank you for reading!

Samantha Donnelly (PhD Student)

For any further information please have a chat with your parent/guardian who can contact the research team by telephone [REDACTED] or by email at [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 3F: Study 4 Child consent form**CHILD CONSENT FORM: CONFIDENTIAL**

Please tick the boxes as appropriate:

I _____ (name) agree to my participation in this research

Information on the study has been explained to me via the information sheet

I understand that my participation includes:

-Wearing 2 devices for 7 days and bringing it back to the school office

-Having my height and weight recorded and completing a questionnaire

-Possibly participating in a short write, draw, show and tell group on activity

Signature: _____ (Child)

Date: _____

Appendix 3G: Study 4 Parent information sheet**PARENT INFORMATION SHEET**

Dear Parent,

A research team from the University of the West of Scotland is undertaking a study examining children's activity behaviour profiles. Your child's class has been chosen to participate in the research study.

To examine children's activity behaviour profiles, the following measures will be taken:

- Physical activity levels
- Nutrition
- Sedentary behaviours including screen-time
- Sleep duration
- Body mass index.
- Write, draw, show and tell group (pupils)

These measures will be conducted at two time-points; 1) Week 1 of the intervention (registration week), and 2) Week 8 of the intervention (second-last week). Should you and your child agree to participate in the study; your child will wear an accelerometer on their non-dominant wrist and a small device on their right thigh for 7 consecutive days at both time points, along with having their height and weight recorded. Your child will also complete a Day in the Life Questionnaire to measure their diet. You will be required to fill out: a short demographic form, a form on your child's screen-time, and a short questionnaire on home-based learning. No costs/expenses are associated with your participation in this study.

The data you provide us with will be kept confidential within the research team and will therefore not be shared with school personnel. Your participation along with that of your child's is completely voluntary, and you are both free to withdraw from the study at any point. We hope you chose to participate in our study and add to research!

Warmest regards,

Samantha Donnelly (PhD Student) and Dr Rosie Arthur (Director of Studies)

For any further information please contact the research team by [REDACTED] or by email at [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 3H: Study 4 Parent consent form**PARENT CONSENT FORM: CONFIDENTIAL**

Parent (Primary Caregiver's) name: _____
 Age: _____ Gender: _____
 Occupation: _____ Household income (approx.): _____
 Postcode: _____ Home phone: _____
 Mobile: _____ Appropriate day and time to be contacted for interview: _____
 Email address (if applicable): _____
 Relationship to the child: _____
 Number of children living at home: _____
 Highest education qualification achieved (e.g., college degree): _____
 Family type (e.g., single-parent family): _____

Child's name: _____ School child attends: _____
 Year child is in: _____ Classroom child is in: _____
 Age of child: _____ Date of birth: _____ Gender of child: _____

Please tick the boxes as appropriate:

I _____ (name) agree to myself and my child's participation in this research

I understand the information sheet provided to me

I understand that myself and my child's participation includes:

-Providing information attached in this sheet (e.g., postcode, occupation, etc.) and complete a family involvement and diet questionnaire and participating in a short telephone interview (recorded)

-My child will wear 2 accelerometer devices for 7 days over 2 time points (7 weeks apart) and will return the devices to their school on the 8th day along with the completed documents/questionnaires.

-My child will have their height, weight and waist circumference recorded at 2 time points (7 weeks apart)

Signature: _____ (parent)

Date: _____

Samantha Donnelly PhD Student (Primary Investigator)

Please contact me with any questions you may have: _____

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 3I: Study 4 Accelerometry device information

DEVICE INFORMATION

Parent’s name: _____ School: _____

Childs name: _____ Year and classroom number: _____

Wrist worn accelerometer:

Please ensure the device is worn on your child’s non-dominant wrist. So, if your child is right handed, they would wear the accelerometer on their left wrist. Please ensure your child wears the device for 24 hours a day for 7 days (including during sleep). **During water-based activities such as bathing and swimming this wrist-worn device must be removed as it is not water-proof.**

Childs non-dominant wrist: Left Right

Thigh worn device:

Please ensure the device is worn on your child’s right leg, 24 hours a day for 7 days (including during sleep). This device has been made waterproof and therefore does not have to be removed during water-based activities. **The device must remain in the white balloon at all times.** The drawing indicates the direction of the device (so it is not applied upside down). Additional tape has been provided.

Sleep:

Record the days and times your child went to bed and the times they woke up (e.g., Mon 7:30am – 8pm)

DAYS	1:	2:	3:	4:	5:	6:	7:
Awake							
Asleep							

We ask you to return the devices and relevant documents to the school’s office where they will be picked up by a member of the research team.

Thank you again for your participation in this study!

Please contact Samantha Donnelly at [REDACTED] should you have any questions relating to this study.

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 3J: HH example A

WEEK ONE - HOMEWORK SESSION ONE

TASK ONE YOGA

HAPPY HOMEWORK

It's always great to stretch off before we take part in activities. This can warm your muscles and improve range of motion. Let's use this week to stretch! Come up with a word and every time someone says this word, whether it be on the television or in conversation you could perform some **YOGA** poses.

OPTION A: Child's Pose

- Begin on hands and knees
- Spread knees wide apart while keeping big toes touching
- Sit straight up and lengthen your spine
- Bow forward, draping your torso between your thighs
- Keep your arms long and extended

OPTION B: Downward Dog

- Start in Child's Pose
- Curl your toes under and lift your hips up and back
- Push up and back with your thigh muscles
- Keep your arms long and extended

TASK TWO FRUIT AND VEGETABLES

Your task for this week's homework is to eat your 5+ a day (fruit and vegetables). 1 serving of fruit or vegetables is the amount that fits into the palm of your child's hand.

REMINDER

- Tonight, try and get to **bed** earlier than you normally would
- Avoid **glaring screens** close to bed time
- Stay **active** throughout the day tomorrow

Parent/Guardian Signature to collect happy face sticker:

Appendix 3K: HH example B

WEEK TWO – MONDAY HOMEWORK

Well done on completing Week 1 – remember to collect your HAPPY STICKER!

HAPPY HOMEWORK

TASK 1 SPELLING WORKOUTS

Spell your name workout using the form provided. Make sure you take a note of the workout you performed in the box bellow. Once you have spelled your name out, why not pick a word you are learning in class or even a vegetable?

Remember to keep moving throughout the day! Why not pick a word after dinner and complete the workout again.

TASK 2 WEEKLY NUTRITION

- Over the rest of the week, why don't you look at the labels on packaged goods and compare the energy some foods provide us with as opposed to other foods.
- Why don't you draw out some of the labels! Make sure you colour in the different sections red, amber or green (see example bellow).
- You could then try swapping something you normally eat which has red and orange labels for food with more green labels

Each serving (150g) contains

Energy	Fat	Saturates	Sugars	Salt
1046kJ 250kcal	3.0g LOW	1.3g LOW	34g HIGH	0.9g MED
13%	4%	7%	38%	15%

of an adult's reference intake
Typical values (as sold) per 100g:697kJ/167kcal

Parent/Guardian signature to collect happy face sticker:

Appendix 3L: DILQ (Edmunds and Ziebland, 2002)

A DAY IN THE LIFE OF...

Name _____ Age _____
 Girl Boy Date _____

What did you do?

YESTERDAY MORNING

1 Did you have something to eat and drink for breakfast? (What did you have?)

_____ drink _____

My Breakfast

Draw your breakfast here.

2 Did you watch television yesterday morning?

YES	NO
-----	----

3 Did you eat or drink anything on the way to school? (What did you have?)

4 How did you travel to school in the morning?

Walk	Cycle	By Bus	By Car

YESTERDAY AT SCHOOL

5 Did you have a morning break? YES NO

If you had a morning break, did you have anything to eat or drink?

YES (What did you have?) NO

6 If you had a morning break, what did you do at morning break yesterday?

Sit around	Stand around	Walk around	Run around

7 Did you have something to eat and drink for lunch yesterday? (What did you have?)

_____ drink _____

My Lunch

Draw your lunch here.

8 What did you do at lunchtime yesterday?

Sit around	Stand around	Walk around	Run around

AFTER SCHOOL

9 How did you travel home after school or your after school activity yesterday?

Walk	Cycle	By Bus	By Car

10 Did you eat or drink anything when you were travelling home? (What did you have?)

11 After school yesterday, did you:

<input type="checkbox"/>	go home?			
<input type="checkbox"/>	go to a club or after school activity?			
<input type="checkbox"/>	go somewhere else?			

12 Did you have anything to eat, or something to drink between the end of school (apart from the journey) and your evening meal? (What did you have?)

AFTER SCHOOL (continued)

13 Did you play outside yesterday after school? Yes No

14 Did you have an evening meal yesterday?
(What did you have?)

_____ drink _____

My Evening Meal

Draw your evening meal here.

15

Did you watch television yesterday evening?

YES NO

16 Did you do anything else after your evening meal yesterday? (What did you do?)

17 Did you have anything else to eat or drink between your evening meal and before you went to bed? (What did you have?)

THANK YOU VERY MUCH!

Appendix 3M: ST questionnaire

Screen time record PRE / POST

School: _____

Child's name: _____ Year and class: _____

Do you have (circle your answer):

A television in your bedroom: YES / NO

A computer in your bedroom: YES / NO

Circle how often you normally fall asleep with a screen on (TV, Tablet, Mobile phone): 1.NEVER 2.RARELY 3.SOMETIMES 4.OFTEN 5.ALWAYS

In the table below please report your typical time on a weekday (before and after school) and weekend day spent watching television, playing computer/video games, and using your mobile phone ranging from:

None, less than 1 hour, 1, 2, 3, 4 or more or equal to 5 HOURS.

	What times do you tend to do these activities during the Week ?		How long for? (hours)	What times do you tend to do these activities during the Weekend ?		How long for? (hours)
	Before school	After school		AM	PM	
Mobile phone and tablet use						
Watching television (without looking at a phone or tablet)						
Playing computer/video games sat down (x-box, Nintendo)						

Appendix 3N: Study 4 FIQ-E (home-based learning sub-scale) (Manz, Fantuzzo and Power, 2004)

Family Involvement Questionnaire: **CONFIDENTIAL**

Parent name: _____ School: _____

Child's name: _____ Year and class: _____

Directions: For each item, please circle how often (*Rarely, Sometimes, Often, or Always*) you perform the activity.

	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
1. Limit TV and video watching	1	2	3	4
2. Review child's school work	1	2	3	4
3. Take child to library	1	2	3	4
4. Keep regular morning and bedtime schedule	1	2	3	4
5. Share stories with child about when in school	1	2	3	4
6. Take child to places in community to learn special things	1	2	3	4
7. Check that child has place to keep school materials	1	2	3	4
8. Read with child	1	2	3	4
9. Bring home learning materials	1	2	3	4
10. Maintain clear rules at home	1	2	3	4
11. Ask child about day at school	1	2	3	4
12. Child has chores at home	1	2	3	4
13. Do creative activities with child	1	2	3	4
14. Spend time working on math skills	1	2	3	4
15. Help with homework	1	2	3	4
16. Talk to family and friends about child's school progress	1	2	3	4
17. Talk to child about how school helped caregiver	1	2	3	4

Appendix 30: Study 4 Teacher interview guide

Just to re-introduce myself, I am Samantha and I am a PhD Student from the University of the West of Scotland. I am talking with you today to discuss the HH intervention in detail and gain feedback on this intervention. This intervention is in its early stages; therefore, I encourage you to be as honest as possible as the feedback you provide us with in this interview will allow us to improve upon the intervention and highlight any positive areas of the intervention. To make you aware, this interview will be recorded for the purposes of our study, which will allow us to have the interview transcribed and then analysed as part of a PhD study which we hope to have published as a journal article and add to research on school-based interventions. Anything you say today will remain confidential with the research team and your identity will remain anonymous. We expect the interview to last around 30 mins. Please feel free to skip any questions should you not want to answer any. You can also end the interview at any point. If you are ready, let's get started.

So, can you tell me a little about yourself and the class you teach?

Tell me about your teaching of HWB?

Previous to the HH activities, what if any homework did you hand out to your class for HWB?

Can you tell me a little about the completion rates of these homework's?

What was your initial thoughts regarding the HH activities?

How did you find implementing the HH activities?

Were there any weeks you preferred over others? (Will provide list of weeks)

Can you tell me what you thought of the Easter activities?

What, if anything, were some positives you took from the HH activities?

What, if anything, were some negatives you took from the HH activities?

Whilst we have collected completion information of the activities, overall as a class, how would you describe the completion of the activities?

If anything, what feedback did you receive from the pupils?

If anything, what feedback did you receive from parents?

Could you provide us with some feedback regarding the happy face stickers to encourage the pupils to complete the activities?

If we asked you to provide us with some key recommendations to improve the HH activities, what comes to mind?

Is there anything you feel you would like to add that we have not covered regarding the HH activities?

Ok, if you're happy we will end the interview here. Thank you again for your participation in this study. Please feel free to contact me if you have any questions or anything else you'd like to add at a later date. We will be in contact with you at a later date with an overview of the interview in which you can review to assure your perceptions were captured. I'll stop the recording now, thank you again.

Appendix 3P: Study 4 WDST group interview guide

Write, Draw, Show and Tell Group. School: _____ Date: _____

Setting:

Area where children can be seen but not overheard

Circular seating arrangement with researcher sat with children

Researcher and children address each other by first name

Introduction:

“Hi everyone! I would first of all like to thank you for being here and I hope we can make this session as fun as possible. For anyone who doesn’t know, my name is Samantha and I am a scientist from the University of the West of Scotland.”

Assent: Verbal explanation of research purpose, processes involved and data uses:

“We are here today to talk to you about physical activity and learn a little bit about your experiences of being physically active. We will collect information here today and we will then put this information together with other boys and girls’ experiences from other schools. This will then provide my team at the university with a good understanding of boys and girls experiences of physical activity and this will then be written up into different types of reports.”

Verbal explanation of structure and context of WDST group:

“So, in this group, we will start off by introducing ourselves to get familiar with each other. Once we do this, I will ask everyone to write down ‘5 words to best describe physical activity to someone else.’ You will also be asked to draw an environment where you were most likely to participate in physical activity. After this, we will all have a conversation about our experiences of physical activity. Is everyone here happy to take part? Just to double check, if anyone here does not want to participate you can say now.”

Obtain verbal child assent: (tick if provided)

Show:

Interactive ice breaker activity

“Let’s go around the table and say your name and your favourite topic to learn about in class. Before we do this, it is very important that we make sure we listen to everyone and be respectful when other people are talking. So, let’s get started...”

Write and Draw:

Provide children with post-it note paper and a pencil and ask them to:

“Write down 5 words to best describe physical activity to someone else.”

Ask the children to provide a verbal explanation of the meaning being their written responses then have the children place these on a board in front of them and discuss the responses as a group.

Invite the children to independently draw an environment where they were most likely to participate in physical activity.

Throughout this activity, separately engage children in informal conversation for them to articulate what there are drawing and why (e.g., 'and what about you Joe? Can you tell me what's going on in your picture?')

Tell: Person-centred (encourage child to talk about themselves).

Challenging open-ended questioning surrounding the children's experiences of physical activity (Autonomous or controlled), providing children with various opportunities to speak about individual PA interests and experiences.

Need-supportive versus controlling contexts (3 basic psychological needs):

Relatedness

Over the past week, what sorts of physical activities have you done outside of school?

Can you tell me where you did the activity and who it was with?

Can you tell me who you like to participate in physical activities with most?

Why do you like to participate in physical activities with this group more than others?

What sorts of things do your parents or carers do, if anything, which encourages you be more active?

Did your parents/carers participate in the HH activities with you?

If so, tell me about your experience of participating in the HH Activities with your parents/cares?

- Supported by parents/carers when participating in the HH Activities?
- Cared for by parents/carers participating in the HH Activities?

How would you describe your relationship with you parents/carers after participating in the HH Activities together?

Autonomy/choice

Can you tell me a little bit about whether or not you got any opportunities to make choices in the activities you carried out for the HH Activities?

Were there times when you felt you didn't have options in the HH activities you completed?

Were there times when you felt pressure to complete the HH Activities?

Competence

Can you tell me about your experience of participating in the HH activities?

How capable did you feel you were when performing the HH activities?

Did you find anything challenging in the HH Activities?

Were you able to overcome challenges in the HH Activities over time?

Once you completed the HH weeks, did anyone feel a sense of accomplishment?

Before we finish, does anyone have anything they would like to add to our conversation about the HH activities or about being active in general?

Thank you for participating in our discussion today! You can all head back into class now.

Appendix 3Q: Study 4 WDST illustration example A

Unpublished work without informed consent for publication. Children's drawing. [Further details may be obtained from the author.]

Appendix 3R: Study 4 WDST illustration example B

Unpublished work without informed consent for publication. Children's drawing. [Further details may be obtained from the author.]